

Diverse Solutions, Modifying Graph Eigenvalues and Bounded-Width ABPs

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Chapter 0

Introduction

In this thesis, we study the following three themes:

Diverse Pair of Solutions

When a real-world problem is modelled as a computational problem, some information is often lost. So, while two solutions may be equally good for the theoretical formulation, one of them may be better than the other for the actual practical application. For example, consider the six wireless devices and their conflict network shown in Figure 1, where an edge joining two devices indicates that they have the same operating frequency and so, the frequency request of at least one of them must be denied to avoid interference. The goal is to minimize the number of denied requests. The three solutions highlighted in the figure have the same size; however, in practice, the user may prefer the first solution over the second solution, and the second solution over the third solution. This is because MP3 player and home theater are merely for entertainment, whereas denying baby monitor's request and laptop's request may risk baby's life and cause delay in urgent office work respectively. In this example, a natural fix is to add weights to the devices according to their respective importance, and then minimize the total weight of the solution. However, in general, accounting for external factors may be difficult, or even impossible when not all such factors are known beforehand.

This issue can be fixed by providing multiple solutions (instead of just one solution) to the user, who may then pick the solution that best fulfills her/his need. However, if the solutions so provided are all quite similar to each other, they may exhibit almost identical behaviours when judged on the basis of any relevant external factor. Thus, to ensure that the user is able to meaningfully compare the given solutions and hand-pick one of them, she/he must be provided a collection of *diverse solutions*, i.e., a few solutions that are sufficiently dissimilar/far apart from each other, for some suitable notion of dissimilarity/distance between solutions. The framework of *diversity* was proposed by Baste et al. [10]. Since the late 2010s, several graph-theoretic and matching problems have been studied in this setting from an algorithmic standpoint. These include diverse variants of vertex cover [11], feedback vertex set [11], hitting set [11], perfect/maximum matching [37], stable matching [41], weighted basis and common independent set of matroids [38], minimum s - t cut [16] and spanning tree [47].

In Chapter 1, we study i) complexity of finding a diverse pair of compatible perfect non-crossing matchings (NCMs) for points in convex position, and ii) complexity of finding a perfect NCM that is maximally far-apart from a given base perfect NCM for points in convex position. The latter problem is an example where the concept of distance between solutions is brought in to generalize the *Another Solution Problem*; in ASP (see [84]), the goal is to check whether a solution different from a given base solution exists. In Chapter 2, we study the complexity of finding a diverse pair of satisfying assignments for affine, 2-CNF and Hitting formulas.

Figure 1: An example conflict network on six wireless devices. Three solutions (i.e., sets of devices denying whose requests ensures that no two of the remaining devices can interfere with each other) are highlighted: {Laptop, Mobile, Baby camera} (green), {Laptop, Mobile, MP3 player} (orange), {Home theater, Mobile, MP3 player}(blue).

Modifying Graphs to Bound the Number of Distinct Eigenvalues

A graph modification problem asks whether an input graph can be modified within a given budget so that the resulting graph satisfies a certain property. For example, with vertex deletion as the modification, we get the Minimum Vertex Cover, Feedback Vertex Set and Odd-Cycle Transversal problems for the properties edge-freeness, cycle-freeness and odd-cycle-freeness respectively. In Chapter 3, we study the complexity of graph modification when the adjacency matrix of the resulting graph is required to have $\leq r$ distinct eigenvalues. Unlike the three example properties, this property is not hereditary, i.e., the adjacency matrix of a subgraph may have more number of distinct eigenvalues than the adjacency matrix of the whole graph (see an example in Figure 2). We consider four modifications: vertex deletion, edge deletion, edge addition, edge editing. This question was posed by Meesum et al. in 2016 in their work on graph modification to reduce rank of the adjacency matrix [64] as follows: “[...] what is complexity of the problem of reducing the number of distinct eigenvalues of a graph by deleting a few vertices or editing a few edges?”

three distinct eigenvalues: $-2, 1, 3$

four distinct eigenvalues: $\pm \left(\frac{\sqrt{5}+1}{2}\right), \pm \left(\frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2}\right)$

Figure 2: This example shows that the adjacency matrix having $\leq r$ distinct eigenvalues is a non-hereditary property. While the adjacency matrix of the graph shown on the left (i.e., Petersen graph) has three distinct eigenvalues, the adjacency matrix of its subgraph induced by four consecutive vertices on the boundary of its outer pentagon (i.e., a path on four vertices) has four distinct eigenvalues.

There is a one-sided connection between rank and number of distinct eigenvalues of adjacency matrix. If adjacency matrix has small rank, then it can have only a few distinct eigenvalues.

More precisely, applying *rank-nullity theorem* [82] on adjacency matrix of an n -vertex graph, we get that the sum of its rank and nullity (i.e., multiplicity of eigenvalue 0) is n . So, as it has n eigenvalues in total (counted with multiplicities), the number of non-zero eigenvalues (again, counted with multiplicities) equals the rank. Thus, overall, the number of distinct eigenvalues can only be at most one more than the rank. In contrast, if adjacency matrix has a few distinct eigenvalues, then its rank need not be small. For example, the adjacency matrix of an n -vertex complete graph has just two distinct eigenvalues (i.e., -1 and $n - 1$), whereas its rank is $n - 1$. So, rank can be arbitrarily larger than the number of distinct eigenvalues.

Bounded-Width Algebraic Branching Programs

Since the advent of Turing machines in 1936 (see [75]), computational problems have been classified into complexity classes based on the number of cells (i.e., space) and the number of steps (i.e., time) needed by TMs to solve them. The notions of *reductions* and *completeness* are used to study the relative computational hardness of problems. A reduction describes how to obtain an algorithm to solve one problem given an algorithm that solves another problem; so, the latter problem is *at least as hard as* the former problem. In this sense, the hardest problems of a class are known as its complete problems. In early 1970s, Levin [59], Cook [24], Karp [56] and others initiated a study of NP-completeness, where NP is the class of *decision problems* (i.e., with YES/NO answers) whose YES instances have efficiently verifiable proofs.

Soon after, in a similar spirit, a theory comparing the complexities of computing polynomials (instead of problems) started to emerge. In 1979, Valiant laid an algebraic framework of complexity theory (see [77]), where sequences of polynomials are classified based on the sizes of algebraic models (e.g., *formulas, circuits, algebraic branching programs*) used to compute them. These models involve algebraic operations (i.e., additions and multiplications). The algebraic analogue of reductions are known as *projections*. A polynomial f is said to be a projection of another polynomial g if f can be obtained from g by substituting each of its indeterminates by an indeterminate or a constant. This leads to the notion of *complete polynomial families* for any algebraic class; these are the families whose efficient projections can give all other polynomial families of the class. See [61] for an insightful survey by Mahajan.

The n^{th} *Iterated Matrix Multiplication* polynomial of degree k , denoted as $IMM_{k,n}$, is the $(1, 1)$ entry of the product of n many $k \times k$ matrices of indeterminates. The readers familiar with algebraic branching programs can observe that $IMM_{k,n}$ corresponds to *width- k ABPs*. In 1992, Ben-Or and Cleve showed that $IMM_{3,n}$ can efficiently simulate formulas [14]. That is, any polynomial family that can be computed by polynomial-sized formulas can also be obtained as an efficient projection of $IMM_{3,n}$. In contrast, Allender and Wang came up with an explicit polynomial (i.e., $x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + \dots + x_8y_8$) in 2016 that cannot be obtained as a projection of $IMM_{2,n}$ over any field [3]. To cope with the reduced power of $IMM_{2,n}$, Bringmann et al. showed in 2018 that $IMM_{2,n}$ can still efficiently *approximate* formulas, when the field characteristic is $\neq 2$ [20]. That is, over such fields, any polynomial family that can be computed by polynomial-sized formulas can also be approximated by some polynomial family which can be obtained as an efficient projection of $IMM_{2,n}$. The question that whether $IMM_{2,n}$ can efficiently approximate formulas over characteristic 2 fields is still under our investigation. As a baby step, in Chapter 4, we prove the *universality* of approximate $IMM_{2,n}$. That is, over such fields, every polynomial can be approximated by some polynomial which can be obtained as a (though not-so-efficient) projection of $IMM_{2,n}$. So, as my mentor Balagopal Komarath once said, "*All polynomials are 2×2 matrix multiplications in disguise!*" The construction presented herein extends our construction in [33]. Specifically, instead of sum-of-monomials

representation (i.e., $\Sigma\Pi$ circuits), we work with $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma\Pi^{(2)}$ circuits² here. We also show that for any polynomial f that can be computed by an s -sized formula, some polynomially-bounded (in s) power of f can be approximated by a polynomial-sized (again, in s) width-2 ABP. This may be considered interesting because f and its powers have the same set of roots.

In Chapter 5, we study the power of bounded-width ABPs over min-plus semirings (instead of fields) R and N , where minimum operation serves as addition, and the usual addition serves as multiplication. This is motivated by recurrences in dynamic programming algorithms, which are often of the form minimum-of-sums (see, for example, Bellman-Held-Karp algorithm [13]). We come up with an explicit polynomial (i.e., $x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + x_3y_3$) that cannot be obtained as a projection of $IMM_{2,n}$ over semiring R . It is natural to ask whether $IMM_{k,n}$ for some $k \geq 3$ is powerful enough to efficiently simulate formulas. While this question is still under our investigation, we prove a few weaker results; we show that alternating $\Sigma\Pi$ circuits of depth k can be efficiently simulated by $IMM_{k+1,n}$ for some small values of k (i.e., $k = 2, 3, 4, 5$).

²The superscript '(2)' indicates that bottom fan-in is two.

Chapter 1
**Diverse Pair of Compatible NCMs
for Points in Convex Position**

Introduction

Consider a set P of an even number (say $2n$) of points in *general position* (i.e., no three of these points are collinear) on a plane. A *perfect non-crossing matching* M of P is a collection of line segments in the plane such that i) each line segment in M has its endpoints in P , ii) every point of P is an endpoint of exactly one line segment in M , and iii) no two line segments in M cross each other. Such a matching always exists, and it can be found in polynomial-time [48]. Two perfect NCMs M and N of P are said to be *compatible* with each other if no line segment of M crosses a line segment of N . Such a pair of matchings always exists, and it can be found in polynomial-time as follows: i) Build a simple polygon passing through all points in P (see [73]). ii) Starting from an arbitrary edge of the polygon, pick every alternate edge into the first matching. iii) Pick the remaining n edges into the second matching. In this chapter, we introduce a notion of distance between two perfect matchings, and we devise a polynomial-time algorithm to find a pair of maximally far apart compatible perfect NCMs for points in *convex position* (i.e., when P is the set of vertices of a convex polygon). Also, we devise a polynomial-time algorithm for the setting where the input additionally contains a base perfect NCM M of the set P of points in convex position, and the goal is to find a perfect NCM N of P that is maximally far apart from M , i.e., $\text{dist}(M, N)$ is maximized.

Notion of distance. For any point $p \in P$, and for any perfect matching M of P , we define the *matched partner* of p in M (denoted as $M(p)$) as the unique point $q \in P$ such that the line segment joining p and q belongs to M . For any two perfect matchings M and N of P , we define the distance between M and N (denoted as $\text{dist}(M, N)$) as the minimum of the Euclidean distances between the matched partners of any point in the matchings M and N . That is, $\text{dist}(M, N) := \min_{p \in P} \{ \text{dist}(M(p), N(p)) \}$.

Related work. Many studies on NCMs have focused on optimizing sum of edge-lengths, average edge-length and lengths of longest and shortest edges. In 1991, Marcotte and Suri obtained an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ that computes a perfect NCM on points in convex position such that the sum of edge-lengths is minimized [63]. In 1993, Alon et al. devised an algorithm with running time $o(n^{\frac{5}{2}} \log n)$ that computes a perfect NCM whose sum of edge-lengths is at least $\frac{2}{\pi}$ times the largest possible sum of edge-lengths for any (possible crossing) perfect matching [4]. In 1998, Varadarajan obtained a divide-and-conquer algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}(n^{\frac{3}{2}} \log^5 n)$ that computes a matching such that the sum of edge-lengths is minimized [78]. In 2014, Abu-Affash et al. showed NP-hardness of the problem of computing a perfect NCM such that the length of longest edge is minimized [2]. In the same work, they also derived an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}(n^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\log n})$ that computes a perfect NCM

Figure 3: The black and brown matchings are compatible perfect NCMs for these 18 points in convex position. Their segments together form (in an alternating manner) the edges of a feasible collection of three polygons of lengths 4, 6, 8.

whose length of longest edge is at most $2\sqrt{10}$ times the minimum possible length of longest edge of any perfect NCM.

Diverse Pair of Compatible NCMs: The Algorithm

The algorithm described in this section takes as input a set P of $2n$ points in convex position, and finds the maximum distance between any pair of compatible perfect NCMs of P .

That is, it outputs $\max_{\substack{M, N: M \text{ and } N \\ \text{perfect NCMs of } P}} \{ \text{dist}(M, N) \}$.

Correspondence between pairs of compatible NCMs and feasible polygon-collections.

For any collection \mathcal{F} of even-length simple convex polygons, each of length ≥ 4 , we say that \mathcal{F} is a *feasible collection of polygons on P* if i) every point $p \in P$ is a vertex of exactly one polygon in \mathcal{F} , ii) every polygon in \mathcal{F} has all its vertices in P , and iii) no edge of a polygon in \mathcal{F} crosses an edge of another polygon in \mathcal{F} . Also, for any polygon $T \in \mathcal{F}$, i) let $\text{partners}(T)$ denote the set of all unordered pairs $\{u, v\}$ of vertices of T such that exactly one vertex of T appears between u and v , when one traverses from u to v in counter-clockwise direction along the boundary of T , and ii) let $\text{quality}(T)$ denote the minimum of $\text{dist}(u, v)$ over all pairs $\{u, v\}$ in $\text{partners}(T)$. That is, $\text{quality}(T)$ is the minimum distance between the two neighbors of any vertex in T (i.e., the two vertices that are adjacent to it along the boundary of T). Further, let $\text{quality}(\mathcal{F})$ denote the minimum of $\text{quality}(T)$ over all polygons T in \mathcal{F} .

Given any pair of compatible perfect NCMs of P , their line segments form a feasible collection of polygons on P (see Figure 3 for an example). Also, for any feasible collection of polygons on P , picking alternate edges from each of its polygons into the first matching and picking the remaining edges into the second matching, we get a pair of compatible perfect NCMs of P . Moreover, in both directions, the quality of the polygon-collection is same as the distance between the pair of matchings. Thus, our problem amounts to finding

$$\max_{\substack{\mathcal{F}: \mathcal{F} \text{ is a feasible collection} \\ \text{of polygons on } P}} \{ \text{quality}(\mathcal{F}) \}.$$

Guaranteeing existence of an optimal solution whose polygons have lengths 4 or 6.

In the following crucial lemma, we show that given any feasible collection of polygons on P , its polygons can be 'broken' (made precise in the proof below) without degrading its quality such that the polygons in the new feasible polygon-collection so obtained have lengths 4 or 6. Using this lemma, we can safely restrict our space of feasible polygon-collections. That is, now, our problem amounts to finding

$$\max_{\substack{\mathcal{F}: \mathcal{F} \text{ is a feasible collection of polygons on } P \\ \text{such that all its polygons have lengths 4 or 6}}} \{ \text{quality}(\mathcal{F}) \}.$$

Figure 4: Breaking polygon T on $4q$ points into q length-4 polygons T_0, T_1, \dots, T_{q-1} in Case 1 in the proof of Lemma 1.

Lemma 1. *Let \mathcal{F} be a feasible collection of polygons on P . Then, there exists a feasible collection \mathcal{F}' of polygons on P such that every polygon in \mathcal{F}' has length either 4 or 6, and $\text{quality}(\mathcal{F}') \geq \text{quality}(\mathcal{F})$.*

Proof. Construct \mathcal{F}' using \mathcal{F} as follows: For each polygon T in \mathcal{F} of length > 6 ,

Case 1. T has length $4q$, for some $q \geq 2$.

Let $0, 1, 2, \dots, 4q - 1$ denote the vertices of T , appearing in that order as one traverses in counter-clockwise direction along its boundary. We break T into q simple convex polygons T_0, T_1, \dots, T_{q-1} , each of length 4, where T_0 has vertices $0, 1, 2, 3$, T_1 has vertices $4, 5, 6, 7, \dots$, T_{q-1} has vertices $4q - 4, 4q - 3, 4q - 2, 4q - 1$. That is, we remove the edges $\{3, 4\}, \{7, 8\}, \dots, \{4q - 5, 4q - 4\}, \{4q - 1, 0\}$, and we add the edges $\{0, 3\}, \{4, 7\}, \dots, \{4q - 8, 4q - 5\}, \{4q - 4, 4q - 1\}$ (see Figure 4). Consider any $0 \leq j \leq q - 1$. Although the pair of neighbors of the point $4j$ changes from $\{4j - 1, 4j + 1\}$ to $\{4j + 1, 4j + 3\}$ upon breaking, the point $4j + 2$ already had $\{4j + 1, 4j + 3\}$ as its pair of neighbors in T prior to breaking; so, $\{4j + 1, 4j + 3\} \in \text{partners}(T)$. Similarly, although the pair of neighbors of the point $4j + 3$ changes from $\{4j + 2, 4j + 4\}$ to $\{4j, 4j + 2\}$ upon breaking, the point $4j + 1$ already had $\{4j, 4j + 2\}$ as its pair of neighbors prior to breaking; so, $\{4j, 4j + 2\} \in \text{partners}(T)$. Therefore, no new pairs of points appear in the set $\text{partners}(T_j)$. That is, we have $\text{partners}(T_j) = \{\{4j, 4j + 2\}, \{4j + 1, 4j + 3\}\} \subseteq \text{partners}(T)$. So, $\text{quality}(T_j) \geq \text{quality}(T)$. Thus, we get $\min_{0 \leq j \leq q-1} \{\text{quality}(T_j)\} \geq \text{quality}(T)$.

Case 2. T has length $4q + 2$, for some $q \geq 2$.

Let $0, 1, 2, \dots, 4q + 1$ denote the vertices of T , appearing in that order as one traverses in the counter-clockwise direction along its boundary. Let T_{even} and T_{odd} denote the simple convex polygons, each of length $2q + 1$, on the vertices $0, 2, 4, \dots, 4q$ and $1, 3, 4, \dots, 4q + 1$ respectively. That is, T_{even} has all even-numbered vertices, and T_{odd} has all odd-numbered vertices. Let $e_0, e_2, e_4, \dots, e_{4q}$ denote the interior angles of T_{even} at the vertices $0, 2, 4, \dots, 4q$ respectively, and let $o_1, o_3, o_5, \dots, o_{4q+1}$ denote the interior angles of T_{odd} at the vertices $1, 3, 5, \dots, 4q + 1$ respectively (see Figure 5). For any simple convex polygon, since its exterior angles sum up to 2π , at most two of them are $> \frac{2\pi}{3}$ and so, at most two of its interior angles are $< \frac{\pi}{3}$. Thus, in particular, each of T_{even} and T_{odd} has at most two interior angles that are $< \frac{\pi}{3}$. That is, at most two of $e_0, e_2, e_4, \dots, e_{4q}$ are $< \frac{\pi}{3}$, and at most two of $o_1, o_3, o_5, \dots, o_{4q+1}$ are

Figure 5: The polygons T_{even} and T_{odd} in Case 2 in the proof of Lemma 1.

$< \frac{\pi}{3}$. So, amongst the ≥ 5 pairs of angles $(e_0, o_1), (e_2, o_3), (e_4, o_5), \dots, (e_{4q}, o_{4q+1})$, there must be at least one pair, say $(e_{2\ell}, o_{2\ell+1})$, such that both angles $e_{2\ell}$ and $o_{2\ell+1}$ are $\geq \frac{\pi}{3}$.

We break the polygon T into a simple convex length-6 polygon T_0 and $q-1$ simple convex length-4 polygons T_1, \dots, T_{q-1} , where T_0 has vertices $2\ell-2, 2\ell-1, 2\ell, 2\ell+1, 2\ell+2, 2\ell+3$, T_1 has vertices $2\ell+4, 2\ell+5, 2\ell+6, 2\ell+7$, T_2 has vertices $2\ell+8, 2\ell+9, 2\ell+10, 2\ell+11$, \dots , T_{q-1} has vertices $2\ell+4q-4, 2\ell+4q-3, 2\ell+4q-2, 2\ell+4q-1$ ³. That is, we remove the edges $\{2\ell+3, 2\ell+4\}, \{2\ell+7, 2\ell+8\}, \dots, \{2\ell+4q-1, 2\ell-2\}$, and we add the edges $\{2\ell-2, 2\ell+3\}, \{2\ell+4, 2\ell+7\}, \{2\ell+8, 2\ell+11\}, \dots, \{2\ell+4q-4, 2\ell+4q-1\}$ (see Figure 6). Consider any $1 \leq j \leq q-1$. We have $partners(T_j) = \{\{2\ell+4j, 2\ell+4j+2\}, \{2\ell+4j+1, 2\ell+4j+3\}\} \subseteq partners(T)$ (similar to Case 1). So, $quality(T_j) \geq quality(T)$. Thus, to prove $\min_{0 \leq j \leq q-1} \{quality(T_j)\} \geq quality(T)$, it now suffices to show $quality(T_0) \geq quality(T)$.

Upon breaking, the pairs of neighbors of the points $2\ell+3$ and $2\ell-2$ change from $\{2\ell+2, 2\ell+4\}$ to $\{2\ell+2, 2\ell-2\}$, and from $\{2\ell+4q-1, 2\ell-1\}$ to $\{2\ell+3, 2\ell-1\}$, respectively. So, we have $partners(T_0) \setminus partners(T) = \{\{2\ell+2, 2\ell-2\}, \{2\ell+3, 2\ell-1\}\}$. Thus, showing $quality(T_0) \geq quality(T)$ boils down to proving that $dist(2\ell+2, 2\ell-2)$ and $dist(2\ell+3, 2\ell-1)$ are $\geq quality(T)$. Consider the triangle formed by the points $2\ell-1, 2\ell+1, 2\ell+3$ (see Figure 7). Since its interior angles sum up to π and $o_{2\ell+1} \geq \frac{\pi}{3}$, at least one of its other two interior angles must be $\leq \frac{\pi}{3}$. So, the minimum of these two angles must be at most $o_{2\ell+1}$ and thus, the length of the shorter of the two sides opposite to them must be at most the length of the side opposite to $o_{2\ell+1}$. That is, $dist(2\ell+3, 2\ell-1) \geq \min \{dist(2\ell+1, 2\ell+3), dist(2\ell-1, 2\ell+1)\}$. Also, since $\{2\ell+1, 2\ell+3\}$ and $\{2\ell-1, 2\ell+1\}$ are the pairs of neighbors of the points $2\ell+2$ and 2ℓ in T respectively, these two pairs appear in the set $partners(T)$. Thus, $quality(T) \leq \min \{dist(2\ell+1, 2\ell+3), dist(2\ell-1, 2\ell+1)\}$. Therefore, $dist(2\ell+3, 2\ell-1) \geq quality(T)$. Next, consider the triangle formed by the points $2\ell-2, 2\ell, 2\ell+2$ (see Figure 8). Again, since its interior angles sum up to π and $e_{2\ell} \geq \frac{\pi}{3}$, at least one of its other two interior angles

³Here, the additions are modulo $4q+2$.

Figure 6: Breaking polygon T on $4q+2$ points into one length-6 polygon T_0 and $q-1$ length-4 polygons T_1, \dots, T_{q-1} in Case 2 in the proof of Lemma 1.

Figure 7: Triangle on points $2\ell - 1, 2\ell + 1, 2\ell + 3$ in Case 2 in Lemma 1's proof.

Figure 8: Triangle on points $2\ell - 2, 2\ell, 2\ell + 2$ in Case 2 in Lemma 1's proof.

must be $\leq \frac{\pi}{3}$. So, the minimum of these two angles must be at most $e_{2\ell}$ and thus, the length of the shorter of the two sides opposite to them must be at most the length of the side opposite to $e_{2\ell}$. That is, $\text{dist}(2\ell + 2, 2\ell - 2) \geq \min \{ \text{dist}(2\ell, 2\ell + 2), \text{dist}(2\ell - 2, 2\ell) \}$. Also, since $\{2\ell, 2\ell + 2\}$ and $\{2\ell - 2, 2\ell\}$ are the pairs of the neighbors of the points $2\ell + 1$ and $2\ell - 1$ respectively, these two pairs appear in the set $\text{partners}(T)$. Thus, $\text{quality}(T) \leq \min \{ \text{dist}(2\ell, 2\ell + 2), \text{dist}(2\ell - 2, 2\ell) \}$. Therefore, $\text{dist}(2\ell + 2, 2\ell - 2) \geq \text{quality}(T)$. This proves Lemma 1. \square

Dynamic programming. At a high level, our algorithm works as follows: Consider all $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ continuous intervals of points along the boundary of the convex polygon on P . For each such interval, consider the subproblem obtained by restricting to only those points of P that lie in this interval. We find optimal solutions for these subproblems in increasing order of the corresponding interval sizes, and we store them in a DP table. To find solution for the subproblem corresponding to any interval, we use the solutions stored for subproblems corresponding to shorter intervals. To do so, we guess whether the starting point of the current interval belongs to a length-4 polygon or a length-6 polygon in desired solution. Also, we guess the remaining three and five points of this polygon respectively. Once the polygon containing the starting point is so guessed, the remaining points of the current interval get partitioned into four and six sub-intervals respectively. Combining the solutions stored in the DP table for the subproblems corresponding to these sub-intervals along with the polygon containing the starting point gives us a solution for the subproblem corresponding to the current interval. We find and store the solution that is best (i.e., it has the maximum quality) amongst all solutions so obtained for the $\mathcal{O}(n^5)$ guesses. We make this more precise below.

Let $0, 1, \dots, 2n-1$ denote the points of P in counter-clockwise order. For every $0 \leq i < j \leq 2n-1$ such that $j-i$ is odd, let $\mathbb{T}(i, j)$ denote the maximum quality attainable amongst all feasible polygon-collections on the even-sized set of points $i, i+1, \dots, j-1, j$ whose polygons have lengths 4 or 6. We compute and store $\mathbb{T}(i, j)$'s in increasing order of $(j-i)$'s. When $j-i=1$, we set $\mathbb{T}(i, j) = -\infty$. Next, consider $j-i \geq 3$. We have $\mathbb{T}(i, j) = \max\{\alpha(i, j), \beta(i, j)\}$, where $\alpha(i, j)$ and $\beta(i, j)$ denote the maximum qualities when the point i belongs to a length-4 polygon and a length-6 polygon respectively. In the first case, we guess the remaining three vertices p_1, p_2, p_3 of the length-4 polygon containing i . Combining solutions for the sub-intervals $\{i+1, \dots, p_1-1\}, \{p_1+1, \dots, p_2-1\}, \{p_2+1, \dots, p_3-1\}, \{p_3+1, \dots, j\}$ along with the length-4 polygon on the points i, p_1, p_2, p_3 gives a solution for the interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$ (see Figure 9). In the second case, we guess the remaining five vertices q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5 of the length-6 polygon containing i . Combining solutions for the sub-intervals $\{i+1, \dots, q_1-1\}, \{q_1+1, \dots, q_2-1\}, \{q_2+1, \dots, q_3-1\}, \{q_3+1, \dots, q_4-1\}, \{q_4+1, \dots, q_5-1\}, \{q_5+1, \dots, j\}$ along with the length-6 polygon on the points $i, q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5$ gives a solution for the interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$ (see Figure 10). Thus, we use the following recurrences to get $\alpha(i, j)$ and $\beta(i, j)$ ⁴:

$$\alpha(i, j) = \max_{\substack{i < p_1 < p_2 < p_3 \leq j \\ p_1 - i, p_2 - p_1, p_3 - p_2 \text{ are odd}}} \left\{ \min \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{dist}(i, p_2), \\ \text{dist}(p_1, p_3), \\ \mathbb{T}(i+1, p_1-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(p_1+1, p_2-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(p_2+1, p_3-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(p_3+1, j) \end{array} \right) \right\}$$

$$\beta(i, j) = \max_{\substack{i < q_1 < q_2 < q_3 < q_4 < q_5 \leq j \\ q_1 - i, q_2 - q_1, q_3 - q_2, \\ q_4 - q_3, q_5 - q_4 \text{ are odd}}} \left\{ \min \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{dist}(i, q_2), \\ \text{dist}(q_1, q_3), \\ \text{dist}(q_2, q_4), \\ \text{dist}(q_3, q_5), \\ \text{dist}(q_4, i), \\ \text{dist}(q_5, q_1), \\ \mathbb{T}(i+1, q_1-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_1+1, q_2-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_2+1, q_3-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_3+1, q_4-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_4+1, q_5-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_5+1, j) \end{array} \right) \right\}$$

Another Diverse NCM: The Algorithm

The algorithm described in this section takes as input a set P of $2n$ points in convex position and a base perfect NCM M of P , and finds the maximum distance between the base matching M and any perfect NCM of P . That is, it outputs $\max_{N: N \text{ is a perfect NCM of } P} \{\text{dist}(M, N)\}$.

At a high level, our algorithm works as follows: Consider all $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ continuous intervals of points along the boundary of the convex polygon P . For each such interval, our subproblem

⁴Some choices of p_1, p_2, p_3 are such that $p_1 = i+1$ or $p_2 = p_1+1$ or $p_3 = p_2+1$ or $j = p_3$, i.e., the sub-interval $\{i+1, \dots, p_1-1\}$ or $\{p_1+1, \dots, p_2-1\}$ or $\{p_2+1, \dots, p_3-1\}$ or $\{p_3+1, \dots, j\}$ is empty. So, in the min argument, omit the corresponding term, i.e., $\mathbb{T}(i+1, p_1-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(p_1+1, p_2-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(p_2+1, p_3-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(p_3+1, j)$, respectively. Similarly, omit the term $\mathbb{T}(i+1, q_1-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(q_1+1, q_2-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(q_2+1, q_3-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(q_3+1, q_4-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(q_4+1, q_5-1)$ or $\mathbb{T}(q_5+1, j)$ whenever the corresponding sub-interval is empty.

Figure 9: This figure illustrates that once a choice of p_1, p_2, p_3 is fixed (i.e., the length-4 polygon containing the point i is guessed), this polygon combined with solutions for the four shorter sub-intervals $\{i+1, \dots, p_1-1\}, \{p_1+1, \dots, p_2-1\}, \{p_2+1, \dots, p_3-1\}, \{p_3+1, \dots, j\}$ gives solution for the interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$.

Figure 10: This figure illustrates that once a choice of q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4, q_5 is fixed (i.e., the length-6 polygon containing the point i is guessed), this polygon combined with solutions for the six shorter sub-intervals $\{i+1, \dots, q_1-1\}, \{q_1+1, \dots, q_2-1\}, \{q_2+1, \dots, q_3-1\}, \{q_3+1, \dots, q_4-1\}, \{q_4+1, \dots, q_5-1\}, \{q_5+1, \dots, j\}$ gives solution for the interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$.

asks for a perfect NCM of the set of points in this interval for which the minimum distance between the matched partners of any point of this interval in this matching and the base matching is maximized. We find optimal solutions for these subproblems in increasing order of the corresponding interval sizes, and we store them in a DP table. To find solution for the subproblem corresponding to any interval, we guess the matched partner of the starting point of this interval in desired solution. This partitions the current interval into at most two sub-intervals. Since solution is non-crossing, no point in one of these sub-intervals can be matched to a point in the other sub-interval. Combining the solutions stored in the DP table for the sub-problems corresponding to these sub-intervals along with the segment joining the starting point and its guessed matched partner gives solution for the subproblem corresponding to the current interval. We find and store the solution that is best (i.e., it has the maximum value of the minimum distance between the matched partners of any point in the current interval) amongst all solutions so obtained for the $\mathcal{O}(n)$ guesses. We make this more precise below.

Let $0, 1, 2, \dots, 2n-1$ denote the points of P in counter-clockwise order. For every $0 \leq i < j \leq 2n-1$ such that $j-i$ is odd, let $\mathbb{T}(i, j)$ denote the maximum of $\min_{\ell \in \{i, i+1, \dots, j\}} \{ \text{dist}(M(\ell), N(\ell)) \}$ over all perfect NCMs N of the even-sized set of points $i, i+1, \dots, j$, where $M(\ell)$ and $N(\ell)$ denote the matched partners of the point ℓ in the matchings M and N respectively. We compute and store $\mathbb{T}(i, j)$'s in increasing order of $(j-i)$'s. When $j = i+1$, the segment joining i and $i+1$ forms the only perfect NCM N on the points i and $i+1$ (see Figure 11) and so, $\mathbb{T}(i, j) = \min \{ \text{dist}(M(i), i+1), \text{dist}(M(i+1), i) \}$. Next, consider $j-i \geq 3$. We go over all possible choices $k \in \{i+1, i+3, \dots, j\}$ for the matched partner of the point i in N . Combining solutions for the sub-intervals $\{i+1, \dots, k-1\}$ and $\{k+1, \dots, j\}$ along with the segment joining the points i and k gives solution for the interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$ (see Figure 12). So, we use the following recurrence to get $\mathbb{T}(i, j)$ ⁵:

$$\mathbb{T}(i, j) = \max_{k \in \{i+1, i+3, \dots, j\}} \left\{ \min \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{dist}(M(i), k), \text{dist}(M(k), i), \\ \mathbb{T}(i+1, k-1), \mathbb{T}(k+1, j) \end{array} \right) \right\}$$

Figure 11: This figure shows the base case, i.e., $j = i+1$. The distances between matched partners of the points i and $i+1$ in the matchings M and N are marked.

⁵When $k = i+1$, the sub-interval $\{i+1, \dots, k-1\}$ is empty and so, omit the term $\mathbb{T}(i+1, k-1)$ in the min argument. Similarly, when $k = j$, the sub-interval $\{k+1, \dots, j\}$ is empty and so, omit the term $\mathbb{T}(k+1, j)$.

Figure 12: This figure illustrates that once a choice of the matched partner $k \in \{i+1, i+3, \dots, j\}$ of the point i is fixed, the segment joining the points i and k combined with solutions for the sub-intervals $\{i+1 \dots, k-1\}$ and $\{k+1, \dots, j\}$ gives solution for the interval $\{i, \dots, j\}$.

Directions for Future Work. The complexities of finding i) diverse pair of compatible perfect NCMs for points in general position, ii) diverse pair of perfect NCMs (without the compatibility constraint) for points in convex and general positions, and iii) another diverse perfect NCM for points in general position, remain unresolved. The diverse variant of finding perfect NCMs can also be studied for i) more than two matchings, ii) other notions of distance between matchings, iii) other notions of distance between points (i.e., different from Euclidean distance), and iv) for point-sets that have a bounded number of convex layers.

Pseudocodes:

Algorithm 1 Another Diverse NCM for Points in Convex Position

Input: A set P of $2n$ points in convex position ($0, 1, 2, \dots, 2n-1$ in counterclockwise order)
A base perfect NCM M of P

Output: Maximum distance between M and any perfect NCM of P

Polynomial-time algorithm:

```

for  $length$  in  $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n-1\}$  do
  for  $i$  in  $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, (2n-1) - length\}$  do
     $j \leftarrow i + length$ 
    if  $length == 1$  then
       $\mathbb{T}(i, j) \leftarrow \min \{ \text{dist}(M(i), i+1), \text{dist}(M(i+1), i) \}$ 
    else
       $\mathbb{T}(i, j) \leftarrow -\infty$ 
      for  $k$  in  $\{i+1, i+3, i+5, \dots, j\}$  do
         $\mathbb{T}(i, j) \leftarrow \max \left\{ \mathbb{T}(i, j), \min \left( \begin{array}{l} \text{dist}(M(i), k), \text{dist}(M(k), i), \\ \mathbb{T}(i+1, k-1), \mathbb{T}(k+1, j) \end{array} \right) \right\}$ 
      end for
    end if
  end for
end for
return  $\mathbb{T}(0, 2n-1)$ 

```

Algorithm 2 Diverse Pair of Compatible NCMs for Points in Convex Position

Input: A set P of $2n$ points in convex position $(0, 1, 2, \dots, 2n-1)$ in counterclockwise order)

Output: Maximum distance between any pair of compatible perfect NCMs of P
Polynomial-time algorithm:

```

for  $length$  in  $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2n-1\}$  do
  for  $i$  in  $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, (2n-1) - length\}$  do
     $j \leftarrow i + length$ 
    if  $length == 1$  then
       $\mathbb{T}(i, j) \leftarrow -\infty$ 
    else
       $\alpha(i, j) \leftarrow -\infty$ 
      for  $p_1$  in  $\{i+1, i+3, i+5, \dots, j-2\}$  do
        for  $p_2$  in  $\{p_1+1, p_1+3, p_1+5, \dots, j-1\}$  do
          for  $p_3$  in  $\{p_2+1, p_2+3, p_2+5, \dots, j\}$  do
            
$$\alpha(i, j) \leftarrow \max \left\{ \alpha(i, j), \min \left( \begin{array}{l} \text{dist}(i, p_2), \\ \text{dist}(p_1, p_3), \\ \mathbb{T}(i+1, p_1-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(p_1+1, p_2-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(p_2+1, p_3-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(p_3+1, j) \end{array} \right) \right\}$$

          end for
        end for
      end for
       $\beta(i, j) \leftarrow -\infty$ 
      for  $q_1$  in  $\{i+1, i+3, i+5, \dots, j-4\}$  do
        for  $q_2$  in  $\{q_1+1, q_1+3, q_1+5, \dots, j-3\}$  do
          for  $q_3$  in  $\{q_2+1, q_2+3, q_2+5, \dots, j-2\}$  do
            for  $q_4$  in  $\{q_3+1, q_3+3, q_3+5, \dots, j-1\}$  do
              for  $q_5$  in  $\{q_4+1, q_4+3, q_4+5, \dots, j\}$  do
                
$$\beta(i, j) \leftarrow \max \left\{ \beta(i, j), \min \left( \begin{array}{l} \text{dist}(i, q_2), \\ \text{dist}(q_1, q_3), \\ \text{dist}(q_2, q_4), \\ \text{dist}(q_3, q_5), \\ \text{dist}(q_4, i), \\ \text{dist}(q_5, q_1), \\ \mathbb{T}(i+1, q_1-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_1+1, q_2-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_2+1, q_3-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_3+1, q_4-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_4+1, q_5-1), \\ \mathbb{T}(q_5+1, j) \end{array} \right) \right\}$$

              end for
            end for
          end for
        end for
      end for
       $\mathbb{T}(i, j) \leftarrow \max\{\alpha(i, j), \beta(i, j)\}$ 
    end if
  end for
end for
return  $\mathbb{T}(0, 2n-1)$ 

```

Chapter 2

Diverse Pair of Satisfying Assignments for Affine, 2-CNF and Hitting Formulas

SAT and its complexity. The Boolean Satisfiability problem (SAT) asks whether a given Boolean formula has a satisfying assignment. This problem serves a crucial role in complexity theory [56], cryptography [65] and artificial intelligence [79]. In the early 1970s, SAT became the first problem proved to be NP-complete in independent works of Cook [24] and Levin [59]. Around the same time, Karp [56] built upon this result by showing NP-completeness of twenty-one graph-theoretic and combinatorial problems via reductions from SAT. In the late 1970s, Schaefer [71] formulated the closely related Generalized Satisfiability problem (SAT(S)), where each constraint applies on some variables, and it forces the corresponding tuple of their truth-values to belong to a certain Boolean relation from a fixed finite set S . His celebrated dichotomy result listed six conditions such that SAT(S) is polynomial-time solvable if S meets one of them; otherwise, SAT(S) is NP-complete.

Since SAT is NP-complete, it is unlikely to admit a polynomial-time algorithm, unless $P = NP$. Further, in the late 1990s, Impagliazzo and Paturi [51] conjectured that SAT is unlikely to admit even sub-exponential time algorithms, often referred to as the *exponential-time hypothesis*. To cope with the widely believed hardness of SAT, several special classes of Boolean formulas have been identified for which SAT is polynomial-time solvable. In the late 1960s, Krom [58] devised a quadratic-time algorithm to solve SAT on 2-CNF formulas. In the late 1970s, follow-up works of Even et al. [35] and Aspvall et al. [7] proposed linear-time algorithms to solve SAT on 2-CNF formulas. These algorithms used limited back-tracking and analysis of the strongly-connected components of the implication graph respectively. In the late 1980s, Iwama [52] introduced the class of hitting formulas, for which he gave a closed-form expression to count the number of satisfying assignments in polynomial-time. It is also known that SAT can be solved in polynomial-time on affine formulas using Gaussian elimination [46]. Some other polynomial-time recognizable classes of formulas for which SAT is polynomial-time solvable include Horn formulas [29, 72], CC-balanced formulas [23], matched formulas [39], renamable-Horn formulas [60] and q -Horn DNF formulas [17, 18].

Diverse variant of SAT. In this chapter, we undertake a complexity-theoretic study of SAT in the framework of diversity. We focus on the problem of finding a *diverse pair of satisfying assignments* of a given Boolean formula, and we take the number of variables on which the two assignments differ as a measure of dissimilarity between them. Specifically, we define the problem Max Differ SAT (resp. Exact Differ SAT) as follows: Given a Boolean formula Φ on n variables and a non-negative integer d , decide whether there are two satisfying assignments of Φ that differ on at least d (resp. exactly d) variables. That is, this problem asks whether there are two satisfying assignments of Φ that overlap on at most $n - d$ (resp. exactly $n - d$) variables. SAT can be reduced to its diverse variant by setting d to 0. Thus, as SAT is NP-hard in general, so is Max/Exact Differ SAT. So, it is natural to study the diverse variant on those

classes of formulas for which SAT is polynomial-time solvable. In particular, we consider affine formulas, 2-CNF formulas and hitting formulas. We refer to the corresponding restrictions of Max/Exact Differ SAT as Max/Exact Differ Affine-SAT, Max/Exact Differ 2-SAT and Max/Exact Differ Hitting-SAT respectively. We analyze the classical and parameterized (in parameters d and $n - d$) complexities of these problems. We show that

- Exact/Max Differ Affine-SAT is polynomial-time solvable on 2-affine formulas (Theorem 3).
- Max Differ Affine-SAT admits a single-exponential FPT algorithm in the parameter d (Theorem 5).
- Max Differ Affine-SAT admits a polynomial kernel in the parameter d (Theorem 6).
- Exact/Max Differ 2-SAT can be solved in polynomial-time on $(2, 2)$ -CNF formulas. (Theorems 8 and 9)
- Exact/Max Differ Hitting-SAT is polynomial-time solvable (Theorem 11).

Also, we show the following hardness results:

- Exact Differ Affine-SAT is NP-hard, even on $(3, 4)$ -affine formulas (Theorem 1).
- Max Differ Affine-SAT is NP-hard, even on 4-affine formulas (Theorem 2).
- Exact Differ Affine-SAT is $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter d (Theorem 4).
- Exact/Max Differ Affine-SAT is $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter $n - d$ (Theorem 7).
- Exact/Max Differ 2-SAT is $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter d (Theorem 10).

Parameterized complexity. In the 1990s, Downey and Fellows [31] laid the foundations of parameterized algorithmics. This framework measures the running time of an algorithm as a function of both the input size and a *parameter* k , i.e., a suitably chosen attribute of the input. Such a fine-grained analysis helps to cope with the lack of polynomial-time algorithms for NP-hard problems by instead looking for an algorithm with running time whose super-polynomial explosion is confined to the parameter k alone. That is, such an algorithm has a running time of the form $f(k) \cdot n^{O(1)}$, where $f(\cdot)$ is any computable function (could be exponential, or even worse) and n denotes the input size. Such an algorithm is said to be *fixed-parameter tractable* (FPT) because its running time is polynomially-bounded for every fixed value of the parameter k . *Kernelization* refers to an efficient pre-processing of an input instance by repeated application of some *reduction rules* such that size of the reduced instance (equivalent to the original instance) is bounded by a function of the parameter k . Note that kernelization followed by application of any known trivial algorithm on the reduced instance gives an FPT algorithm for the problem. Further, the notion of $W[1]$ -hardness captures intractability in this area. Loosely speaking, $W[1]$ -hard problems are unlikely to admit FPT algorithms. We refer readers to the textbook ‘Parameterized Algorithms’ by Cygan et al. [26] for precise definitions.

Related work. This is not the first work to study algorithms to determine the maximum number of variables on which two solutions of a given SAT instance can differ. Several exact exponential-time algorithms are known to find a pair of maximally far-apart satisfying assignments. In the mid 2000s, Angelsmark and Thapper [6] devised an $\mathcal{O}(1.7338^n)$ time algorithm to solve Max Hamming Distance 2-SAT. Their algorithm involved a careful analysis of the micro-structure graph and used a solver for weighted 2-SAT as a sub-routine. Around the same time, Dahlöf [27] proposed an $\mathcal{O}(1.8348^n)$ time algorithm for Max Hamming Distance XSAT. In the late 2010s, follow-up works of Hoi et al. [50, 49] developed algorithms for the same problem with improved running times, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(1.4983^n)$ for the general case, and $\mathcal{O}(1.328^n)$ for the case when every clause has at most three literals.

Preliminaries

A Boolean variable can take one of the two truth values: 0 (False) and 1 (True). We use n to denote the number of variables in a Boolean formula Φ . An *assignment* of Φ is a mapping from the set of all its n variables to $\{0, 1\}$. A *satisfying assignment* of Φ is an assignment σ such that Φ evaluates to 1 under σ , i.e., when every variable x is substituted with its assigned truth value $\sigma(x)$. We say that two assignments σ_1 and σ_2 *differ* on a variable x if they assign different truth values to x . That is, one of them sets x to 0, and the other sets x to 1. Otherwise, we say that σ_1 and σ_2 *overlap* on x . That is, either both of them set x to 0, or both of them set x to 1.

A *literal* is either a variable x (called a *positive literal*) or its negation $\neg x$ (called a *negative literal*). A *clause* is a disjunction (denoted by \vee) of literals. A Boolean formula in *conjunctive normal form*, i.e., a conjunction (denoted by \wedge) of clauses, is called a *CNF formula*. A *2-CNF formula* is a CNF formula with at most two literals per clause. A *(2,2)-CNF formula* is a 2-CNF formula in which each variable appears in at most two clauses. An *affine formula* is a conjunction of linear equations over the two-element field \mathbb{F}_2 . We use \oplus to denote the XOR operator, i.e., addition-modulo-2. A *2-affine formula* is an affine formula in which each equation has at most two variables. Similarly, a *3-affine* (resp. *4-affine*) *formula* is an affine formula in which each equation has at most three (resp. four) variables. A *(3,4)-affine formula* is a 3-affine formula in which each variable appears in at most four equations.

The solution set of a system of linear equations can be obtained in polynomial-time using Gaussian elimination [46]. It may have no solution, a unique solution or multiple solutions. When it has multiple solutions, the solution set is described as follows: Some variables are allowed to take any value; we call them *free variables*. The remaining variables take values that are dependent on the values taken by the free variables; we call them *forced variables*. That is, the value taken by any forced variable is a linear combination of the values taken by some free variables. For example, consider the following system of three linear equations over \mathbb{F}_2 : $x \oplus y \oplus z = 1$, $u \oplus y = 1$, $w \oplus z = 1$. This system has multiple solutions, and its solution set can be described as $\{(x, y, z, u, w) \mid y \in \mathbb{F}_2, z \in \mathbb{F}_2, x = y \oplus z \oplus 1, u = y \oplus 1, w = z \oplus 1\}$. Here, y and z are free variables. The remaining variables, i.e., x , u and w , are forced variables.

A *hitting formula* is a CNF formula such that for any pair of its clauses, there is some variable that appears as a positive literal in one clause, and as a negative literal in the other clause. Note that no two clauses of a hitting formula Φ on n variables can be simultaneously falsified and so, the count of its unsatisfying assignments is

$$\sum_{C: C \text{ is a clause of } \Phi} |\{\sigma \mid \sigma \text{ is an assignment of } \Phi \text{ that falsifies } C\}|$$

Also, the assignments falsifying a clause C of Φ are those that i) set the variables that appear as a positive literal in C to 0, ii) set the variables that appear as a negative literal in C to 1, and iii) can set each of the remaining variables as either 0 or 1. So, the count of such assignments is $2^{n-|\text{vars}(C)|}$, where $\text{vars}(C)$ denotes the set of all variables that appear in the clause C . Thus, the number of unsatisfying assignments of Φ is $\sum_{C: C \text{ is a clause of } \Phi} 2^{n-|\text{vars}(C)|}$. Note

that this expression (derived by Iwama [52]) is polynomial-time computable. Some later works on hitting formulas studied their resolution complexity [70] and a related proof system [36].

We use the following as source problems in our reductions:

- Independent Set. Given a graph G and a positive integer k , decide whether G has an

independent set of size k . This problem is known to be NP-hard on cubic graphs [68], and W[1]-hard in the parameter k [32].

- Multicolored Clique. Given a graph G whose vertex set is partitioned into k color-classes, decide whether G has a k -sized clique that picks exactly one vertex from each color-class. This problem is known to be NP-hard on r -regular graphs [26].
- Exact Even Set. Given a universe \mathcal{U} , a family \mathcal{F} of subsets of \mathcal{U} and a positive integer k , decide whether there is a set $X \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ of size exactly k such that $|X \cap S|$ is even for all sets S in the family \mathcal{F} . This problem is known to be W[1]-hard in the parameter k [30].
- Odd Set (resp. Exact Odd Set). Given a universe \mathcal{U} , a family \mathcal{F} of subsets of \mathcal{U} and a positive integer k , decide whether there is a set $X \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ of size at most k (resp. exactly k) such that $|X \cap S|$ is odd for all sets S in the family \mathcal{F} . Both these problems are known to be W[1]-hard in the parameter k [30].

We use a polynomial-time algorithm for the following problem as a sub-routine:

- Subset Sum problem. Given a multi-set of integers $\{w_1, \dots, w_p\}$ and a target sum k , decide whether there exists $X \subseteq [p]$ such that $\sum_{i \in X} w_i = k$. This problem is known to be polynomial-time solvable when the input integers are specified in unary [57].

Affine formulas

Theorem 1. *Exact Differ Affine-SAT is NP-hard, even on (3, 4)-affine formulas.*

Proof. We describe a reduction from Independent Set on Cubic graphs. Consider an instance (G, k) of Independent Set, where G is a cubic graph. We construct an affine formula Φ as follows: For every vertex $v \in V(G)$, introduce a variable x_v , its $3k$ copies (say x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k}), and $3k$ equations: $x_v \oplus x_v^1 = 0$, $x_v^1 \oplus x_v^2 = 0$, \dots , $x_v^{3k-1} \oplus x_v^{3k} = 0$. For every edge $e = uv \in E(G)$, introduce variable y_e and equation $x_u \oplus x_v \oplus y_e = 0$. We set $d = k \cdot (3k + 4)$. For every vertex $v \in V(G)$, the variable x_v appears in four equations (i.e., $x_v \oplus x_v^1 = 0$ and the three equations corresponding to the three edges incident to v in G), each of x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k-1} appears in two equations, and x_v^{3k} appears in one equation. For every edge $e \in E(G)$, the variable y_e appears in one equation. So, overall, every variable appears in at most four equations. Also, the equation corresponding to any edge contains three variables, and the remaining equations contain two variables each. Therefore, Φ is a (3, 4)-affine formula.

Now, we prove that (G, k) is a YES instance of Independent Set if and only if (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT. At a high level, we argue this equivalence as follows: In the forward direction, we show that the two desired satisfying assignments are the all 0 assignment, and the assignment that i) assigns 1 to every x variable (and also, its $3k$ copies) that corresponds to a vertex of the independent set, ii) assigns 1 to every y variable that corresponds to an edge that has one endpoint inside the independent set and the other endpoint outside it, iii) assigns 0 to every x variable (and also, its $3k$ copies) that corresponds to a vertex outside the independent set, and iv) assigns 0 to every y variable that corresponds to an edge that has both its endpoints outside the independent set. In the reverse direction, we show that the desired k -sized independent set consists of those vertices that correspond to the x variables on which the two assignments differ. We make this argument precise below.

Forward direction. Suppose that G has a k -sized independent set, say S . Let σ_1 and σ_2 be assignments of Φ defined as follows: For every vertex $v \in V(G) \setminus S$, both σ_1 and σ_2

set $x_v, x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k}$ to 0. For every vertex $v \in S$, σ_1 sets $x_v, x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k}$ to 0, and σ_2 sets $x_v, x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k}$ to 1. For every edge $e \in E(G)$ that has both its endpoints in $V(G) \setminus S$, both σ_1 and σ_2 set y_e to 0. For every edge $e \in E(G)$ that has one endpoint in S and the other endpoint in $V(G) \setminus S$, σ_1 sets y_e to 0, and σ_2 sets y_e to 1.

As σ_1 sets all variables to 0, it is clear that it satisfies Φ . Now, we show that σ_2 satisfies Φ . Consider any edge $e = uv \in E(G)$ and its corresponding equation $x_u \oplus x_v \oplus y_e = 0$. If both endpoints of e belong to $V(G) \setminus S$, then σ_2 sets x_u, x_v and y_e to 0. Also, if e has one endpoint (say u) in S , and the other endpoint in $V(G) \setminus S$, then σ_2 sets x_u to 1, x_v to 0 and y_e to 1. Therefore, in both cases, $x_u \oplus x_v \oplus y_e$ takes the truth value 0 under σ_2 . Also, for any vertex $v \in V(G)$, since σ_2 gives the same truth value to $x_v, x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k}$ (i.e., all 1 if $v \in S$, and all 0 if $v \in V(G) \setminus S$), it also satisfies the equations $x_v \oplus x_v^1 = 0, x_v^1 \oplus x_v^2 = 0, \dots, x_v^{3k-1} \oplus x_v^{3k} = 0$. Thus, σ_2 is a satisfying assignment of Φ .

As G is a cubic graph, every vertex in S is incident to three edges in G . Also, as S is an independent set, none of these edges has both endpoints in S . Therefore, there are $3 \cdot |S|$ edges that have one endpoint in S and the other endpoint in $V(G) \setminus S$. Note that σ_1 and σ_2 differ on the y variables that correspond to these $3 \cdot |S|$ edges. Also, they differ on $|S|$ many x variables, and their $3k \cdot |S|$ copies. Therefore, overall, they differ on $(3k + 1) \cdot |S| + 3 \cdot |S| = k \cdot (3k + 4)$ variables. Hence, (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine SAT.

Reverse direction. Suppose that (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT. That is, there exist satisfying assignments σ_1 and σ_2 of Φ that differ on $k \cdot (3k + 4)$ variables. Let $S := \{v \in V(G) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } x_v\}$. We show that S is a k -sized independent set of G . Let $e(S, \bar{S})$ denote the number of edges in G that have one endpoint in S and the other endpoint in $V(G) \setminus S$. Now, let us express the number of variables on which σ_1 and σ_2 differ in terms of $|S|$ and $e(S, \bar{S})$.

Consider any edge $e = uv \in E(G)$. First, suppose that e has both its endpoints in S . Then, as σ_1 and σ_2 differ on both x_u and x_v , the expression $x_u \oplus x_v$ takes the same truth value under σ_1 and σ_2 . So, as both of them satisfy the equation $x_u \oplus x_v \oplus y_e = 0$, it follows that σ_1 and σ_2 must overlap on y_e . Next, suppose that e has both its endpoints in $V(G) \setminus S$. Then, as σ_1 and σ_2 overlap on both x_u and x_v , the expression $x_u \oplus x_v$ takes the same truth value under σ_1 and σ_2 . So, again, σ_1 and σ_2 must overlap on y_e . Next, suppose that e has one endpoint (say u) in S and the other endpoint in $V(G) \setminus S$. Then, as σ_1 and σ_2 differ on x_u and overlap on x_v , the expression $x_u \oplus x_v$ takes different truth values under σ_1 and σ_2 . So, as both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the equation $x_u \oplus x_v \oplus y_e = 0$, it follows that σ_1 and σ_2 must differ on y_e . So, overall, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on $e(S, \bar{S})$ many y variables.

For any vertex $v \in V(G)$, since any satisfying assignment satisfies the equations $x_v \oplus x_v^1 = 0, x_v^1 \oplus x_v^2 = 0, \dots, x_v^{3k-1} \oplus x_v^{3k} = 0$, it must assign the same truth value to $x_v, x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k}$. So, for any $v \in S$, as σ_1 and σ_2 differ on x_v , they also differ on x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k} . Similarly, for any $v \in V(G) \setminus S$, as σ_1 and σ_2 overlap on x_v , they also overlap on x_v^1, \dots, x_v^{3k} . So, overall, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on $|S|$ many x variables and their $3k \cdot |S|$ copies. Now, summing up the numbers of y variables and x variables (and their copies) on which σ_1 and σ_2 differ, we get

$$\begin{aligned} e(S, \bar{S}) + (3k + 1) \cdot |S| &= d \\ &= k \cdot (3k + 4). \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Let $e(S, S)$ denote the number of edges in G that have both endpoints in S . Note that

$$\sum_{v \in S} \text{degree}_G(v) = 2 \cdot e(S, S) + e(S, \bar{S}).$$

Also, as G is a cubic graph, we know that $\text{degree}_G(v) = 3$ for all $v \in S$. Therefore, we get $e(S, \bar{S}) = 3 \cdot |S| - 2 \cdot e(S, S)$. Putting this expression for $e(S, \bar{S})$ in (1), we have

$$(3k + 4) \cdot (|S| - k) = 2 \cdot e(S, S). \quad (2)$$

If $|S| \geq k + 1$, then LHS of (1) becomes $\geq (3k + 1) \cdot (k + 1) = k \cdot (3k + 4) + 1$, which is greater than its RHS. So, we must have $|S| \leq k$. Also, as RHS of (2) is non-negative, so must be its LHS. This gives us $|S| \geq k$. Therefore, it follows that $|S| = k$. Putting $|S| = k$ in (2), we also get $e(S, S) = 0$. That is, S is an independent set of G . Hence, (G, k) is a YES instance of Independent Set. This proves Theorem 1. \square

Theorem 2. Max Differ Affine-SAT is NP-hard, even on 4-affine formulas.

Proof. We describe a reduction from Multicolored Clique on Regular graphs. Consider an instance (G, k) of Multicolored Clique, where G is a r -regular graph. We assume that each color-class of G has size N of the form $2 \cdot 3^q$ (see Remark 1). We construct an affine formula Φ as follows: For every vertex $v \in V(G)$, introduce a variable x_v and its ℓ copies (say $x_v^1, x_v^2, \dots, x_v^\ell$), where $\ell := k \cdot (r - k + 1) + k \cdot q$. We force these copies to take the same truth value as x_v via the equations $x_v \oplus x_v^1 = 0, x_v^1 \oplus x_v^2 = 0, \dots, x_v^{\ell-1} \oplus x_v^\ell = 0$. For every edge $e = uv \in E(G)$, we add variables y_e and z_e , and also the equation $x_u \oplus x_v \oplus y_e \oplus z_e = 1$.

For any $1 \leq i \leq k$, consider the i^{th} color-class, say $V_i = \{v_i^1, v_i^2, \dots, v_i^N\}$. First, we add $N/3$ many *Stage 1 dummy variables* (say $d_{i,1}^1, d_{i,1}^2, \dots, d_{i,1}^{N/3}$), group the x variables corresponding to the vertices of V_i into $N/3$ triplets, and add $N/3$ equations that equate the xor of a triplet's variables and a dummy variable to 0. More precisely, we add the following $N/3$ equations:

$$(x_{v_i^1} \oplus x_{v_i^2} \oplus x_{v_i^3}) \oplus d_{i,1}^1 = 0, (x_{v_i^4} \oplus x_{v_i^5} \oplus x_{v_i^6}) \oplus d_{i,1}^2 = 0, \dots, (x_{v_i^{N-2}} \oplus x_{v_i^{N-1}} \oplus x_{v_i^N}) \oplus d_{i,1}^{N/3} = 0$$

Next, we repeat the same process as follows: We introduce $N/3^2$ many *Stage 2 dummy variables* (say $d_{i,2}^1, d_{i,2}^2, \dots, d_{i,2}^{N/3^2}$), group the $N/3$ many Stage 1 dummy variables into $N/3^2$ triplets, and add $N/3^2$ equations that equate the xor of a triplet's Stage 1 dummy variables and a Stage 2 dummy variable to 0. More precisely, we add the following $N/3^2$ equations:

$$(d_{i,1}^1 \oplus d_{i,1}^2 \oplus d_{i,1}^3) \oplus d_{i,2}^1 = 0, (d_{i,1}^4 \oplus d_{i,1}^5 \oplus d_{i,1}^6) \oplus d_{i,2}^2 = 0, \dots, (d_{i,1}^{N/3-2} \oplus d_{i,1}^{N/3-1} \oplus d_{i,1}^{N/3}) \oplus d_{i,2}^{N/3^2} = 0$$

Repeating the same procedure, we add the following $N/3^3, N/3^4, \dots, N/3^q = 2$ equations:

$$(d_{i,2}^1 \oplus d_{i,2}^2 \oplus d_{i,2}^3) \oplus d_{i,3}^1 = 0, (d_{i,2}^4 \oplus d_{i,2}^5 \oplus d_{i,2}^6) \oplus d_{i,3}^2 = 0, \dots, (d_{i,2}^{N/3^2-2} \oplus d_{i,2}^{N/3^2-1} \oplus d_{i,2}^{N/3^2}) \oplus d_{i,3}^{N/3^3} = 0$$

$$(d_{i,3}^1 \oplus d_{i,3}^2 \oplus d_{i,3}^3) \oplus d_{i,4}^1 = 0, (d_{i,3}^4 \oplus d_{i,3}^5 \oplus d_{i,3}^6) \oplus d_{i,4}^2 = 0, \dots, (d_{i,3}^{N/3^3-2} \oplus d_{i,3}^{N/3^3-1} \oplus d_{i,3}^{N/3^3}) \oplus d_{i,4}^{N/3^4} = 0$$

\vdots

$$(d_{i,q-1}^1 \oplus d_{i,q-1}^2 \oplus d_{i,q-1}^3) \oplus d_{i,q}^1 = 0, (d_{i,q-1}^4 \oplus d_{i,q-1}^5 \oplus d_{i,q-1}^6) \oplus d_{i,q}^2 = 0$$

Next, we add $B + 1$ *auxiliary variables* (say D_i^1, \dots, D_i^{B+1}) and the following equations:

$$(d_{i,q}^1 \oplus d_{i,q}^2) \oplus D_i^1 = 0, (d_{i,q}^1 \oplus d_{i,q}^2) \oplus D_i^2 = 0, \dots, (d_{i,q}^1 \oplus d_{i,q}^2) \oplus D_i^{B+1} = 0,$$

where $B := k \cdot (\ell + 1) + k \cdot (r - k + 1) + k \cdot q$ is the budget that we set on the total number of overlaps. That is, we set $d = n - B$, where n denotes the number of variables in Φ . Now, we prove that (G, k) is a YES instance of Multicolored Clique if and only if (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Max Differ Affine-SAT. We present a proof sketch of this equivalence below.

Forward direction. In the first assignment, we set i) all x and y variables to 0, ii) all z variables to 1, and iii) all dummy and auxiliary variables to 0. In the second assignment, we assign i) 0 to the k many x variables that correspond to the multi-colored clique's vertices, ii) 1 to the remaining x variables, iii) 0 to all z variables, iv) 0 to the $k \cdot (r - k + 1)$ many y variables that correspond to those edges that have one endpoint inside the multi-colored clique and the other endpoint outside it, v) 1 to the remaining y variables, and vi) 1 to all auxiliary variables. Also, in the second assignment, for each $1 \leq i \leq k$, we assign i) 0 to that Stage 1 dummy variable which was grouped with the x variable corresponding to the multi-colored clique's vertex from the i^{th} color-class, 0 to that Stage 2 dummy variable which was grouped with this Stage 1 dummy variable, 0 to that Stage 3 dummy variable which was grouped with this Stage 2 dummy variable, and so on \dots , and ii) 1 to the remaining dummy variables. It can be verified that these two assignments satisfy Φ , and they overlap on B many variables.

Reverse direction. First, we show that each of the k color-classes has at least one vertex on whose corresponding x variable the two assignments overlap. Consider any $1 \leq i \leq k$. Since the $B+1$ auxiliary variables are forced to take the same truth value and there are only at most B overlaps, the two assignments must differ on them. This forces the two assignments to overlap on one of the two Stage q dummy variables. Further, this forces at least one overlap amongst the three Stage $q-1$ dummy variables that were grouped with this Stage q dummy variable. This effect propagates to lower-indexed stages, and eventually forces at least one overlap amongst the x variables corresponding to the vertices of the i^{th} color-class.

Next, we show that each of the k color-classes has at most one vertex on whose corresponding x variable the two assignments overlap. Suppose not. Then, there are at least two overlaps amongst the x variables corresponding to the vertices of some color class. Also, based on the previous paragraph, we know that there is at least one overlap amongst the x variables corresponding to the vertices of each of the remaining $k-1$ color classes. Therefore, overall, there are at least $k+1$ many overlaps amongst the x variables. So, the contribution of these x variables and their copies to the total number of overlaps becomes $\geq (k+1) \cdot (\ell+1) = B+1$. However, this exceeds the budget B on the number of overlaps, which is a contradiction.

Based on the previous two paragraphs, we know that for each $1 \leq i \leq k$, there is exactly one overlap amongst the x variables corresponding to the vertices of the i^{th} color class. Finally, we show that the set, say S , formed by these k vertices is the desired multi-colored clique. Suppose not. Then, there are $> k \cdot (r - k + 1)$ edges that have one endpoint in S and the other endpoint outside S . Also, for each such edge, the two assignments must overlap on one of its corresponding y and z variables. Therefore, we have $> k \cdot (r - k + 1)$ overlaps on the y and z variables. Also, $k \cdot q$ overlaps are forced on the dummy variables via the equations added in the grouping procedure. Thus, overall, the total number of overlaps exceeds B , which is a contradiction. This concludes a proof sketch of Theorem 2. \square

Remark 1. *In the proof of Theorem 2, we assumed that the instance (G, k) of Multicolored Clique is such that each color-class of the r -regular graph G has size N of the form $2 \cdot 3^q$. We argue the safety of this assumption as follows: Note that the reduction described in [26] from Clique on Regular graphs to Multicolored Clique on Regular graphs is such that i) every color-class of reduced graph has size equal to the number of vertices in the original graph, and ii) degree of the reduced regular graph is a multiple of the degree of the original regular graph. So, as the sum of degrees (i.e., product of degree and number of vertices) in the original graph must be even, it follows that the product of degree (i.e., r) and size of color-class (i.e., N) in the reduced graph must be even. Now, consider the smallest integer (say T) of the form $2 \cdot 3^q$ that exceeds N by at least $r + 1$. As $(T - N) \cdot r$ is even (because T is even and $N \cdot r$*

Figure 13: This figure shows the bipartite components of the graph G_1 constructed in the proof of Theorem 3, when the 2-affine formula Φ' consists of the following equations: $u \oplus a = 1$, $u \oplus b = 1$, $u \oplus c = 1$, $v \oplus a = 1$, $v \oplus b = 1$, $v \oplus c = 1$, $s \oplus p = 1$, $s \oplus q = 1$, $t \oplus p = 1$, $t \oplus q = 1$, $r \oplus f = 1$, $g \oplus w = 1$, $g \oplus f = 1$, $g \oplus z = 1$, $h \oplus f = 1$, $h \oplus z = 1$.

is even) and $T - N \geq r + 1$, there exists an r -regular graph on $T - N$ vertices.⁶ Adding this r -regular graph to each color-class of G gives an equivalent instance of Multicolored Clique where the new graph is still r -regular, and each color-class has size (i.e., T) of the form $2 \cdot 3^q$.

Theorem 3. Exact/Max Differ Affine-SAT is polynomial-time solvable on 2-affine formulas.

Proof. Consider an instance (Φ, d) of Exact Differ Affine-SAT, where Φ is a 2-affine formula. First, we construct a graph G_0 as follows: Introduce a vertex for every variable of Φ . For every equation of the form $x \oplus y = 0$ in Φ , add the edge xy . We compute the connected components of G_0 . Observe that for each component C of G_0 , the equations of Φ corresponding to the edges of C are simultaneously satisfied if and only if all variables of C take the same truth value. So, any pair of satisfying assignments of Φ either overlap on all variables in C , or differ on all variables in C . Thus, we replace all variables in C by a single variable, and set its weight to be the size of C . More precisely, i) we remove all but one variable (say z) of C from the variable-set of Φ , ii) we remove all those equations from Φ that correspond to the edges of C , iii) for every variable $v \in C \setminus \{z\}$, we replace the remaining appearances of v in Φ (i.e., in equations of the form $v \oplus _ = 1$) with z , and iv) we set the weight of z to be the number of variables in C . Let Φ' denote the variable-weighted affine formula so obtained. Then, our goal is to decide whether Φ' has a pair of satisfying assignments such that the weights of the variables at which they differ add up to exactly d .

Note that all equations in Φ' are of the form $x \oplus y = 1$. Next, we construct a vertex-weighted graph G_1 as follows: Introduce a vertex for every variable of Φ' , and assign it the same weight as that of its corresponding variable. For every equation $x \oplus y = 1$ of Φ' , add the edge xy . We compute the connected components of G_1 . Then, we run a bipartiteness-testing algorithm on each component of G_1 . Suppose that there is a component C of G_1 that is not bipartite. Then, there is an odd-length cycle in C , say with vertices $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{2\ell}, x_{2\ell+1}$ (in that order). Note that the edges of this cycle correspond to the equations $x_1 \oplus x_2 = 1$, $x_2 \oplus x_3 = 1$, \dots , $x_{2\ell} \oplus x_{2\ell+1} = 1$, $x_{2\ell+1} \oplus x_1 = 1$ in Φ' . Adding (modulo 2) these $2\ell + 1$ equations, we get LHS = $(2 \cdot x_1 + 2 \cdot x_2 + \dots + 2 \cdot x_{2\ell+1}) \bmod 2 = 0$, and RHS = $(2\ell + 1) \bmod 2 = 1$. So, these $2\ell + 1$ equations of Φ' cannot be simultaneously satisfied. Thus, we return NO. Now, assume that all components of G_1 are bipartite. See Figure 13 for an example.

Let C_1, \dots, C_p denote the connected components of G_1 . Consider any $1 \leq i \leq p$. Let

⁶See the necessary-and-sufficient condition for existence of regular graphs in [83].

A and B denote the parts of the bipartite component C_i . Observe that the equations of Φ' corresponding to the edges of C_i are simultaneously satisfied if and only if either i) all variables in A are set to 1, and all variables in B are set to 0, or ii) all variables in A are set to 0, and all variables in B are set to 1. So, any pair of satisfying assignments of Φ' either overlap on all variables in C_i , or differ on all variables in C_i . Thus, our problem amounts to deciding whether there is a subset of components of G_1 whose collective weight is exactly d . That is, our goal is to decide whether there exists $X \subseteq [p]$ such that $\sum_{i \in X} \text{weight}(C_i) = d$, where $\text{weight}(C_i)$ denotes the sum of the weights of the variables in C_i . To do so, we use the algorithm for Subset Sum problem with $\{\text{weight}(C_1), \dots, \text{weight}(C_p)\}$ as the multi-set of integers and d as the target sum.

The algorithm described here works almost as it is for Max Differ Affine-SAT too. In the last step, instead of reducing to Subset Sum problem, we simply check whether the collective weight of all components of G_1 is at least d . That is, if $\sum_{i=1}^p \text{weight}(C_i) \geq d$, we return YES; otherwise, we return NO. Thus, both Exact Differ Affine-SAT and Max Differ Affine-SAT are polynomial-time solvable on 2-affine formulas. This proves Theorem 3. \square

Theorem 4. Exact Differ Affine-SAT is $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter d .

Proof. We describe a reduction from Exact Even Set. Consider an instance $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ of Exact Even Set. We construct an affine formula Φ as follows: For every element u in the universe \mathcal{U} , introduce a variable x_u . For every set S in the family \mathcal{F} , introduce the equation $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 0$.

We set $d = k$. We prove that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Even Set if and only if (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT. At a high level, we argue this equivalence as follows: In the forward direction, we show that the two desired satisfying assignments are i) the all 0 assignment, and ii) the assignment that assigns 1 to the variables that correspond to the elements of the given even set, and assigns 0 to the remaining variables. In the reverse direction, we show that the desired even set consists of those elements of the universe that correspond to the variables on which the two given satisfying assignments differ. We make this argument precise below.

Forward direction. Suppose that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Even Set. That is, there is a set $X \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ of size exactly k such that $|X \cap S|$ is even for all sets S in the family \mathcal{F} . Let σ_1 and σ_2 be assignments of Φ defined as follows: For every $u \in X$, σ_1 sets x_u to 0, and σ_2 sets x_u to 1. For every $u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus X$, both σ_1 and σ_2 set x_u to 0. Note that σ_1 and σ_2 differ on exactly $|X| = k$ variables. Consider any set S in the family \mathcal{F} . The equation corresponding to S in the formula Φ is $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 0$. All variables in the left-hand side are set to 0 by σ_1 .

Also, the number of variables in the left-hand side that are set to 1 by σ_2 is $|X \cap S|$, which is an even number. Therefore, the left-hand side evaluates to 0 under both σ_1 and σ_2 . So, σ_1 and σ_2 are satisfying assignments of Φ . Hence, (Φ, k) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT.

Reverse direction. Suppose that (Φ, k) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT. That is, there are satisfying assignments σ_1 and σ_2 of Φ that differ on exactly k variables. Let X denote the k -sized set $\{u \in \mathcal{U} \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } x_u\}$. Consider any set S in the family \mathcal{F} . The equation corresponding to S in the formula Φ is $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 0$. We split the left-hand side into two parts to express this equation as $\underbrace{\bigoplus_{u \in S \setminus X} x_u}_A \oplus \underbrace{\bigoplus_{u \in X \cap S} x_u}_B = 0$. Note that σ_1 and σ_2

overlap on all variables in the first part, i.e., A . So, A evaluates to the same truth value under

both assignments. Thus, as both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy this equation, they must assign the same truth value to the second part, i.e., B , as well. Also, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on all variables in B . So, for its truth value to be same under both assignments, B must have an even number of variables. That is, $|X \cap S|$ must be even. Hence, $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Even Set. This proves Theorem 4. \square

Theorem 5. Max Differ Affine-SAT admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(2^d)^7$.

Proof. Consider an instance (Φ, d) of Max Differ Affine-SAT. We use Gaussian elimination to find the solution set of Φ in polynomial-time. If Φ has no solution, we return NO. If Φ has a unique solution and $d = 0$, we return YES. If Φ has a unique solution and $d \geq 1$, we return NO. Now, assume that Φ has multiple solutions.

Let F denote the set of all free variables. Suppose that $|F| \geq d$. Let σ_1 denote the solution of Φ obtained by setting all free variables to 0, and then setting the forced variables to take values as per their dependence on the free variables. Similarly, let σ_2 denote the solution of Φ obtained by setting all free variables to 1, and then setting the forced variables to take values as per their dependence on the free variables. Note that σ_1 and σ_2 differ on all free variables (and possibly some forced variables too). So, overall, they differ on at least $|F| \geq d$ variables. Thus, we return YES. Now, assume that $|F| \leq d - 1$. We guess the subset $D \subseteq F$ of free variables on which two desired solutions (say σ_1 and σ_2) differ. Note that there are $2^{|F|} \leq 2^{d-1}$ such guesses.

First, consider any forced variable x that depends on an odd number of free variables from D . That is, the expression for its value is the XOR of an odd number of free variables from D (possibly along with the constant 1 and/or some free variables from $F \setminus D$). Then, note that this expression takes different truth values under σ_1 and σ_2 . That is, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on x .

Next, consider any forced variable x that depends on an even number of free variables from D . That is, the expression for its value is the XOR of an even number of free variables from D (possibly along with the constant 1 and/or some free variables from $F \setminus D$). Then, note that this expression takes the same truth value under σ_1 and σ_2 . That is, σ_1 and σ_2 overlap on x .

Thus, overall, these two solutions differ on i) all free variables from D , and ii) all those forced variables that depend upon an odd number of free variables from D . If the total count of such variables is $\geq d$ for some guess D , we return YES. Otherwise, we return NO. This proves Theorem 5. \square

Theorem 6. Max Differ Affine-SAT admits a kernel with $\mathcal{O}(d^2)$ variables and $\mathcal{O}(d^2)$ equations.

Proof. Consider an instance (Φ, d) of Max Differ Affine-SAT. We use Gaussian elimination to find the solution set of Φ in polynomial-time. Then, as in the proof of Theorem 5, i) we return NO if Φ has no solution, or if Φ has a unique solution and $d \geq 1$, ii) we return YES if Φ has a unique solution and $d = 0$, or if Φ has multiple solutions with at least d free variables. Now, assume that Φ has multiple solutions with at most $d - 1$ free variables.

Note that the expression for the value of any forced variable (i.e., its value in terms of values of free variables) can be treated as a linear equation. Observe that the system of these equations (one for each forced variable) is an affine formula (say Φ') that is equivalent to Φ . That is,

⁷The notation $\mathcal{O}^*(\cdot)$ hides polynomial factors.

Φ' and Φ have the same solution sets. So, we work with the instance (Φ', d) in the remaining proof. Note that every equation in Φ' has exactly one forced variable and some free variables.

Suppose that there is a free variable, say x , such that at least $d - 1$ forced variables depend on x . That is, there are at least $d - 1$ forced variables y such that the expression for the value of y is XOR of x and some other free variables (possibly along with the constant 1). Let σ_1 denote the solution of Φ' obtained by setting all free variables to 0, and then setting the forced variables to take values as per their dependence on the free variables. Let σ_2 denote the solution of Φ' obtained by setting x to 1 and the remaining free variables to 0, and then setting the forced variables to take values as per their dependence on the free variables. Note that σ_1 and σ_2 differ on x , and also on each of the $\geq d - 1$ forced variables that depend on x . So, overall, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on at least d variables. Thus, we return YES.

Now, assume that for every free variable x , there are at most $d - 2$ forced variables that depend on x . So, as there are at most $d - 1$ free variables, it follows that there are at most $(d - 1) \cdot (d - 2)$ forced variables that depend on at least one free variable. The remaining forced variables are the ones that do not depend on any free variable. That is, any such forced variable y is set to a constant (i.e., 0 or 1) as per the expression for its value. We remove the variable y and its corresponding equation (i.e., $y = 0$ or $y = 1$) from Φ' , and we leave d unchanged. This is safe because y takes the same truth value under all solutions of Φ' .

Note that the affine formula so obtained has at most $d - 1$ free variables and at most $(d - 1) \cdot (d - 2)$ forced variables. So, overall, it has at most $(d - 1)^2$ variables. Also, it has at most $(d - 1) \cdot (d - 2)$ equations. This proves Theorem 6. \square

Theorem 7. Exact/Max Differ Affine-SAT is $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter $n - d$.

Proof. We describe a reduction from Exact Odd Set to Exact Differ Affine-SAT. Consider an instance $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ of Exact Odd Set. We construct an affine formula Φ as follows: For every element u in the universe \mathcal{U} , introduce a variable x_u . For every odd-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} , introduce the equation $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 1$. For every even-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} , introduce $k + 1$ variables $y_S, z_S^1, z_S^2, \dots, z_S^k$, and the equations $y_S \oplus z_S^1 = 0, y_S \oplus z_S^2 = 0, \dots, y_S \oplus z_S^k = 0$ and $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u \oplus y_S = 0$. The number of variables in Φ is $n = |\mathcal{U}| + (k + 1) \cdot |\{S \in \mathcal{F} \mid |S| \text{ is even}\}|$. We set $d = n - k$.

We prove that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Odd Set if and only if (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT. At a high level, we argue this equivalence as follows: In the forward direction, we show that the two desired satisfying assignments are i) the assignment that sets all y and z variables to 0 and all x variables to 1, and ii) the assignment that sets all y and z variables to 1, assigns 1 to all those x variables that correspond to the elements of the given odd set, and assigns 0 to the remaining x variables. In the reverse direction, we show that the two assignments must differ on all y and z variables (and so, all k overlaps are restricted to occur at x variables), and the desired odd set consists of those elements of the universe that correspond to the x variables on which the two assignments overlap. We make this argument precise below.

Forward direction. Suppose that $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Odd Set. That is, there is a set $X \subseteq \mathcal{U}$ of size exactly k such that $|X \cap S|$ is odd for all sets S in the family \mathcal{F} . Let σ_1 and σ_2 be assignments of Φ defined as follows: For every even-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} , σ_1 sets $y_S, z_S^1, z_S^2, \dots, z_S^k$ to 0, and σ_2 sets $y_S, z_S^1, z_S^2, \dots, z_S^k$ to 1. For every $u \in X$, both σ_1 and σ_2 set x_u to 1. For every $u \in \mathcal{U} \setminus X$, σ_1 sets x_u to 1, and σ_2 sets x_u to 0. Note that

σ_1 and σ_2 overlap on exactly $|X| = k$ variables (and so, they differ on exactly $n - k$ variables). Now, we show that σ_1 and σ_2 are satisfying assignments of Φ .

First, we argue that σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the equations of Φ that were added corresponding to odd-sized sets of the family \mathcal{F} . Consider any odd-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} . The equation corresponding to S in the formula Φ is $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 1$. The number of variables in the left-hand side that are set to 1 by σ_2 is $|X \cap S|$, which is an odd number. Also, all $|S|$ (again, which is an odd number) variables in the left-hand side are set to 1 by σ_1 . Therefore, the left-hand side evaluates to 1 under both σ_1 and σ_2 . So, both these assignments satisfy the equation $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 1$.

Next, we argue that σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the equations of Φ that were added corresponding to even-sized sets of the family \mathcal{F} . Consider any even-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} . The $k + 1$ equations corresponding to S in the formula Φ are $y_S \oplus z_S^1 = 0, y_S \oplus z_S^2 = 0, \dots, y_S \oplus z_S^k = 0$ and $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u \oplus y_S = 0$. Consider any of the first k equations, say $y_S \oplus z_S^i = 0$, where $1 \leq i \leq k$.

Both variables on the left-hand side, i.e., y_S and z_S^i , are assigned the same truth value, i.e., both 0 by σ_1 and both 1 by σ_2 . So, both these assignments satisfy the equation $y_S \oplus z_S^i = 0$. Next, consider the last equation, i.e., $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u \oplus y_S = 0$. The number of variables amongst

$x_u|_{u \in S}$ that are set to 1 by σ_2 is $|X \cap S|$, which is an odd number. Also, the variable y_S is set to 1 by σ_2 . Therefore, overall, the number of variables in the left-hand side that are set to 1 by σ_2 is even. Also, σ_1 sets all variables on the left-hand side to 1 except y_S . That is, it sets all the $|S|$ (again, which is an even number) variables $x_u|_{u \in S}$ to 1. Therefore, the left-hand side evaluates to 0 under both σ_1 and σ_2 . So, both these assignments satisfy the equation $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u \oplus y_S = 0$. Hence, $(\Phi, n - k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT.

Reverse direction. Suppose that $(\Phi, n - k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Differ Affine-SAT. That is, there are satisfying assignments σ_1 and σ_2 of Φ that overlap on exactly k variables. Consider any even-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} . As σ_1 satisfies the equations $y_S \oplus z_S^1 = 0, y_S \oplus z_S^2 = 0, \dots, y_S \oplus z_S^k = 0$, it must assign the same truth value to all the $k + 1$ variables $y_S, z_S^1, z_S^2, \dots, z_S^k$. Similarly, σ_2 must assign the same truth value to $y_S, z_S^1, z_S^2, \dots, z_S^k$. Therefore, either σ_1 and σ_2 overlap on all these $k + 1$ variables, or they differ on all these $k + 1$ variables. So, as there are only k overlaps, σ_1 and σ_2 must differ on $y_S, z_S^1, z_S^2, \dots, z_S^k$. Thus, all the k overlaps occur at x variables. Let X denote the k -sized set $\{u \in \mathcal{U} \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } x_u\}$. Now, we show that $|X \cap S|$ is odd for all sets S in the family \mathcal{F} .

First, we argue that X has odd-sized intersection with all odd-sized sets of the family \mathcal{F} . Consider any odd-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} . The equation corresponding to S in the formula Φ is $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u = 1$. We split the left-hand side into two parts to express this equation as

$$\underbrace{\bigoplus_{u \in X \cap S} x_u}_A \oplus \underbrace{\bigoplus_{u \in S \setminus X} x_u}_B = 1. \text{ Note that } \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ overlap on all variables in the first part, i.e.,}$$

A. So, A evaluates to the same truth value under both assignments. Thus, as both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy this equation, they must assign the same truth value to the second part, i.e., B, as well. Also, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on all variables in B. So, for its truth value to be same under both assignments, B must have an even number of variables. That is, $|S \setminus X|$ must be even. Now, as $|S|$ is odd and $|S \setminus X|$ is even, we infer that $|X \cap S| = |S| - |S \setminus X|$ is odd.

Next, we argue that X has odd-sized intersection with all even-sized sets of the family \mathcal{F} .

Consider any even-sized set S in the family \mathcal{F} . Amongst the $k + 1$ equations corresponding to S in the formula Φ , consider the last equation, i.e., $\bigoplus_{u \in S} x_u \oplus y_S = 0$. We split the left-hand side into two parts to express this equation as $\underbrace{\bigoplus_{u \in X \cap S} x_u}_A \oplus \underbrace{\bigoplus_{u \in S \setminus X} x_u}_B \oplus y_S = 0$. Note that σ_1

and σ_2 overlap on all variables in the first part, i.e., A . So, A evaluates to the same truth value under both assignments. Thus, as both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy this equation, they must assign the same truth value to the second part, i.e., B . Also, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on all variables in B . So, for its truth value to be same under both assignments, B must have an even number of variables. That is, $|S \setminus X| + 1$ must be even. Now, as $|S|$ is even and $|S \setminus X|$ is odd, we infer that $|X \cap S| = |S| - |S \setminus X|$ is odd. Hence, $(\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{F}, k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Odd Set.

This reduction also works with Odd Set as the source problem and Max Differ Affine-SAT as the target problem. So, both Exact Differ Affine-SAT and Max Differ Affine-SAT are $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter $n - d$. This proves Theorem 7. \square

2-CNF formulas

Theorem 8. Max Differ 2-SAT is polynomial-time solvable on $(2, 2)$ -CNF formulas.

Proof. Consider an instance (Φ, d) of Max Differ 2-SAT, where Φ is a $(2, 2)$ -CNF formula on n variables. We construct a graph G as follows: For every variable x of Φ , introduce vertices $x[0]$ and $x[1]$. We add an edge corresponding to each clause of Φ as follows: For every clause of the form $x \vee y$, add the edge $\{x[1], y[1]\}$. For every clause of the form $\neg x \vee \neg y$, add the edge $\{x[0], y[0]\}$. For every clause of the form $x \vee \neg y$, add the edge $\{x[1], y[0]\}$. We refer to such edges as *clause-edges*. Also, for every variable x of Φ , add the edge $\{x[0], x[1]\}$. We refer to such edges as *matching-edges*. See Figure 14 for an example.

The structure of G can be understood as follows: In the absence of matching-edges, the graph is a disjoint union of some paths and cycles. Some of these paths/cycles get glued together upon the addition of matching-edges. Observe that a matching-edge can either join a terminal vertex of one path with a terminal vertex of another path, or join any vertex of a path/cycle to an isolated vertex. These are the only two possibilities because the endpoints of any matching-edge together can have only at most two neighbors (apart from each other). Thus, once the matching-edges are added, observe that each component of G becomes a path or a cycle, possibly with pendant matching-edges attached to some of its vertices. We call them *path-like* and *cycle-like* components respectively. We further classify a cycle-like component based on the parity of the length of its corresponding cycle: *odd-cycle-like* and *even-cycle-like*. For each of these three types of components, we analyze the maximum number of its variables on which any two assignments can differ such that both of them satisfy all clauses corresponding to its clause-edges. Consider any component, say C , of G .

Case 1. C is a path-like component.

Starting from one of the two terminal vertices of the corresponding path, i) let $x_1[i_1], x_2[i_2], x_3[i_3] \dots$ denote the odd-positioned vertices, and ii) let $y_1[j_1], y_2[j_2], y_3[j_3], \dots$ denote the even-positioned vertices. That is, the path has these vertices in the following order: $x_1[i_1], y_1[j_1], x_2[i_2], y_2[j_2], x_3[i_3], y_3[j_3], \dots$ and so on.

Let σ_1 denote the following assignment: i) σ_1 sets x_1 to i_1, x_2 to i_2, x_3 to i_3, \dots and so on. ii) For those $y_k[j_k]$'s (amongst $y_1[j_1], y_2[j_2], y_3[j_3], \dots$) whose neighbor along the matching-edge

Figure 14: This figure shows the graph G constructed in the proof of Theorem 8 when the input $(2, 2)$ -CNF formula Φ is $(x \vee y) \wedge (y \vee \neg z) \wedge (\neg z \vee \neg c) \wedge (c \vee b) \wedge (b \vee a) \wedge (\neg a \vee \neg x) \wedge (t \vee p) \wedge (p \vee \neg q) \wedge (\neg q \vee r) \wedge (\neg r \vee s) \wedge (\neg s \vee \neg t) \wedge (\neg u \vee \neg v) \wedge (v \vee w) \wedge (w \vee f) \wedge (\neg f \vee g) \wedge (g \vee \neg h)$. The red line segments denote the matching-edges, and the black line segments denote the clause-edges. Note that G has one odd-cycle-like component, one even-cycle-like component and one path-like component.

(i.e., $y_k[1 - j_k]$) is not one of its two neighbors along the path (i.e., $x_k[i_k]$ and $x_{k+1}[i_{k+1}]$), and rather hangs as a pendant vertex attached to $y_k[j_k]$: σ_1 sets y_k to $1 - j_k$. Similarly, let σ_2 denote the following assignment: i) σ_2 sets y_1 to j_1 , y_2 to j_2 , y_3 to j_3 , \dots and so on. ii) For those $x_k[i_k]$'s (amongst $x_1[i_1]$, $x_2[i_2]$, $x_3[i_3]$, \dots) whose neighbor along the matching-edge (i.e., $x_k[1 - i_k]$) is not one of its two neighbors along the path (i.e., $y_{k-1}[j_{k-1}]$ and $y_k[j_k]$), and rather hangs as a pendant vertex attached to $x_k[i_k]$: σ_2 sets x_k to $1 - i_k$.

Observe that any clause-edge of C is of the form $\{x_k[i_k], y_k[j_k]\}$ or $\{y_k[j_k], x_{k+1}[i_{k+1}]\}$. In either case, both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the corresponding clause. This is because i) in the first case, σ_1 sets x_k to i_k and σ_2 sets y_k to j_k , and ii) in the second case, σ_1 sets x_{k+1} to i_{k+1} and σ_2 sets y_k to j_k . Thus, overall, both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C . Also, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on all variables that appear in C (i.e., x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots and y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots).

As an example, for the path-like component shown in Figure 14, starting from the terminal vertex $u[0]$, i) σ_1 sets u to 0, v to 1, w to 0, f to 1, g to 1, h to 1, and ii) σ_2 sets u to 1, v to 0, w to 1, f to 0, g to 0, h to 0.

Case 2. C is an even-cycle-like component.

Starting from an arbitrary vertex of the corresponding cycle, and moving along the cycle in one direction (say, clockwise): i) let $x_1[i_1], x_2[i_2], \dots, x_\ell[i_\ell]$ denote the odd-positioned vertices, and ii) let $y_1[j_1], y_2[j_2], \dots, y_\ell[j_\ell]$ denote the even-positioned vertices. That is, the cycle has these vertices in the following order: $x_1[i_1], y_1[j_1], x_2[i_2], y_2[j_2], \dots, x_\ell[i_\ell], y_\ell[j_\ell]$.

Let σ_1 denote the following assignment: i) σ_1 sets x_1 to i_1 , x_2 to i_2 , \dots , x_ℓ to i_ℓ . ii) For those $y_k[j_k]$'s (amongst $y_1[j_1]$, $y_2[j_2]$, \dots , $y_\ell[j_\ell]$) whose neighbor along the matching-edge

Figure 15: This figure is with reference to Case 3 in the proof of Theorem 8. Note that the removal of $y[0]$ and $y[1]$ from the odd-cycle-like component shown in Figure 14 results in a path-like component.

(i.e., $y_k[1 - j_k]$) is not one of its two neighbors along the cycle (i.e., $x_k[i_k]$ and $x_{k+1}[i_{k+1}]$ ⁸), and rather hangs as a pendant vertex attached to $y_k[j_k]$: σ_1 sets y_k to $1 - j_k$. Similarly, let σ_2 denote the following assignment: i) σ_2 sets y_1 to j_1 , y_2 to j_2 , ..., y_ℓ to j_ℓ . ii) For those $x_k[i_k]$'s (amongst $x_1[i_1]$, $x_2[i_2]$, ..., $x_\ell[i_\ell]$) whose neighbor along the matching-edge (i.e., $x_k[1 - i_k]$) is not one of its two neighbors along the cycle (i.e., $y_{k-1}[j_{k-1}]$ ⁹ and $y_k[j_k]$), and rather hangs as a pendant vertex attached to $x_k[i_k]$: σ_2 sets x_k to $1 - i_k$. Using the same argument as in Case 1, both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C , and they differ on all variables that appear in C (i.e., x_1, x_2, \dots, x_ℓ and y_1, y_2, \dots, y_ℓ).

As an example, for the even-cycle-like component shown in Figure 14, starting from the vertex $q[0]$, i) σ_1 sets q to 0, r to 0, s to 0, t to 1, p to 0, and ii) σ_2 sets r to 1, s to 1, t to 0, p to 1, q to 1.

Case 3. C is an odd-cycle-like component.

If every vertex $v[i]$ of the corresponding cycle is such that its neighbor along the matching-edge (i.e., $v[1 - i]$) also belongs to the cycle, then the cycle would have even-length. So, as the cycle has odd-length, it must have at least one vertex $v[i]$ such that $v[1 - i]$ is not one of its two neighbors along the cycle, and rather hangs as a pendant vertex attached to $v[i]$. Then, we construct assignments σ_1 and σ_2 as follows: Both σ_1 and σ_2 set v to i , thereby satisfying the two clauses that correspond to the two clause-edges that are incident to $v[i]$ along the cycle. Then, since $C \setminus \{v[i], v[1 - i]\}$ is a path-like component, we extend the assignments σ_1 and σ_2 to the remaining variables of C (i.e., other than v) in the manner described in Case 1. This ensures that both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C . Also, they differ on all but one variable (i.e., all except v) of C .

As an example, for the odd-cycle-like component shown in Figure 14, after setting y to 1 in both σ_1 and σ_2 , we remove $y[0]$ and $y[1]$ from the component (see Figure 15). Then, starting from the terminal vertex $z[0]$ of the path corresponding to the path-like component so obtained, i) σ_1 sets z to 0, c to 1, b to 0, a to 1, x to 0, and ii) σ_2 sets z to 1, c to 0, b to 1, a to 0, x to 1.

Next, we show that at least one overlap is unavoidable no matter how the variables of C are assigned truth values by a pair of satisfying assignments. For the sake of contradiction, assume that there are assignments σ_1 and σ_2 that satisfy all clauses corresponding to the

⁸When $k = \ell$, take $k + 1$ as 1.

⁹When $k = 1$, take $k - 1$ as ℓ .

clause-edges of C , and also differ on all variables of C . Then, construct vertex-subsets S_1 and S_2 of C as follows: For every variable x that appears in C , i) if σ_1 sets x to 0 (and so, σ_2 sets x to 1), then add $x[0]$ to S_1 and $x[1]$ to S_2 , and ii) if σ_1 sets x to 1 (and so, σ_2 sets x to 0), then add $x[1]$ to S_1 and $x[0]$ to S_2 . Observe that S_1 and S_2 are disjoint vertex covers of C . So, C must be a bipartite graph. However, this is not possible as C contains an odd-length cycle.

Thus, overall, based on Cases 1, 2, 3, we express the maximum number of variables on which any two satisfying assignments of Φ can differ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{C: C \text{ is a path-like component of } G} |vars(C)| + \sum_{C: C \text{ is an even-cycle-like component of } G} |vars(C)| + \sum_{C: C \text{ is an odd-cycle-like component of } G} (|vars(C)|-1) \\ & = n - |\{C \mid C \text{ is an odd-cycle-like component of } G\}|, \end{aligned}$$

where $vars(C)$ denotes the set of variables that appear in the component C . So, if the number of odd-cycle-like components in G is at most $n - d$, we return YES; otherwise, we return NO. This proves Theorem 8. \square

Theorem 9. *Exact Differ 2-SAT is polynomial-time solvable on $(2, 2)$ -CNF formulas.*

Proof. Consider an instance (Φ, d) of Exact Differ 2-SAT, where Φ is a $(2, 2)$ -CNF formula. We re-consider the graph G constructed in the proof of Theorem 8. Recall that G has three types of components, namely path-like components, even-cycle-like components and odd-cycle-like components. We further classify the even-cycle-like components into two categories: ones with pendants, and ones without pendants. That is, the former category consists of those even-cycle-like components whose corresponding cycles contain at least one vertex that has a pendant edge attached to it, while the latter category consists of all even-cycle components. For each of the four types of components, we analyze the possible values for the number of its variables on which any two assignments can differ such that both of them satisfy all clauses corresponding to its clause-edges. Consider any component, say C , of G . We use $vars(C)$ to denote the set of variables that appear in C .

Case 1. C is a path-like component.

Consider any $0 \leq \mu \leq |vars(C)|$. We move along the corresponding path, starting from one of its two terminal vertices. At any point, we say that a variable v has been *seen* if either i) both $v[0]$ and $v[1]$ are vertices of the sub-path traversed so far, or ii) one of $v[0]$ and $v[1]$ is a vertex of the sub-path traversed so far, and the other one hangs as a pendant vertex attached to it. We stop moving along the path once the first μ variables have been seen. Let $x[i]$ denote the path's vertex at which we stop, and let $y[j]$ denote its immediate next neighbor along the path. Observe that the edge joining $x[i]$ and $y[j]$ along the path is a clause-edge, whose removal breaks C into two smaller path-like components, say C_1 (containing x) and C_2 (containing y).

We construct assignments σ_1 and σ_2 as follows: For the path-like component C_1 , we re-apply the analysis of Case 1 in the proof of Theorem 8. That is, as described therein, σ_1 and σ_2 are made to set the variables of C_1 such that both of them satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C_1 , and they differ on all its $|vars(C_1)|$ many variables. Then, for the path-like component C_2 , both σ_1 and σ_2 are made to mimic one of the two assignments (namely, the one that sets y to j) constructed in Case 1 in the proof of Theorem 8. This ensures that both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C_2 , and they overlap

Figure 16: This figure is with reference to Case 1 in the proof of Theorem 9. Note that the removal of the clause-edge $\{w[1], f[1]\}$ from the path-like component shown in Figure 14 breaks it into two smaller path-like components.

on all its $|vars(C_2)|$ many variables. Further, since both σ_1 and σ_2 set y to j , they also satisfy the clause corresponding to the clause-edge $\{x[i], y[j]\}$. Thus, overall, both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C , and they differ on exactly $|vars(C_1)| = \mu$ many of its variables.

For example, consider the path-like component shown in Figure 14, and let $\mu = 3$. We traverse the corresponding path starting from the terminal vertex $u[0]$, and we stop at $w[1]$, i.e., once three variables have been seen. Now, removing the clause-edge $\{w[1], f[1]\}$ results in two path-like components: one on variables u, v, w , and the other on variables f, g, h (see Figure 16). Then, i) σ_1 sets u to 0, v to 1, w to 0, ii) σ_2 sets u to 1, v to 0, w to 1, and iii) both σ_1 and σ_2 set f to 1, g to 1, h to 1. So, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on u, v, w and overlap on f, g, h .

Case 2. C is an even-cycle-like component with pendants.

As argued in Case 2 in the proof of Theorem 8, we already know that there is a pair of assignments such that both of them satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C , and they differ on all its $|vars(C)|$ many variables. Next, consider any $0 \leq \mu \leq |vars(C)| - 1$. Arbitrarily fix a vertex $v[i]$ on the cycle corresponding to C such that its neighbor along the matching-edge (i.e., $v[1 - i]$) does not belong to the cycle, and rather hangs as a pendant vertex attached to $v[i]$. Then, we construct assignments σ_1 and σ_2 as follows: Both σ_1 and σ_2 set v to i , thereby satisfying the two clauses that correspond to the two clause-edges incident to $v[i]$ along the cycle. Then, since $C \setminus \{v[i], v[1 - i]\}$ is a path-like component, we apply the analysis of Case 1 on it (with the same μ) to assign truth-values to the variables in $vars(C) \setminus \{v\}$ under σ_1 and σ_2 . Note that both σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C . Also, they overlap on v , and they differ on exactly μ many variables in $vars(C) \setminus \{v\}$.

Case 3. C is an odd-cycle-like component.

As argued in Case 3 in the proof of Theorem 8, we already know that at least one overlap is unavoidable amongst the variables in $vars(C)$ for any pair of assignments that satisfy the clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C . Next, consider any $0 \leq \mu \leq |vars(C)| - 1$. Since the cycle corresponding to C has odd-length, it must contain a vertex $v[i]$ whose neighbor $v[1 - i]$ hangs as a pendant vertex attached to it. Then, using the same argument as that in Case 2, we obtain a pair of assignments such that both of them satisfy all clauses corresponding to the clause-edges of C , and they differ on exactly μ many variables in $vars(C)$.

Case 4. C is an even-length cycle.

Figure 17: This figure shows the even-length cycle C in Case 4 in the proof of Theorem 9.

Observe that the vertices in C , in order of their appearance along the cycle, must be of the following form: $x_1[i_1], x_1[1-i_1], x_2[i_2], x_2[1-i_2], \dots, x_\ell[i_\ell], x_\ell[1-i_\ell]$ (see Figure 17). Here, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_ℓ are variables, and $i_1, \dots, i_\ell \in \{0, 1\}$. Note that setting x_1 to i_1 forces x_2 to be set to i_2 (in order to satisfy the clause corresponding to the clause-edge $\{x_1[1-i_1], x_2[i_2]\}$), which in turn forces x_3 to be set to i_3 (in order to satisfy the clause corresponding to the clause-edge $\{x_2[1-i_2], x_3[i_3]\}$), \dots and so on. Similarly, setting x_1 to $1-i_1$ forces x_ℓ to be set to $1-i_\ell$ (in order to satisfy the clause corresponding to the clause-edge $\{x_\ell[1-i_\ell], x_1[i_1]\}$), which in turn forces $x_{\ell-1}$ to be set to $1-i_{\ell-1}$ (in order to satisfy the clause corresponding to the clause-edge $\{x_{\ell-1}[1-i_{\ell-1}], x_\ell[i_\ell]\}$), \dots and so on. Therefore, it is clear that there are only two different assignments that satisfy the clauses corresponding to the ℓ clause-edges of C : i) one that sets x_1 to i_1, x_2 to i_2, \dots, x_ℓ to i_ℓ , and ii) the other that sets x_1 to $1-i_1, x_2$ to $1-i_2, \dots, x_\ell$ to $1-i_\ell$. So, any pair of such assignments either i) differ on all $|vars(C)|$ many variables of C , or ii) overlap on all $|vars(C)|$ many variables of C .

Thus, overall, based on Cases 1, 2, 3, 4, we know the following: i) Amongst the variables of all path-like components, even-cycle-like components with pendants and odd-cycle-like components of G , the number d' of variables on which any two satisfying assignments can differ is allowed to take any value ranging from 0 to D (both inclusive), where

$$D := \sum_{\substack{C: C \text{ is a path-like component, or an} \\ \text{even-cycle-like component with pendants}}} |vars(C)| + \sum_{\substack{C: C \text{ is an odd-cycle-} \\ \text{like component}}} (|vars(C)| - 1),$$

and ii) amongst the variables of all even-cycle components of G (say C_1, C_2, \dots, C_t), the number of variables on which any two satisfying assignments can differ is allowed to take any value that can be obtained as a sum of some elements of $\{|vars(C_1)|, |vars(C_2)|, \dots, |vars(C_t)|\}$. So, for each $0 \leq d' \leq D$, we run the algorithm for Subset Sum problem on the multi-set $\{|vars(C_1)|, |vars(C_2)|, \dots, |vars(C_t)|\}$ with $d - d'$ as the target sum. We return YES if at least one of these runs returns YES; otherwise, we return NO. This proves Theorem 9. \square

Theorem 10. Exact/Max Differ 2-SAT is $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter d .

Proof. We describe a reduction from Independent Set. Consider an instance (G, k) of Independent Set. We construct a 2-CNF formula Φ as follows: For every vertex $v \in V(G)$, introduce two variables x_v and y_v ; we refer to them as x -variable and y -variable respectively.

For every edge $uv \in E(G)$, i) we add a clause that consists of the x -variables corresponding to the vertices u and v , i.e., $x_u \vee x_v$, and ii) we add a clause that consists of the y -variables corresponding to the vertices u and v , i.e., $y_u \vee y_v$. For every pair of vertices $u, v \in V(G)$, we add a clause that consists of the x -variable corresponding to u and the y -variable corresponding to v , i.e., $x_u \vee y_v$. We set $d = 2k$.

We prove that (G, k) is a YES instance of Independent Set if and only if (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Exact Differ 2-SAT. At a high level, we argue this equivalence as follows: In the forward direction, we show that the two desired satisfying assignments are i) the assignment that assigns 0 to all x -variables corresponding to the vertices of the given independent set, and 1 to the remaining variables, and ii) the assignment that assigns 0 to all y -variables corresponding to the vertices of the given independent set, and 1 to the remaining variables. In the reverse direction, we partition the set of variables on which the two given assignments differ into two parts: i) one part consists of those variables that are set to 1 by the first assignment, and 0 by the second assignment, and ii) the other part consists of those variables that are set to 0 by the first assignment, and 1 by the second assignment. Then, we show that at least one of these two parts has the desired size, and it is not a mix of x -variables and y -variables. That is, either it has only x -variables, or it has only y -variables. Finally, we show that the vertices that correspond to the variables in this part form the desired independent set. We make this argument precise below.

Forward direction. Suppose that (G, k) is a YES instance of Independent Set. That is, G has a k -sized independent set X . Let σ_1 and σ_2 be assignments of Φ defined as follows: For every vertex $v \in X$, i) σ_1 sets x_v to 0, σ_2 sets x_v to 1, and ii) σ_1 sets y_v to 1, σ_2 sets y_v to 0. For every vertex $v \in V(G) \setminus X$, both σ_1 and σ_2 set x_v and y_v to 1. Note that σ_1 and σ_2 differ on $2|X| = 2k$ variables, namely $x_v|_{v \in X}$ and $y_v|_{v \in X}$. Now, we show that σ_1 and σ_2 are satisfying assignments of Φ .

First, we argue that σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the clauses that were added corresponding to the edges of G . Consider an edge $uv \in E(G)$. The clauses added in Φ corresponding to this edge are $x_u \vee x_v$ and $y_u \vee y_v$. Since X is an independent set, no edge of G has both its endpoints inside X . So, at least one endpoint of the edge uv must be outside X . Without loss of generality, assume that $u \in V(G) \setminus X$. Then, both σ_1 and σ_2 set x_u and y_u to 1, thereby satisfying the clauses $x_u \vee x_v$ and $y_u \vee y_v$.

Next, we argue that σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the clauses that were added corresponding to the vertex-pairs of G . Consider a pair of vertices $u, v \in V(G)$. The clause added in Φ corresponding to this vertex-pair is $x_u \vee y_v$. Suppose that at least one of u and v lies outside X . If $u \in V(G) \setminus X$, then both σ_1 and σ_2 set x_u to 1. Similarly, if $v \in V(G) \setminus X$, then both σ_1 and σ_2 set y_v to 1. Therefore, in either case, σ_1 and σ_2 satisfy the clause $x_u \vee y_v$. Now, assume that both u and v lie inside X . Then, since σ_1 sets y_v to 1 and σ_2 sets x_u to 1, both these assignments satisfy the clause $x_u \vee y_v$. Hence, $(\Phi, 2k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Differ 2-SAT.

Reverse direction. Suppose that $(\Phi, 2k)$ is a YES instance of Exact Differ 2-SAT. That is, there are satisfying assignments σ_1 and σ_2 of Φ that differ on $2k$ variables. We partition the set of variables on which σ_1 and σ_2 differ as $D_1 \uplus D_2$, where i) D_1 denotes the set of those variables that are set to 1 by σ_1 and 0 by σ_2 , and ii) D_2 denotes the set of those variables that are set to 0 by σ_1 and 1 by σ_2 . Since $|D_1| + |D_2| = 2k$, at least one of D_1 and D_2 has size at least k . Without loss of generality, assume that $|D_1| \geq k$.

Now, we argue that either all variables in D_1 are x -variables, or all variables in D_1 are y -variables. For the sake of contradiction, assume that $x_u \in D_1$ and $y_v \in D_1$ for some vertices

$u, v \in V(G)$. That is, i) σ_1 sets both x_u and y_v to 1, and ii) σ_2 sets both x_u and y_v to 0. Then, σ_2 fails to satisfy the clause $x_u \vee y_v$ added in Φ corresponding to the vertex-pair u, v . However, this is not possible because σ_2 is given to be a satisfying assignment of Φ .

First, suppose that all variables in D_1 are x -variables. Let $X := \{u \in V(G) \mid x_u \in D_1\}$. Note that $|X| = |D_1| \geq k$. We show that X is an independent set of G . For the sake of contradiction, assume that there is an edge $uv \in E(G)$ with both endpoints in X . That is, i) σ_1 sets both x_u and x_v to 1, and ii) σ_2 sets both x_u and x_v to 0. Then, σ_2 fails to satisfy the clause $x_u \vee x_v$ added in Φ corresponding to the edge uv . However, this is not possible because σ_2 is given to be a satisfying assignment of Φ .

Next, suppose that all variables in D_1 are y -variables. Let $Y := \{u \in V(G) \mid y_u \in D_1\}$. Note that $|Y| = |D_1| \geq k$. We show that Y is an independent set of G . For the sake of contradiction, assume that there is an edge $uv \in E(G)$ with both endpoints in Y . That is, i) σ_1 sets both y_u and y_v to 1, and ii) σ_2 sets both y_u and y_v to 0. Then, σ_2 fails to satisfy the clause $y_u \vee y_v$ added in Φ corresponding to the edge uv . However, this is not possible because σ_2 is given to be a satisfying assignment of Φ . Hence, (G, k) is a YES instance of Independent Set.

This reduction also works with Max Differ 2-SAT as the target problem. So, both Exact Differ 2-SAT and Max Differ 2-SAT are $W[1]$ -hard in the parameter d . This proves Theorem 10. \square

Hitting formulas

Theorem 11. Exact/Max Differ Hitting-SAT admits a polynomial-time algorithm.

Proof. Consider an instance (Φ, d) of Exact Differ Hitting-SAT, where Φ is a hitting formula with m clauses (say C_1, \dots, C_m) on n variables. Let $\text{vars}(\Phi)$ denote the set of all n variables of Φ . For every $1 \leq i \leq m$, let $\text{vars}(C_i)$ denote the set of all variables that appear in the clause C_i . For every $1 \leq i, j \leq m$, let $\lambda(i, j)$ denote the number of variables $x \in \text{vars}(C_i) \cap \text{vars}(C_j)$ such that x appears as a positive literal in one clause, and as a negative literal in the other clause. Note that

$$\begin{aligned}
& |\{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } d \text{ variables, and both } \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ satisfy } \Phi\}| \\
&= |\{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } d \text{ variables}\}| \\
&\quad - |\{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } d \text{ variables, and } \sigma_1 \text{ falsifies } \Phi\}| \\
&\quad - |\{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } d \text{ variables, and } \sigma_2 \text{ falsifies } \Phi\}| \\
&\quad + |\{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ differ on } d \text{ variables, and both } \sigma_1 \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ falsify } \Phi\}| \\
&= 2^n \cdot \binom{n}{d} - |\{\sigma_1 \mid \sigma_1 \text{ falsifies } \Phi\}| \cdot \binom{n}{d} - |\{\sigma_2 \mid \sigma_2 \text{ falsifies } \Phi\}| \cdot \binom{n}{d} \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m \underbrace{|\{(\sigma_1, \sigma_2) \mid \sigma_1 \text{ falsifies } C_i, \text{ and } \sigma_2 \text{ falsifies } C_j\}|}_{\alpha(i, j)}
\end{aligned}$$

Since Φ has $\sum_{i=1}^m 2^{n-|\text{vars}(C_i)|}$ unsatisfying assignments, the above expression becomes

$$\left(2^n - 2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^m 2^{n-|\text{vars}(C_i)|}\right) \cdot \binom{n}{d} + \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^m \alpha(i, j).$$

Consider any $1 \leq i, j \leq m$. Let us derive an expression for $\alpha(i, j)$. That is, let us count the number of pairs (σ_1, σ_2) of assignments of Φ such that σ_1 and σ_2 differ on d variables, σ_1 falsifies C_i , and σ_2 falsifies C_j . Since σ_1 falsifies C_i , it must set every variable in $\text{vars}(C_i)$ such that its corresponding literal in the clause C_i is falsified. That is, for every $x \in \text{vars}(C_i)$, if x appears as a positive literal in C_i , then σ_1 must set x to 0; otherwise, it must set x to 1. Similarly, since σ_2 falsifies C_j , it must set every variable in $\text{vars}(C_j)$ such that its corresponding literal in the clause C_j is falsified.

There is just one choice for the truth values assigned to the variables in $\text{vars}(C_i) \cap \text{vars}(C_j)$ by σ_1 and σ_2 . Also, note that for every variable x in $\text{vars}(C_i) \cap \text{vars}(C_j)$, if x appears as a positive literal in one clause and as a negative literal in the other clause, then σ_1 and σ_2 differ on x ; otherwise, they overlap on x . So, overall, σ_1 and σ_2 differ on $\lambda(i, j)$ variables amongst the variables in $\text{vars}(C_i) \cap \text{vars}(C_j)$.

Next, we go over all possible choices for the numbers of variables on which σ_1 and σ_2 differ (say d_1, d_2 and d_3 many variables) amongst the variables in $\text{vars}(C_i) \setminus \text{vars}(C_j)$, $\text{vars}(C_j) \setminus \text{vars}(C_i)$ and $\text{vars}(\Phi) \setminus (\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j))$ respectively. Since σ_1 and σ_2 differ on d variables in total, we have $\lambda(i, j) + d_1 + d_2 + d_3 = d$.

There is just one choice for the truth values assigned to the variables in $\text{vars}(C_i) \setminus \text{vars}(C_j)$ by σ_1 , and there are $\binom{|\text{vars}(C_i) \setminus \text{vars}(C_j)|}{d_1}$ choices for the truth values assigned to the variables in $\text{vars}(C_i) \setminus \text{vars}(C_j)$ by σ_2 . Similarly, there is just one choice for the truth values assigned to the variables in $\text{vars}(C_j) \setminus \text{vars}(C_i)$ by σ_2 , and there are $\binom{|\text{vars}(C_j) \setminus \text{vars}(C_i)|}{d_2}$ choices for the truth values assigned to the variables in $\text{vars}(C_j) \setminus \text{vars}(C_i)$ by σ_1 .

There are $\binom{n - |\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j)|}{d_3}$ choices for the d_3 variables on which σ_1 and σ_2 differ amongst the variables in $\text{vars}(\Phi) \setminus (\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j))$. For each variable x amongst these d_3 variables, there are two ways in which σ_1 and σ_2 can assign truth values to x . That is, either i) σ_1 sets x to 0 and σ_2 sets x to 1, or ii) σ_1 sets x to 1 and σ_2 sets x to 0. For each variable x amongst the remaining $n - |\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j)| - d_3$ variables, there are again two ways in which σ_1 and σ_2 can assign truth values to x . That is, either i) both σ_1 and σ_2 set x to 1, or ii) both σ_1 and σ_2 set x to 0. So, overall, the number of ways in which σ_1 and σ_2 can assign truth values to the variables in $\text{vars}(\Phi) \setminus (\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j))$ is $\binom{n - |\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j)|}{d_3} \cdot 2^{d_3} \cdot 2^{n - |\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j)| - d_3}$.

Thus, we get the following expression for $\alpha(i, j)$:

$$2^{n - |\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j)|} \cdot \sum_{\substack{d_1, d_2, d_3 \geq 0: \\ d_1 + d_2 + d_3 = d - \lambda(i, j)}} \binom{|\text{vars}(C_i) \setminus \text{vars}(C_j)|}{d_1} \binom{|\text{vars}(C_j) \setminus \text{vars}(C_i)|}{d_2} \binom{n - |\text{vars}(C_i) \cup \text{vars}(C_j)|}{d_3}$$

Plugging this into the previously obtained equality, we get an expression to count the number of pairs (σ_1, σ_2) of satisfying assignments of Φ that differ on d variables. Note that this expression can be evaluated in polynomial-time. If the count so obtained is non-zero, we return YES; otherwise, we return NO. So, Exact Differ Hitting-SAT is polynomial-time solvable.

Note that (Φ, d) is a YES instance of Max Differ Hitting-SAT if and only if at least one of $(\Phi, d), (\Phi, d + 1), \dots, (\Phi, n)$ is a YES instance of Exact Differ Hitting-SAT. Thus, as Exact Differ Hitting-SAT is polynomial-time solvable, so is Max Differ Hitting-SAT. This proves Theorem 11. \square

Directions for Future Work. An immediate open question is to resolve the parameterized complexity of Exact/Max Differ 2-SAT in the parameter $n - d$ ¹⁰. The diverse variant of SAT can also be studied for i) other classes of formulas on which SAT is polynomial-time solvable, ii) more than two solutions, and iii) other notions of distance between assignments. Its parameterized complexity can be studied in structural parameters of graphs associated with the input Boolean formula; some examples include primal, dual, conflict, incidence and consensus graphs [42]. Also, while our polynomial-time algorithm for Hitting formulas counts the number of solution pairs, it is not clear whether it can also be used to output a solution pair¹¹.

¹⁰This question has been recently addressed by Gima et al. in [44].

¹¹This came up as a post-talk question from audience during ISAAC 2024.

Chapter 3

Modifying Graphs to Bound the Number of Distinct Eigenvalues

In the problems r -Eigenvalue Vertex Deletion (r -EVD), r -Eigenvalue Edge Addition (r -EEA), r -Eigenvalue Edge Deletion (r -EED) and r -Eigenvalue Edge Editing (r -EEE), we are given a graph G and a budget k as input, and the goal is to decide whether G can be turned into a graph whose adjacency matrix has $\leq r$ distinct eigenvalues by deleting $\leq k$ vertices, adding $\leq k$ edges, deleting $\leq k$ edges and editing $\leq k$ edges respectively. These problems are motivated by the following question posed by Meesum et al. in their work on graph modification to reduce rank of the adjacency matrix [64]:

“[...] what is complexity of the problem of reducing the number of distinct eigenvalues of a graph by deleting a few vertices or editing a few edges?”

It can be argued that all eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of a graph coincide if and only if the graph is edgeless. So, 1-EVD is same as Minimum Vertex Cover problem. We list our findings for $r \geq 2$ below.

- For any $d \geq 2$, 2-EVD is NP-hard on $3d$ -regular triangle-free graphs (Theorem 12).
- For any $d \geq 8$, 2-EVD is NP-hard on d -regular graphs (Theorem 13).
- 2-EVD admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(3^k)$ (Theorem 14).
- 2-EVD is polynomial-time solvable on trees and 2-regular graphs (Proposition 1).
- For any $r \geq 3$, r -EVD is NP-hard on bipartite graphs of maximum degree four (Theorem 15).
- For any $r \geq 3$, r -EVD is FPT in the combined parameter k and maximum degree $\Delta(G)$ (Theorem 16).
- 2-EEA is NP-hard on cluster graphs, 2-regular graphs and linear forests (Theorem 17).
- 2-EEA admits a kernel with $\mathcal{O}(k^2)$ vertices (Theorem 18).
- For any $r \geq 3$, r -EEA is NP-hard (Theorem 19).
- 2-EED admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(2^k)$ (Theorem 20).
- 2-EED is polynomial-time solvable on triangle-free graphs (Proposition 2).
- For any $r \geq 3$, r -EED is NP-hard (Theorem 21).
- 2-EEE is NP-hard (Theorem 22).

Related work. In 2016, Meesum et al. studied vertex deletion, edge deletion and edge editing variants of the rank reduction problem [64]. That is, given a graph G and budget k as input, the goal of these problems is to decide whether G can be turned into a graph whose adjacency matrix has rank $\leq r$ by deleting $\leq k$ vertices, deleting $\leq k$ edges and editing $\leq k$ edges respectively. They showed that i) all three variants are NP-hard, ii) vertex deletion variant admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(2^{\mathcal{O}(k \log r)})$ and a kernel on $(2(r+1)) \cdot (2(r+1))! \cdot (k+1)^{2r+2}$ vertices, and iii) edge editing variant admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(2^{\mathcal{O}(k \log r)})$ and a kernel on $\mathcal{O}((2^{\frac{r}{2}} + 2k) \cdot (k+1))$ vertices.

In 2024, Gaikwad et al. proved in a follow-up work that i) 2-EVD admits a kernel of size $\mathcal{O}(k^3)$ and an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(2^k)$, ii) 2-EEE admits a kernel of size $\mathcal{O}(k^2)$, iii) 2-EEA and 2-EED admit kernels of sizes $5k$ and $6k$ respectively, and iv) 2-EED admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(1.47^k)$ [40].

Preliminaries

The *adjacency matrix* A_G of a simple undirected graph G on n vertices is a 0 – 1 matrix of order $n \times n$. For any $1 \leq i, j \leq n$, the entry at i^{th} row and j^{th} column of A_G is 1 if and only if G contains an edge joining the vertices i and j . The *spectrum* of G refers to the multiset of eigenvalues of A_G , and it can be computed in polynomial time using results from [8] and [15]. A *principal submatrix* of a square matrix A is a matrix obtained by removing an equal number of rows and columns from A such that the indices of the removed rows match with the indices of the removed columns.

Lemma 2 ([45, 28]). *Let G be a graph. Then, its adjacency matrix A_G has at most two distinct eigenvalues if and only if G is a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques.*

Lemma 3 ([21], Proposition 1.3.3). *Let G be a connected graph with diameter d . Then, its adjacency matrix A_G has at least $d + 1$ distinct eigenvalues.*

Lemma 4 ([21], Corollary 2.5.2). **Cauchy interlacing.**

Let A be a symmetric matrix of size $n \times n$. Let B be a principal submatrix of A of size $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$. Then, the eigenvalues of B interlace the eigenvalues of A . That is,

$$\mu_1 \geq \sigma_1 \geq \mu_2 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \mu_3 \geq \dots \geq \mu_{n-2} \geq \sigma_{n-2} \geq \mu_{n-1} \geq \sigma_{n-1} \geq \mu_n,$$

where $\mu_1 \geq \mu_2 \geq \dots \geq \mu_n$ and $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_{n-1}$ denote the n eigenvalues of A and $n - 1$ eigenvalues of B respectively.

Lemma 5 ([21], Chapter 3, Exercise 1). *Let G be a graph such that the smallest eigenvalue of its adjacency matrix A_G is -1 . Then, G is a disjoint union of cliques.*

Spectra of graph classes such as complete graphs, paths and cycles are well-known [21].

Lemma 6 ([21], Chapter 1). *A complete graph on n vertices has eigenvalues -1 and $n-1$ (with multiplicities $n-1$ and 1 respectively). A path on n vertices has eigenvalues $2 \cos\left(\frac{\pi j}{n+1}\right) \Big|_{1 \leq j \leq n}$.*

We use the following as source problems in our reductions:

- Independent Set. Given a graph G and an integer k , decide whether G has a k -sized independent set. This problem is NP-hard on planar cubic triangle-free graphs [76].
- 3-Partition. Given a set $T = \{s_1, \dots, s_{3n}\}$ and a positive integer b , where s_i 's are integers such that $b/4 < s_i < b/2$ and $\sum_{i=1}^{3n} s_i = nb$, decide whether T can be partitioned into n triplets such that the elements of each triplet sum up to b . This problem is known to be strongly NP-hard, i.e., it is NP-hard even when s_i 's and b are specified in unary [43].
- Partition into Triangles. Given a graph G on n vertices, decide whether its vertex set can be partitioned into $n/3$ triplets such that each triplet induces a triangle. This problem is known to be NP-hard on graphs of clique number three [25].

r -Eigenvalue Vertex Deletion

Theorem 12. *For any $d \geq 2$, 2-EVD is NP-hard on $3d$ -regular triangle-free graphs.*

Figure 18: Adding edges in H corresponding to any edge e of G in Theorem 12.

Figure 19: This example illustrates construction of H from G in Theorem 12.

Proof. We describe a reduction from Independent Set on cubic triangle-free graphs. Consider an instance, say (G, k) , of Independent Set, where G is a cubic triangle-free graph on n vertices. Construct a graph, say H , as follows: For each vertex $v \in V(G)$, introduce two¹² copies of v , say $v^{(1)}$ and $v^{(2)}$. Also, for each edge $e \in E(G)$, say with endpoints u and v , make the i^{th} copy of u , i.e., $u^{(i)}$, adjacent to the j^{th} copy of v , i.e., $v^{(j)}$, for all $1 \leq i, j \leq 2$ (see Figure 18). That is, $V(H) = \{v^{(i)} \mid v \in V(G) \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq 2\}$ and $E(H) = \{\{u^{(i)}, v^{(j)}\} \mid \{u, v\} \in E(G) \text{ and } 1 \leq i, j \leq 2\}$. See Figure 19 for an example.

Note that for every vertex $v \in V(G)$, each of the two copies of v , i.e., $v^{(1)}$ and $v^{(2)}$, has six neighbours in H , namely the two copies of each of the three neighbours of v in G . So, H is a 6-regular graph. Also, as G is a triangle-free graph, so is H . Let us show that G has an independent set of size k if and only if $(H, 2(n - k))$ is a YES instance of 2-EVD.

Forward direction. Suppose that G has a k -sized independent set, say I . Let $I' \subseteq V(H)$ denote the set that consists of both copies of each vertex in I . That is, $I' = \{v^{(i)} \mid v \in I \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq 2\}$. Note that I' is an independent set in H . All eigenvalues of $H[I']$'s adjacency matrix are 0. So, as $|V(H) \setminus I'| = 2(n - k)$, $(H, 2(n - k))$ is a YES instance of 2-EVD.

Reverse direction. Suppose that $(H, 2(n - k))$ is a YES instance of 2-EVD. That is, there exists $S \subseteq V(H)$ of size $\leq 2(n - k)$ such that the adjacency matrix of $H \setminus S$ has at most two distinct eigenvalues. Using Lemma 2, $H \setminus S$ is a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques, say

¹²The description here is for $d = 2$. In general, for any $d \geq 2$, introduce d copies of every vertex.

Figure 20: This figure is with reference to Case 1 in the proof of Theorem 12.

C_1, \dots, C_t , each of size s . We have $|V(H) \setminus S| = s \cdot t \geq 2k$. As H has no triangles, $s \leq 2$.

Case 1. $s = 1$.

For each $1 \leq i \leq t$, let $u_i^{(\alpha_i)}$ denote the vertex of C_i . That is, the clique C_i consists of the α_i^{th} copy of the vertex u_i of G . Note that for any $1 \leq i < j \leq t$, u_i is not adjacent to u_j in G ; otherwise, there is an edge joining the cliques C_i and C_j , namely $\{u_i^{(\alpha_i)}, u_j^{(\alpha_j)}\}$ (Figure 20).

Case 2. $s = 2$.

For each $1 \leq i \leq t$, let $u_i^{(\alpha_i)}$ and $v_i^{(\beta_i)}$ denote the two vertices of C_i . That is, the clique C_i consists of the α_i^{th} copy of the vertex u_i and the β_i^{th} copy of the vertex v_i . Consider any $1 \leq i < j \leq t$. Note that u_i is not adjacent to u_j in G ; otherwise, there's an edge joining the cliques C_i and C_j , namely $\{u_i^{(\alpha_i)}, u_j^{(\alpha_j)}\}$ (see Figure 21). Next, let us show that u_i is distinct from u_j . For the sake of contradiction, assume that u_i and u_j are the same vertex, say u , of G . Without loss of generality, C_i contains the first copy of u , i.e., $u^{(1)}$, and C_j contains the second copy of u , i.e., $u^{(2)}$. Observe that $u^{(1)}$ and $u^{(2)}$ are twins in H . Thus, as $u^{(1)}$ is adjacent to $v_i^{(\beta_i)}$, so is $u^{(2)}$. Likewise, as $u^{(2)}$ is adjacent to $v_j^{(\beta_j)}$, so is $u^{(1)}$. So, there are two edges joining the cliques C_i and C_j , namely $\{u^{(1)}, v_j^{(\beta_j)}\}$ and $\{u^{(2)}, v_i^{(\beta_i)}\}$ (see Figure 21), a contradiction. Therefore, in both Case 1 and Case 2, u_1, \dots, u_t are $t \geq k$ distinct vertices that form an independent set in G . This proves Theorem 12. \square

Theorem 13. For any $d \geq 8$, 2-EVD is NP-hard on d -regular graphs.

Proof. We describe a reduction from Independent Set on planar cubic triangle free graphs. Consider an instance, say (G, k) , of Independent Set, where G is a planar cubic triangle-free graph on n vertices. Construct a graph, say H , as follows: For each vertex $v \in V(G)$, introduce six¹³ copies of v , say $v^{(1)}, \dots, v^{(6)}$, and make them pairwise adjacent to each other. Also, for each edge $e \in E(G)$, say with endpoints u and v , make the i^{th} copy of u , i.e., $u^{(i)}$, adjacent to the i^{th} copy of v , i.e., $v^{(i)}$, for all $1 \leq i \leq 6$. That is, $V(H) = \{v^{(i)} \mid v \in V(G) \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq 6\}$, and $E(H) = \left\{ \{v^{(i)}, v^{(j)}\} \mid v \in V(G) \text{ and } 1 \leq i < j \leq 6 \right\} \uplus \left\{ \{u^{(i)}, v^{(i)}\} \mid \{u, v\} \in E(G) \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq 6 \right\}$. See Figure 22 for an example.

Note that for each vertex $v \in V(G)$ and each $1 \leq i \leq 6$, the i^{th} copy of v , i.e., $v^{(i)}$, has eight neighbours in H , namely the remaining five copies of v , and the i^{th} copies of the three neighbours of v in G . So, H is an 8-regular graph. Let us show that G has an independent set of size k if and only if $(H, 6(n - k))$ is a YES instance of 2-EVD.

¹³The description here is for $d = 8$. In general, for any $d \geq 8$, introduce $d - 2$ copies of every vertex.

Figure 21: These figures are with reference to Case 2 in the proof of Theorem 12.

Figure 22: This example illustrates construction of H from G in Theorem 13.

Figure 23: This figure is with reference to forward direction in proof of Theorem 13.

Forward direction. Suppose that G has a k -sized independent set, say I . Let v_1, \dots, v_k denote the vertices of I . Let $I' \subseteq V(H)$ denote the set that consists of all six copies of each of v_1, \dots, v_k . That is, $I' = \{v_i^{(j)} \mid 1 \leq i \leq k \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq 6\}$. $H[I']$ is a disjoint union of k cliques, each of size 6 (Figure 23), namely the clique on six copies of v_1 (i.e., $v_1^{(1)}, \dots, v_1^{(6)}$), the clique on six copies of v_2 (i.e., $v_2^{(1)}, \dots, v_2^{(6)}$), \dots , the clique on six copies of v_k (i.e., $v_k^{(1)}, \dots, v_k^{(6)}$). The adjacency matrix of each of these k cliques has two distinct eigenvalues, i.e., -1 and 5 . So, as $|V(H) \setminus I'| = 6(n - k)$, $(H, 6(n - k))$ is a YES instance of 2-EVD.

Reverse direction. Suppose that $(H, 6(n - k))$ is a YES instance of 2-EVD. That is, there exists $S \subseteq V(H)$ of size $\leq 6(n - k)$ such that the adjacency matrix of $H \setminus S$ has at most two distinct eigenvalues. Using Lemma 2, $H \setminus S$ is a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques, say C_1, \dots, C_t , each of size s . We have $|V(H) \setminus S| = s \cdot t \geq 6k$. We show that G has a k -sized independent set. It is known that any planar cubic triangle-free graph on n vertices has an independent set of size $\geq \frac{3n}{8}$ [12]. So, if $k \leq \frac{3n}{8}$, we are done. Next, assume $k > \frac{3n}{8}$. For any vertex $v \in V(G)$ and any $1 \leq i < j \leq t$, it is not possible that each of C_i and C_j contains a copy of v ; otherwise, there is an edge joining the cliques C_i and C_j in H . That is, each vertex of G contributes its copy(ies) to at most one of the t cliques C_1, \dots, C_t . So, we get $t \leq n$. Now, we have $s \geq \lceil \frac{6k}{t} \rceil \geq \lceil \frac{6(\frac{3n}{8})}{n} \rceil = 3$.

For each $1 \leq i \leq 6$, let X_i denote the set of those vertices in $H \setminus S$ that are the i^{th} copy of some vertex in G . We have $V(H) \setminus S = X_1 \uplus \dots \uplus X_6$. Now, as $|V(H) \setminus S| \geq 6k$, by pigeonhole principle, there exists $1 \leq p \leq 6$ such that X_p contains at least k vertices, say $v_1^{(p)}, \dots, v_k^{(p)}$. It suffices to show that v_1, \dots, v_k form an independent set in G . For the sake of contradiction, assume that there exist $1 \leq i < j \leq k$ such that v_i and v_j are adjacent to each other in G . Then, $v_i^{(p)}$ and $v_j^{(p)}$ are adjacent to each other in H . So, $v_i^{(p)}$ and $v_j^{(p)}$ belong to the same clique, say C_ℓ , amongst the t cliques C_1, \dots, C_t . As $s \geq 3$, the clique C_ℓ has at least one vertex, say $u^{(q)}$, other than $v_i^{(p)}$ and $v_j^{(p)}$. These three vertices, i.e., $u^{(q)}$, $v_i^{(p)}$, $v_j^{(p)}$, are pairwise adjacent to each other in H . If $p = q$, then G has a triangle on the vertices u, v_i, v_j , which is not possible as G is a triangle-free graph. So, $p \neq q$. Note that at least one of v_i and v_j is distinct from u . If $v_i \neq u$, then the edge $\{v_i^{(p)}, u^{(q)}\}$ (shown in blue in Figure 24) is not present in H , a contradiction. Similarly, if $v_j \neq u$, then the edge $\{v_j^{(p)}, u^{(q)}\}$ (shown in pink in Figure 24) is not present in H , a contradiction. This proves Theorem 13. \square

Theorem 14. 2-EVD admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(3^k)$.

Proof. We describe a recursive branching algorithm. Consider an instance, say (G, k) , of

Figure 24: This figure is with reference to reverse direction in proof of Theorem 13.

2-EVD. By Lemma 2, our goal is to decide whether we can delete $\leq k$ vertices from G to get a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques. First, we check if G has an induced path on three vertices. This takes polynomial time.

Case 1. G has no induced path on three vertices.

Since G has no induced path on three vertices, it is a disjoint union of cliques (see [1]), say C_1, \dots, C_t , of sizes s_1, \dots, s_t respectively. We know that deleting the vertices of any solution results in a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques (say, of size x). Observe that for each $1 \leq i \leq t$,

- If $s_i \geq x$, then $s_i - x$ vertices of the clique C_i are deleted, leaving behind x of its vertices.
- If $s_i < x$, then the entire clique C_i , i.e., all its s_i vertices, are deleted.

So, the overall solution size, i.e., total number of deleted vertices, is

$$\sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq t: \\ s_i \geq x}} (s_i - x) + \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq t: \\ s_i < x}} s_i = \sum_{i=1}^t s_i - x \cdot \mu(x)$$

where $\mu(x)$ denotes the number of s_i 's amongst s_1, \dots, s_t such that $s_i \geq x$.

Thus, the size of any minimum-sized solution is

$$\sum_{i=1}^t s_i - \max_{1 \leq j \leq t} (s_j \cdot \mu(s_j))$$

If this size is $\leq k$, we return YES; otherwise, we return NO. This takes polynomial time.

Case 2. G has an induced path on three vertices, say $a - b - c$.

Note that any solution must pick at least one of its three vertices, i.e., a, b, c . So, if $k = 0$, we return NO; otherwise, we guess a vertex that is picked into solution. That is, we branch as follows: In the first (resp. second and third) branch, we include the vertex a (resp. b and c) into solution, delete it from G , and reduce the parameter k by 1. It takes polynomial time to create the subproblems $(G \setminus \{a\}, k - 1)$, $(G \setminus \{b\}, k - 1)$ and $(G \setminus \{c\}, k - 1)$. Next, we run our algorithm on these three instances. If at least one of these three recursive calls returns YES, so do we; otherwise, we return NO.

The depth of our search tree is at most k . Also, each of its internal nodes has three children. Therefore, it has at most $\mathcal{O}(3^k)$ nodes. Thus, as we spend polynomial time at each node, the overall running time is at most $\mathcal{O}^*(3^k)$. This proves Theorem 14. \square

Proposition 1. *2-EVD is polynomial-time solvable on trees and 2-regular graphs.*

Proof. Consider an instance, say (T, k) , of 2-EVD, where T is a tree, say on n vertices. Note that our goal is to decide if at least one of the following holds true:

- There exists $S \subseteq V(T)$ of size $\leq k$ such that $T \setminus S$ is a disjoint union of 1-sized cliques. That is, T has a vertex cover of size $\leq k$.
- There exists $S \subseteq V(T)$ of size $\leq k$ such that $T \setminus S$ is a disjoint union of 2-sized cliques. That is, T has an induced matching of size $\geq \frac{n-k}{2}$.

It is known that there is a polynomial time algorithm to find a minimum vertex cover [5] and a maximum induced matching [85] when the input graph is a tree. So, 2-EVD is polynomial-time solvable on trees. Next, let us consider the case when input graph G is 2-regular. That is, G is a disjoint union of cycles, say C_1, \dots, C_t . Note that

- The minimum number of vertex deletions needed to get a disjoint union of three-sized cliques is

$$k_1 := \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq t: \\ C_i \text{ is not a triangle}}} \ell(C_i).$$

- The minimum number of vertex deletions needed to get a disjoint union of two-sized cliques is

$$k_2 := \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq t: \\ \ell(C_i) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}}} \frac{\ell(C_i)}{3} + \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq t: \\ \ell(C_i) \equiv 1 \pmod{3}}} \frac{\ell(C_i) + 2}{3} + \sum_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq t: \\ \ell(C_i) \equiv 2 \pmod{3}}} \frac{\ell(C_i) + 4}{3}.$$

where for every $1 \leq i \leq t$, $\ell(C_i)$ denotes the length of the cycle C_i . If $\min(k_1, k_2) \leq k$, we return YES; otherwise, we return NO. Thus, 2-EVD is polynomial-time solvable on 2-regular graphs. This proves Proposition 1. \square

Theorem 15. *For every $r \geq 3$, r -EVD is NP-hard on bipartite graphs of maximum degree 4.*

Proof. We describe a reduction from Vertex Cover on Cubic graphs. Consider an instance, say (G, k) , of Vertex Cover, where G is a cubic graph. Let us construct a graph, say H , as follows: For each vertex $v \in V(G)$, let us attach a path on $\ell := \lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor$ vertices (denoted by \star_v 's) to v (see Figure 25). Also, for each edge $e \in E(G)$, say with endpoints u and v , let us subdivide e into two edges using a vertex (denoted by \triangle_e), and then attach a path on $\ell - 1$ vertices (denoted by \square_e 's) to \triangle_e (see Figure 26). See Figure 29 for an example.

Figure 25: Attaching a path of $\ell - 1$ vertices to every vertex v in Theorem 15.

Figure 26: Subdividing edge e and attaching path of $\ell - 1$ vertices in Theorem 15.

Observe that every cycle in H is obtained from some cycle in G by subdividing each of its edges into two edges. So, all cycles in H have even length and thus, H is a bipartite graph. We show that G has a vertex cover of size $\leq k$ if and only if (H, k) is a YES instance of r -EVD.

Forward direction. Suppose that G has a vertex cover, say S , of size $\leq k$. Observe that the graph $H \setminus S$ consists of three types of components (explained in Figure 27, and see example in Figure 30). Each Type 1 or Type 2 component of $H \setminus S$ is a path on ℓ vertices; the ℓ eigenvalues of its adjacency matrix are $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_\ell$, where $\lambda_j := 2 \cos\left(\frac{\pi j}{\ell+1}\right)$ for each $1 \leq j \leq \ell$. Next, consider any Type 3 component, say C , of $H \setminus S$. Let v denote the central vertex of C . Note that $C \setminus \{v\}$ is a disjoint union of four paths, each on ℓ vertices. So, the adjacency matrix of $C \setminus \{v\}$, i.e., $A_{C \setminus \{v\}}$, has eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_\ell$, each with multiplicity 4. Also, using Cauchy interlacing (Lemma 4), we know that the eigenvalues of $A_{C \setminus \{v\}}$ interlace the eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of C , i.e., A_C . Therefore, each of $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_\ell$ is an eigenvalue of A_C with multiplicity at least 3 (explained in Figure 28). Now, apart from $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_\ell$, there are at most $(4\ell + 1) - 3\ell = \ell + 1$ eigenvalues of A_C . So, the adjacency matrix of $H \setminus S$ has at most $\ell + (\ell + 1) = 2\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 1 \leq r$ distinct eigenvalues. Thus, (H, k) is a YES instance of r -EVD.

Figure 27: Three types of components of $H \setminus S$ in forward direction in Theorem 15.

Figure 28: Eigenvalues of $A_{C \setminus \{v\}}$ and A_C in forward direction in Theorem 15.

Figure 31 lists eigenvalues of adjacency matrices of Type 1, 2, 3 components when $\ell = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

Figure 29: This example illustrates the construction of graph H from graph G (when $\ell = 2$) in the reduction described in the proof of Theorem 15.

Figure 30: Three types of components in the graph $H \setminus S$ obtained by removing vertex cover $S = \{b, c, d, e\}$ of G from H for the example shown in Figure 29. This figure is with reference to forward direction in the proof of Theorem 15.

ℓ	The ℓ eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of a Type 1/2 component	The $4\ell + 1$ eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of a Type 3 component
1	0	2, 0, 0, 0, -2
2	1, -1	$\sqrt{5}, 1, 1, 1, 0, -1, -1, -1, -\sqrt{5}$
3	$\sqrt{2}, 0, -\sqrt{2}$	$3 + \sqrt{5}, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2}, 3 - \sqrt{5}, 0, 0, 0, -(3 - \sqrt{5}), -\sqrt{2}, -\sqrt{2}, -\sqrt{2}, -(3 + \sqrt{5})$
4	$\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1)$	$\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{13} + 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{13} - 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), \frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), 0, -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} - 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{13} - 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{13} + 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{5} + 1), -\frac{1}{2}(\sqrt{13} + 1)$

Figure 31: This table lists the eigenvalues of adjacency matrices of Type 1, 2, 3 components when $\ell = 1, 2, 3, 4$ in Theorem 15.

Reverse direction. Suppose that (H, k) is a YES instance of r -EVD. That is, there exists $S \subseteq V(H)$ of size $\leq k$ such that the adjacency matrix of $H \setminus S$ has at most r distinct eigenvalues. Let us construct a set $S' \subseteq V(G)$ as follows: For each vertex $v \in V(G)$ such that $v \in S$ or at least one of the ℓ \star_v 's belongs to S , add v to S' . Also, for each edge $e \in E(G)$ such that $\Delta_e \in S$, arbitrarily pick an endpoint of e and add it to S' . Note that $|S'| \leq k$. Now, it suffices to show that S' is a vertex cover of G .

For the sake of contradiction, assume that there exists an edge, say e , of G such that neither of its endpoints, say u and v , belongs to S' . Then, none of u, v, Δ_e , the ℓ \star_u 's and the ℓ \star_v 's belong to S . Let C denote the component of $H \setminus S$ that contains all these $2\ell + 3$ vertices. Consider the following two vertices: i) the \star_u farthest from u , and ii) the \star_v farthest from v . Note that in C , the shortest path joining these two vertices has $2\ell + 2$ edges (see Figure 32). So, the diameter of C is at least $2\ell + 2$. Thus, using Lemma 3, the adjacency matrix of C (and so, $H \setminus S$) has at least $(2\ell + 2) + 1 = 2\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 3 > r$ distinct eigenvalues, a contradiction. This proves Theorem 15. \square

Figure 32: This figure is with reference to reverse direction in Theorem 15.

Theorem 16. For every $r \geq 3$, r -EVD can be solved in time $\mathcal{O}^*((r+1)^{2k} \cdot 2^{k^2} \cdot (\Delta(G))^{rk})$, where $\Delta(G)$ denotes the maximum degree of G .

Proof. Consider an instance (G, k) of r -EVD. First, we prove the following claim to explain the effect of removing one vertex on the number of distinct eigenvalues of adjacency matrix:

Claim 1. Let $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2 > \dots > \lambda_t$ denote the distinct eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of a graph G . Then, for any vertex $v \in V(G)$, the adjacency matrix of $G \setminus \{v\}$ has $\geq \lfloor \frac{t}{2} \rfloor$ distinct eigenvalues.

Proof of Claim 1. Using Cauchy interlacing (Lemma 4), we know that the eigenvalues of $A_{G \setminus \{v\}}$ interlace the eigenvalues of A_G . In the interlaced sequence, consider those eigenvalues of $A_{G \setminus \{v\}}$ that are sandwiched between last appearance of λ_1 and first appearance of λ_2 , last appearance of λ_3 and first appearance of λ_4 , last appearance of λ_5 and first appearance of λ_6 , and so on (marked in red in Figure 33). Due to the interlacing inequalities, the first red eigenvalue is $\geq \lambda_2$, and the second red eigenvalue is $\leq \lambda_3$. So, as $\lambda_2 > \lambda_3$, the first red eigenvalue is strictly greater than the second red eigenvalue. Similarly, the second red eigenvalue is $\geq \lambda_4$, and the third red eigenvalue is $\leq \lambda_5$. So, as $\lambda_4 > \lambda_5$, the second red eigenvalue is strictly greater than the third red eigenvalue. This continues in a similar manner. Thus, these $\lfloor \frac{t}{2} \rfloor$ red eigenvalues of $A_{G \setminus \{v\}}$ must be distinct. This proves Claim 1.

Suppose that A_G has $> (r+1) \cdot 2^k$ distinct eigenvalues. Then, we repeatedly apply Claim 1 to show that (G, k) is a NO instance of r -EVD. For the sake of contradiction, assume that there exists $S \subseteq V(G)$ of size $\leq k$ such that $A_{G \setminus S}$ has $\leq r$ distinct eigenvalues. Let $v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{|S|}$ denote the vertices of S . Using Claim 1 for graph G and vertex v_1 , we get $A_{G \setminus \{v_1\}}$ has $\geq (r+1) \cdot 2^{k-1}$ distinct eigenvalues. Next, using Claim 1 for graph $G \setminus \{v_1\}$ and

$$\begin{array}{cccccccccccccccc}
\lambda_1 & \geq & \dots & \geq & \lambda_1 & \geq & \text{●} & \geq & \lambda_2 & \geq & \dots & \geq & \lambda_2 & \geq & \text{○} & \geq & \lambda_3 & \geq & \dots & \geq & \lambda_3 & \geq & \text{●} \\
& \text{IV} \\
\dots & \lambda_6 & \leq & \dots & \leq & \lambda_6 & \leq & \text{●} & \leq & \lambda_5 & \leq & \dots & \leq & \lambda_5 & \leq & \text{○} & \leq & \lambda_4 & \leq & \dots & \leq & \lambda_4
\end{array}$$

Figure 33: This figure is with reference to proof of Claim 1 in Theorem 16.

vertex v_2 , we get that $A_{G \setminus \{v_1, v_2\}}$ has $\geq (r+1) \cdot 2^{k-2}$ distinct eigenvalues. Continuing this in a similar manner, we get that $A_{G \setminus \{v_1, \dots, v_S\}}$ has $\geq (r+1) \cdot 2^{k-|S|} > r$ distinct eigenvalues, a contradiction. Thus, if A_G has $> (r+1) \cdot 2^k$ distinct eigenvalues, we return NO.

Suppose that $\text{diameter}(G) \geq r$. That is, G has a shortest path P containing r edges. Note that if a solution picks none of the $r+1$ vertices of P , then these vertices would survive together in a component after solution's removal; this component would have diameter $\geq r$ and so, its adjacency matrix would have $\geq r+1$ distinct eigenvalues (using Lemma 3). Thus, a solution must pick at least one of the $r+1$ vertices of P . We guess which of these $r+1$ vertices is picked into solution. In the corresponding branching tree, every node has $r+1$ children, and the budget k drops by 1 along each branch. So, there are $\mathcal{O}((r+1)^k)$ leaf nodes in this tree.

Consider any leaf node, say (H, k') . Note that $\text{diameter}(H) \leq r-1$. Also, if the adjacency matrix of H has $\leq r$ or $> (r+1) \cdot 2^{k'}$ distinct eigenvalues, then (H, k') is a YES instance and NO instance of r -EVD respectively. Next, assume that it has $\geq r+1$ and $\leq (r+1) \cdot 2^{k'}$ distinct eigenvalues. At least one of these eigenvalues must be such that it does not survive as an eigenvalue of the adjacency matrix of the graph obtained by removing solution. So, we guess such an eigenvalue, say λ . There are $\leq (r+1) \cdot 2^{k'}$ such choices. Next, we arbitrarily fix a component C of H such that its adjacency matrix has λ as an eigenvalue. Note that solution must pick at least one vertex of C ; otherwise, C would survive as is after removing solution and so, the eigenvalue λ would not vanish. So, we guess a vertex of C that is picked into solution. Also, as $\text{diameter}(C) \leq r-1$, there are $\leq (\Delta(G))^r$ such choices (i.e., number of vertices in C). The leaf node (H, k') is processed in time $\mathcal{O}^*\left(\left((r+1) \cdot 2^{k'} \cdot (\Delta(G))^r\right)^{k'}\right)$. The overall running time is $\mathcal{O}^*\left((r+1)^k \cdot \left(\left((r+1) \cdot 2^k \cdot (\Delta(G))^r\right)^k\right)\right)$. This proves Theorem 16. \square

r -Eigenvalue Edge Addition

Theorem 17. *2-EEA is NP-hard on cluster graphs, 2-regular graphs and linear forests¹⁴.*

Proof. We describe a reduction from 3-Partition. Consider an instance (T, b) of 3-Partition, where $T = \{s_1, \dots, s_{3n}\}$ such that $s_i \in (b/4, b/2)$ for all $1 \leq i \leq 3n$ and $\sum_{i=1}^{3n} s_i = nb$. Construct a cluster graph G as follows: For every $1 \leq i \leq 3n$, introduce a clique C_i of size s_i . Also, add $M := 3nb$ cliques, each of size b ; we refer to them as *dummy cliques*. The graph G is disjoint union of $3n + M$ cliques, namely C_1, \dots, C_{3n} and M dummy cliques. We show that (T, b) is a YES instance of 3-Partition if and only if (G, nb^2) is a YES instance of 2-EEA.

Forward direction. Suppose that (T, b) is a YES instance of 3-Partition. Then, there exists a partition of T into n triplets, say $T = T_1 \uplus \dots \uplus T_n$, such that for every $1 \leq i \leq n$, the elements of T_i add up to b . That is, $s_{x_i} + s_{y_i} + s_{z_i} = b$, where $s_{x_i}, s_{y_i}, s_{z_i}$ denote the three elements of T_i . For every $1 \leq i \leq n$, merge the three cliques $C_{x_i}, C_{y_i}, C_{z_i}$ into one clique, say

¹⁴A *linear forest* is a disjoint union of path graphs.

D_i , as follows: i) Make every vertex of C_{x_i} adjacent to every vertex of C_{y_i} . ii) Make every vertex of C_{x_i} adjacent to every vertex of C_{z_i} . iii) Make every vertex of C_{y_i} adjacent to every vertex of C_{z_i} . See Figure 34 for an illustration. The number of edges so added to G is

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (s_{x_i} \cdot s_{y_i} + s_{x_i} \cdot s_{z_i} + s_{y_i} \cdot s_{z_i}) < \sum_{i=1}^n \left(3 \cdot \frac{b}{2} \cdot \frac{b}{2} \right) < nb^2$$

For each $1 \leq i \leq n$, the clique D_i has size $s_{x_i} + s_{y_i} + s_{z_i} = b$. The resulting graph, say H , is the disjoint union of $n + M$ cliques, each of size b , namely D_1, \dots, D_n and the M dummy cliques. The adjacency matrix of H has two distinct eigenvalues, i.e., -1 and $b - 1$. Thus, (G, nb^2) is a YES instance of 2-EEA.

Figure 34: An example illustrating merger of the cliques $C_{x_i}, C_{y_i}, C_{z_i}$, when $s_{x_i} = s_{y_i} = s_{z_i} = 4$. This figure is with reference to forward direction in Theorem 17.

Reverse direction. Suppose that (G, nb^2) is a YES instance of 2-EEA. That is, there exists $S \subseteq \binom{V(G)}{2} \setminus E(G)$ of size $\leq nb^2$ such that adding the edges of S to G results in a graph, say H , whose adjacency matrix has at most two distinct eigenvalues. Using Lemma 2, the graph H is a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques. Observe that each clique of H is formed by merging some of the $3n + M$ cliques of G , namely C_1, \dots, C_{3n} and M b -sized dummy cliques.

First, we show that no dummy clique participates in a merger. That is, in H , each of the M b -sized dummy cliques of G remains as it is. For the sake of contradiction, assume that there exists a dummy clique that merges with some other clique(s) of G to form a bigger (i.e., of size $> b$) clique of H . Then, as all cliques of H have the same size, none of the other $M - 1$

b -sized dummy cliques of G can remain as it is. Now, as each of the M b -sized dummy cliques participates in some merger, it is incident to $\geq b$ edges of S . Also, every edge of S is incident to at most two dummy cliques. Therefore, we get $|S| \geq \frac{Mb}{2} > nb^2$, a contradiction.

Let D_1, \dots, D_t denote the equal-sized cliques of H other than the M dummy cliques. Note that their common size is the same as that of a dummy clique, i.e., b . Consider any $1 \leq i \leq t$. The clique D_i is formed by merging some (say p_i) of the $3n$ cliques C_1, \dots, C_{3n} . Each of these p_i cliques has size $> \frac{b}{4}$ and $< \frac{b}{2}$. Also, their sizes add up to the size of the clique D_i , i.e., b . Therefore, we have $p_i \cdot \frac{b}{4} < b < p_i \cdot \frac{b}{2}$. So, we get $p_i = 3$. Hence, each of the t cliques D_1, \dots, D_t is obtained by merging three of the $3n$ cliques C_1, \dots, C_{3n} . We have $t = n$.

Consider any $1 \leq i \leq n$. Let $C_{x_i}, C_{y_i}, C_{z_i}$ denote the three cliques amongst C_1, \dots, C_{3n} whose merger forms the clique D_i . Let T_i denote the triplet that consists of $s_{x_i}, s_{y_i}, s_{z_i}$. As the sizes of the cliques $C_{x_i}, C_{y_i}, C_{z_i}$ add up to the size of the clique D_i , we have $s_{x_i} + s_{y_i} + s_{z_i} = b$. That is, the elements of the triplet T_i add up to b . Thus, as $T = T_1 \uplus \dots \uplus T_n$, it follows that (T, b) is a YES instance of 3-Partition.

In the reduction above, instead of adding cliques, we could add cycles (resp. paths), and adjust the budget to account for the missing edges, thereby showing NP-hardness of 2-EEA on 2-regular graphs (resp. linear forests) as well. More precisely,

- For showing NP-hardness on 2-regular graphs:
For every $1 \leq i \leq 3n$, introduce a cycle C_i on s_i vertices. Add M dummy cycles, each on b vertices. Set the budget to be $nb^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{3n} \binom{s_i}{2} + M \cdot \binom{b}{2}$. The first term is same as the old budget, the second term accounts for missing edges in the cycles C_i 's, and the third term accounts for missing edges in the dummy cycles.
- For showing NP-hardness on linear forests:
For every $1 \leq i \leq 3n$, introduce a path P_i on s_i vertices. Add M dummy paths, each on b vertices. Set the budget to be $nb^2 + \sum_{i=1}^{3n} (s_i - 1) + M \cdot (b - 1)$. The first term is same as the old budget, the second term accounts for missing edges in the paths P_i 's, and the third term accounts for missing edges in the dummy paths.

This proves Theorem 17. □

Theorem 18. *2-EEA admits a kernel with $\mathcal{O}(k^2)$ vertices.*

Proof. Consider an instance, say (G, k) , of 2-EEA. Due to Lemma 2, this problem amounts to deciding whether we can add $\leq k$ edges to G to get a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques. We apply the following reduction rules (in the specified order):

Reduction rule 1: Suppose that there is a component, say C , of G , that is not a clique. Then, add the missing $\binom{|V(C)|}{2} - |E(C)|$ edges to turn C into a clique, and reduce the budget k by $\binom{|V(C)|}{2} - |E(C)|$. After exhaustively applying Reduction rule 1, G becomes a disjoint union of cliques; say, it consists of n_1 cliques of size x_1 , n_2 cliques of size x_2 , \dots , n_t cliques of size x_t , where $x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_t$.

Reduction rule 2: If $k < 0$, then return NO. If $k \geq 0$ and $t = 1$, then return YES. If $k = 0$ and $t \geq 2$, then return NO. After applying Reduction rule 2, we have $k \geq 1$ and $t \geq 2$.

Reduction rule 3: If there exists $1 \leq i \leq t - 1$ such that $n_i \cdot x_i > 2k$, then return NO.

Safeness of Reduction rule 3: Suppose that (G, k) is a YES instance. Then, there exists $S \subseteq \binom{V(G)}{2} \setminus E(G)$ of size $\leq k$ such that adding the edges of S to G results in a disjoint

union of equal-sized (say, of size x) cliques. Observe that each of these x -sized cliques is obtained by merging some cliques of G . Note that x is at least the size of largest clique in G . That is, $x \geq x_t$. Also, each of the smaller cliques of G , i.e., those of sizes x_1, \dots, x_{t-1} , must participate in some merger. Consider any $1 \leq i \leq t-1$. Each of the n_i cliques of size x_i is incident to $\geq x_i$ edges of S , for it must participate in some merger. Also, any edge of S is incident to at most two of these n_i cliques. Therefore, $|S| \geq \frac{n_i \cdot x_i}{2}$. So, as $|S| \leq k$, we get $n_i \cdot x_i \leq 2k$. Thus, Reduction rule 3 is safe.

After applying Reduction rule 3, $n_i \cdot x_i \leq 2k$ for all $1 \leq i \leq t-1$. Also, as x_1, \dots, x_{t-1} are $t-1$ distinct integers in the interval $[1, 2k]$, we have $t-1 \leq 2k$.

Reduction rule 4: Suppose that $n_t \cdot x_t > 2k$. Then, remove all but $\frac{2k+1}{x_t}$ cliques of size x_t from G .

Safeness of Reduction rule 4: If $n_t \cdot x_t > 2k$, then in any solution, none of the n_t cliques of size x_t participate in a merger. That is, each of them remains as is after the edge additions, and each merger (involving the remaining cliques, i.e., those of sizes x_1, \dots, x_{t-1}) results in an x_t -sized clique. This is because if any clique of size x_t gets to participate in a merger, then each of the remaining $n_t - 1$ cliques of size x_t must also participate in some merger (because all cliques have the same size after the edge additions), thereby needing $\geq \frac{n_t \cdot x_t}{2} > k$ edge additions.

Also, we have $n_t \cdot x_t > 2k$ before, as well as after, applying Reduction rule 4. Therefore, it follows that any solution before applying this rule remains a solution after applying this rule, and vice versa. Thus, Reduction rule 4 is safe.

If Reduction rule 4 is not invoked, then $n_t \cdot x_t \leq 2k$; otherwise, after applying Reduction rule 4, we get $n_t \cdot x_t = 2k + 1$. Finally, the number of vertices in G is at most $n_1 \cdot x_1 + \dots + n_{t-1} \cdot x_{t-1} + n_t \cdot x_t \leq (t-1) \cdot 2k + (2k + 1) \leq 4k^2 + 2k + 1$. This proves Theorem 18. \square

Theorem 19. For every $r \geq 3$, r -EEA is NP-hard.

Proof. We describe a reduction from 3-Partition. Consider an instance, say (T, b) , of 3-Partition, where $T = \{s_1, \dots, s_{3n}\}$. Construct a graph, say G , as follows: For every $1 \leq i \leq 3n$, introduce a clique, say C_i , of size s_i . Add $2nb^2 + 1$ cliques, each of size b . Also, for every $0 \leq i \leq r-3$, add $2nb^2 + 1$ cliques, each of size $L + i$, where $L := 6nb^3$. We show that (T, b) is a YES instance of 3-Partition if and only if (G, nb^2) is a YES instance of r -EEA.

Forward direction. Suppose that (T, b) is a YES instance of 3-Partition. Then, as described in the proof of Theorem 17, we add $\leq nb^2$ edges to merge the cliques C_1, \dots, C_{3n} using the 3-Partition solution. The resulting graph, say H , is the disjoint union of i) $n + 2nb^2 + 1$ cliques of size b (each contributing eigenvalues -1 and $b-1$), and ii) $2nb^2 + 1$ cliques of size $L + i$ (each contributing eigenvalues -1 and $L + i - 1$) for each $0 \leq i \leq r-3$. So, the adjacency matrix of H has r distinct eigenvalues, namely $-1, b-1, L-1, L, L+1, \dots, L+(r-4)$. Thus, (G, nb^2) is a YES instance of r -EEA.

Reverse direction. Suppose that (G, nb^2) is a YES instance of r -EEA. That is, there exists $S \subseteq \binom{V(G)}{2} \setminus E(G)$ of size $\leq nb^2$ such that adding the edges of S to G results in a graph, say H , whose adjacency matrix has at most r distinct eigenvalues. Note that any edge of S is incident to at most two of the $2nb^2 + 1$ cliques of size b . So, as $|S| \leq nb^2$, there exists a b -sized clique that is not incident to any edge of S ; this clique survives as a component in H , contributing eigenvalues -1 and $b-1$. Similarly, for each $0 \leq i \leq r-3$, at least one clique of size $L + i$ survives as a component in H , contributing eigenvalues -1 and $L + i - 1$. So, the r

distinct eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix of H are $-1, b-1, L-1, L, L+1, \dots, L+(r-4)$. Now, using Lemma 5, it is clear that the graph H must be a disjoint union of some cliques, whose sizes are $b, L, L+1, \dots, L+(r-3)$.

Note that any clique of size $\geq L$ would need at least $L > nb^2$ edges to participate in a merger. So, as $|S| \leq nb^2$, all cliques of sizes $L, L+1, \dots, L+(r-3)$ must remain intact in H . So, the remaining cliques (i.e., C_1, \dots, C_{3n} and the $2nb^2+1$ cliques of size b) of G must merge to give some cliques of sizes $b, L, L+1, \dots, L+(r-3)$. However, note that all these cliques together contain $s_1 + \dots + s_{3n} + b \cdot (2nb^2 + 1) = nb + b \cdot (2nb^2 + 1) < L$ vertices. Thus, their merger would only give b -sized cliques; that is, no clique of size $L, L+1, \dots$, or $L+(r-3)$ is produced by such mergers. Now, as described in the proof of Theorem 17, each such b -sized clique must be obtained by merging exactly three cliques amongst C_1, \dots, C_{3n} , thereby showing that (T, b) is a YES instance of 3-Partition. This proves Theorem 19. \square

r -Eigenvalue Edge Deletion

Theorem 20. *2-EED admits an algorithm with running time $\mathcal{O}^*(2^k)$.*

Proof. We describe a recursive branching algorithm. Consider an instance, say (G, k) , of 2-EED. Due to Lemma 2, this problem amounts to deciding whether we can delete at most k edges from G to get a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques. First, we check if G has an induced path on three vertices. This takes polynomial time.

Case 1: G has no induced path on three vertices.

The graph G is a disjoint union of cliques, say C_1, \dots, C_t , of sizes s_1, \dots, s_t respectively. Observe that deleting the edges of any solution breaks each of these t cliques into equal-sized cliques (say, of size x). That is, for every $1 \leq i \leq t$, it breaks the clique C_i into $\frac{s_i}{x}$ cliques, each of size x . As each of these $\frac{s_i}{x}$ cliques has $\binom{x}{2}$ edges, the number of edges deleted from the clique C_i is

$$\binom{s_i}{2} - \frac{s_i}{x} \binom{x}{2} = \frac{s_i(s_i - x)}{2}$$

So, larger x corresponds to smaller solutions, i.e., fewer edge deletions. Also, x must divide each of s_1, \dots, s_t . Therefore, for any minimum-sized solution, we have $x = \gcd(s_1, \dots, s_t)$, and its size is

$$\sum_{i=1}^t \frac{s_i(s_i - \gcd(s_1, \dots, s_t))}{2}$$

If this size is at most k , we return YES; otherwise, we return NO. This takes polynomial time. See Figure 35 for an example.

Case 2. G has an induced path on three vertices, say $a - b - c$:

Note that any solution must pick at least one of its two edges, i.e., $\{a, b\}$ and $\{b, c\}$. So, if $k = 0$, we return NO; otherwise, we guess an edge that is picked into solution. That is, we branch as follows: In the first (resp. second) branch, we include the edge $\{a, b\}$ (resp. $\{b, c\}$) into solution, remove it from G , and reduce the parameter k by 1. It takes polynomial time to create the sub-problems $(G - \{a, b\}, k-1)$ and $(G - \{b, c\}, k-1)$. Next, we run our algorithm on these two instances. If at least one of these two recursive calls returns YES, so do we; otherwise, we return NO.

The depth of our search tree is at most k . Also, each of its internal nodes has two children. Therefore, it has at most $\mathcal{O}(2^k)$ nodes. Thus, as we spend polynomial time at each node, the overall running time is at most $\mathcal{O}^*(2^k)$. This proves Theorem 20. \square

Figure 35: An example illustrating the breaking of cliques in Theorem 20.

Proposition 2. *2-EED is polynomial-time solvable on triangle-free graphs.*

Proof. Due to Lemma 2, 2-EED amounts to deleting minimum number of edges from the input graph G to get a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques (say, of size x). Since G is triangle-free, the only possible values of x are 1 and 2; these correspond to deleting all edges of G , and deleting all edges except the edges of a perfect matching (if existent) of G , respectively.

So, if G has a perfect matching (can be checked in polynomial-time [34]), optimal solution has size $|E(G)| - \frac{|V(G)|}{2}$; otherwise, it has size $|E(G)|$. This proves Proposition 2. \square

Theorem 21. *For every $r \geq 3$, r -EED is NP-hard.*

Proof. We describe a reduction from Partition into Triangles on graphs of clique number three. Consider an instance, say G , of Partition into Triangles, where G is a graph, say on n vertices and m edges, with clique number three. Construct a graph, say H , from G , as follows: First, we add G as it is. Next, for each $3 \leq i \leq r+1$, we introduce $M := m - n + 1$ cliques, each of size i ; we refer to these cliques as *dummy cliques*. That is, the graph H is the disjoint union of the graph G , M dummy cliques of size 3, M dummy cliques of size 4, \dots , M dummy cliques of size $r+1$. We set the budget to be $m - n$. We show that G has $\frac{n}{3}$ pairwise vertex disjoint triangles if and only if $(H, m - n)$ is a YES instance of r -EED.

Forward direction. Suppose that G has $\frac{n}{3}$ pairwise vertex disjoint triangles, say $T_1, \dots, T_{n/3}$. Let S denote the set that consists of those $m - n$ edges of G that do not belong to any of these $\frac{n}{3}$ triangles. Note that the graph $H \setminus S$ is the disjoint union of

- $\frac{n}{3} + M$ triangles, namely $T_1, \dots, T_{n/3}$ and the M dummy cliques of size 3. They contribute two distinct eigenvalues, i.e., -1 and 2 .
- M dummy cliques of size 4. They contribute two distinct eigenvalues, i.e., -1 and 3 .
- \vdots
- M dummy cliques of size $r+1$. They contribute two distinct eigenvalues, i.e., -1 and r .

So, the adjacency matrix of the graph $H \setminus S$ has r distinct eigenvalues, namely $-1, 2, 3, \dots, r$. Thus, $(H, m - n)$ is a YES instance of r -EED.

Reverse direction. Suppose that $(H, m - n)$ is a YES instance of r -EED. That is, there exists $S \subseteq E(H)$ of size $\leq m - n$ such that the adjacency matrix of the graph obtained by deleting the edges of S from H has $\leq r$ distinct eigenvalues. Consider any $3 \leq i \leq r+1$. Note that the number of i -sized dummy cliques, i.e., M , is $> m - n \geq |S|$. So, there is at least one i -sized dummy clique, say C_i , such that none of its edges is deleted. That is, no edge of C_i belongs to S and thus, it appears as a component of the graph $H \setminus S$, thereby contributing two distinct eigenvalues, namely -1 and $i - 1$. Thus, it follows that the adjacency matrix of the graph $H \setminus S$ must have $-1, 2, 3, \dots, r$ as its r distinct eigenvalues. Now, using Lemma 5, it is clear that the graph $H \setminus S$ must be a disjoint union of some cliques, whose sizes are $3, 4, \dots, r+1$. So, as G has clique number 3, after removing those edges of G that belong to S , we are left with $\frac{n}{3}$ pairwise vertex-disjoint triangles of G , as desired. This proves 21. \square

r -Eigenvalue Edge Editing

Theorem 22. *2-EEE is NP-hard.*

Proof. We describe a reduction from Partition into Triangles. Consider an instance, say G , of Partition into Triangles, where G is a graph on n vertices and m edges. Construct a graph H based on G as follows: For every vertex $v \in V(G)$, attach two triangles to v ; we refer to these two triangles as *dummy triangles*, the two edges that join v to these triangles as *dummy edges*, and the four degree two vertices of these triangles as *saviour vertices* (see Figure 36). Note that $|V(H)| = 7n$ and $|E(H)| = m + 8n$. We show that G has $\frac{n}{3}$ pairwise vertex disjoint triangles if and only if $(H, m + n)$ is a YES instance of 2-EEE.

Figure 36: Attaching two triangles to every vertex in the proof of Theorem 22.

The graph G has $n = 6$ vertices and $m = 12$ edges, and it has $\frac{n}{3} = 2$ vertex disjoint triangles, namely T_1 and T_2 , shown in magenta.

Delete the $2n = 12$ red dummy edges, along with the $m - n = 6$ black dashed edges, from H . The resulting graph is the disjoint union of $\frac{7n}{3} = 14$ triangles, namely the two magenta triangles (T_1 and T_2) and the 12 dummy triangles.

Figure 37: This example illustrates the forward direction in proof of Theorem 22.

Forward direction. Suppose that G has $\frac{n}{3}$ pairwise vertex disjoint triangles, say $T_1, \dots, T_{n/3}$. Let $S \subseteq E(H)$ denote the set that consists of the $2n$ dummy edges, along with those $m - n$ edges of G that do not belong to any of these $\frac{n}{3}$ triangles. Note that the graph $H \setminus S$ is the disjoint union of $\frac{7n}{3}$ triangles, namely $T_1, \dots, T_{n/3}$ and the $2n$ dummy triangles. Its adjacency matrix has two distinct eigenvalues, i.e., -1 and 2 . Thus, $(H, m + n)$ is a YES instance of 2-EEE. See example in Figure 37.

Reverse direction. Suppose that $(H, m + n)$ is a YES instance of 2-EEE. That is, there exist $D \subseteq E(H)$ and $A \subseteq \binom{V(H)}{2} \setminus E(H)$ such that: i) $|A| + |D| \leq m + n$, and ii) deleting the edges of D from H , and adding the edges of A to H , results in a graph, say H' , whose adjacency matrix has at most two distinct eigenvalues. Using Lemma 2, the graph H' is a disjoint union of equal-sized cliques (say, of size x). As each of these $\frac{|V(H)|}{x}$ cliques has $\binom{x}{2}$ edges, the number of edges in H' is $\frac{|V(H)|}{x} \cdot \binom{x}{2} = \frac{7n(x-1)}{2}$. Also, we have $|E(H)| + |A| - |D| = |E(H')|$. Therefore, $(m + 8n) + |A| - |D| = \frac{7n(x-1)}{2}$. Adding this to the inequality $|A| + |D| \leq m + n$, we get

$$|A| \leq \frac{7n(x-3)}{4}. \quad (3)$$

Note that each saviour vertex has degrees 2 and $x - 1$ in H and H' respectively. So, each of the $4n$ saviour vertices is incident to $\geq x - 3$ added edges (i.e., edges of A). Also, any edge of A is incident to at most two saviour vertices. Therefore,

$$|A| \geq \frac{4n(x-3)}{2}. \quad (4)$$

Using (3) and (4), we get $x = 3$ and $|A| = 0$. Thus, the graph H' is a disjoint union of $\frac{7n}{3}$ triangles, obtained from H by only edge deletions (i.e., no edge additions are involved). So, we have $\frac{7n}{3}$ pairwise vertex disjoint triangles, say $T_1, \dots, T_{7n/3}$, of the $7n$ -vertex graph H . Note that the vertices of any dummy triangle belong to a unique triangle (i.e., the dummy triangle itself) in H . So, amongst $T_1, \dots, T_{7n/3}$, we must have the $2n$ dummy triangles. The remaining $\frac{7n}{3} - 2n = \frac{n}{3}$ triangles form a collection of pairwise vertex disjoint triangles in G , as desired. This proves Theorem 22. \square

Directions for Future Work. It remains to resolve i) classical complexity of 2-EVD on 3, 4, 5, 7-regular graphs, ii) classical complexity of r -EEE for any $r \geq 3$, and iii) parameterized complexity of r -EVD in the parameter k for any $r \geq 3$.

Chapter 4

Approximating Polynomials using Width-2 ABPs over Characteristic 2 Fields

In this chapter, we discuss the approximation power of width-2 ABPs over characteristic 2 fields (see *Preliminaries* for relevant definitions). It is known that width-2 ABPs can efficiently approximate formulas over fields of characteristic $\neq 2$ [20]. However, the case of characteristic 2 fields is open. To partially address this case, we study the following two related questions:

Q1. (Universality).

Can every polynomial be approximated by some width-2 ABP (of any size)?

Q2. (Efficiently approximating formulas upon powering). For any polynomial f with a small formula, can some small power of f be efficiently approximated by a width-2 ABP?

We answer Q1 affirmatively in Theorem 23. Also, in Theorem 24, we use Horner's method to show that univariate polynomials of degree d can be approximately computed using width-2 ABPs of size $\mathcal{O}(d)$. Finally, in Theorem 25, we answer Q2 affirmatively by showing that for any polynomial f that can be computed by an s -sized formula, some polynomially-bounded (in s) power of f can be approximated by a polynomial-sized (again, in s) width-2 ABP.

Background

In 1979, Valiant showed that algebraic formulas can be efficiently simulated using ABPs [77]. That is, $VF \subseteq VBP$. In 1987, Barrington showed that NC^1 circuits (i.e., polynomial-sized and logarithmic-depth Boolean circuits with fan-in two AND and OR gates) can be simulated using polynomial-sized width-5 permutation branching programs (i.e., S_5 -programs) [9]. As an algebraic analogue of Barrington's result, Ben-Or and Cleve showed in 1992 that polynomial-sized algebraic formulas can be simulated using polynomial-sized width-3 ABPs [14]. That is, $VF \subseteq VBP_3$. ABP has a layered DAG structure; as one moves layer-by-layer from source-to-sink, the polynomial computed at any intermediate node is a weighted combination of the polynomials computed at nodes in the previous layer, where the weights are specified as edge labels. In an ABP of small width, only a few intermediate polynomials can be carried forward from a layer to its next layer. So, intuitively, bounded-width ABPs seem to lose computational power as compared to ABPs. Such ABPs can be efficiently simulated using formulas, i.e., $VBP_k \subseteq VF$ for all $k \geq 1$. Nevertheless, Ben-Or and Cleve's result says that as long as width is ≥ 3 , their power does not fall below that of formulas, i.e., $VF \subseteq VBP_k$ for all $k \geq 3$. Thus, the classes $VBP_3, VBP_4, VBP_5, \dots$ are same as the class VF .

Then, it is natural to ask whether width-2 ABPs are also powerful enough to efficiently simulate formulas. In 2016, Allender and Wang settled this question by proving non-universality of width-2 ABPs [3]. They showed that $x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + \dots + x_8y_8$ cannot be computed by width-2 ABPs (of any size) over any field. So, $VBP_2 \subsetneq VF$. In 2018, Bringmann, Ikenmeyer

and Zuydam showed that width-2 ABPs can efficiently approximate formulas over fields of characteristic $\neq 2$ [20]. That is, $VF \subseteq \overline{VBP}_2$. Approximating complex mathematical objects by simpler ones is a long-standing mathematical tradition (e.g., approximations of π [80]). Specifically, in algebraic complexity theory, some earlier studies of complexity measures by allowing approximations include [69] and [22]. The BIZ proof builds width-2 ABPs to approximate polynomials at all intermediate nodes of formula in the format $Q(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ in a bottom-up manner. The ABP-size so obtained is exponential in formula-depth (which can be logarithmically bounded, as proved by Brent in 1974 [19]). To approximate polynomials computed by $+$ gates, this proof uses the addition rule $Q(f)Q(0)Q(g) = Q(f+g)$. To approximate polynomials computed by \times gates, it reduces multiplication to squaring and addition using the identity $-(f/2)^2 - g^2 + (f/2 + g)^2 = f \cdot g$, and then shows how to attain *squaring*, i.e., how to get a width-2 ABP that approximates $Q(f^2)$ using a width-2 ABP that approximates $Q(f)$ twice. However, the above identity can be used only when characteristic $\neq 2$.

Brief description of our proofs.

Note that every polynomial can be naturally computed by a $\Sigma\Pi$ circuit based on its *sum-of-monomials* representation. So, to answer Q1 (i.e., to show universality), it suffices to approximate $\Sigma\Pi$ circuits using width-2 ABPs. We work with a slight extension, i.e., depth-four $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma\Pi^{(2)}$ circuits with bottom fan-in two. We build a width-2 ABP that computes $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ for the output g (i.e., sum of product of two variables) of any Level 2 Σ gate. Then, we describe how to get a width-2 ABP that approximates $Q(fg)$ using width-2 ABPs that compute $Q(f) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ and $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ twice and once respectively. Also, we show how to get a width-2 ABP that approximates $Q(fg^2)$ using width-2 ABPs that approximate $Q(f)$ and $Q(g)$ once and twice respectively. Using these two conversions repeatedly, we obtain a width-2 ABP that approximates the output of any Level 3 Π gate in Q format, and then repeatedly use $Q(f)Q(0)Q(g) = Q(f+g)$ to approximate the output of the topmost gate, i.e., Level 4 Σ gate. See Theorem 23 for details. This construction works for all characteristics. To address Q2, we approximate a suitable power (in terms of product-depth) of polynomial at every intermediate node of formula in a bottom-up manner. This proof works only when characteristic is 2 as it uses the identity $(f+g)^{2^d} = f^{2^d} + g^{2^d}$. See Theorem 25 for details.

Preliminaries

Polynomial-family. A p -family is a sequence $(f_n)_{n \geq 1}$ of polynomials whose number of variables and degrees are *polynomially-bounded*. That is, there exist polynomial functions $a(n)$ and $b(n)$ such that for each $n \geq 1$, f_n has at most $a(n)$ indeterminates and $\text{degree}(f_n) \leq b(n)$. These constraints ensure that evaluating f_n by substituting its indeterminates with constants would not give too large a number (i.e., it can be expressed using no more than $n^{\mathcal{O}(1)}$ bits).

Algebraic Formulas. A polynomial can be written using multiple expressions on paper. For example, $1+x_1+x_2+x_3+x_1x_2+x_1x_3+x_2x_3$, $(1+x_1)(1+x_2+x_3+x_2x_3)$ and $(1+x_1)(1+x_2)(1+x_3)$ are three different expressions for the same polynomial. These expressions are referred to as *formulas*. The number of additions and multiplications involved in writing a formula is called its *size*. The above three example formulas have sizes 9 (6 $+$'s and 3 \times 's), 6 (4 $+$'s and 2 \times 's) and 5 (3 $+$'s and 2 \times 's) respectively. Equivalently, a formula and its size can be inductively

Figure 38: This figure shows an example width-2 ABP with source s and sink t . There are three $s \rightarrow t$ paths, namely $s \rightarrow v_1 \rightarrow v_2 \rightarrow t$, $s \rightarrow v_1 \rightarrow v_4 \rightarrow t$, $s \rightarrow v_3 \rightarrow v_2 \rightarrow t$. The products of edge labels of these paths are $x_1x_3x_2$, x_1x_2 , x_3x_2 respectively. So, this ABP computes the polynomial $x_1x_3x_2 + x_1x_2 + x_3x_2$.

defined as follows: i) Constants and indeterminates are 0-sized formulas. ii) For any formulas F_1 and F_2 , $F_1 + F_2$ and $F_1 \times F_2$ are also formulas, and their size is $\text{size}(F_1) + \text{size}(F_2) + 1$. Pictorially, a formula can be viewed as a rooted binary tree with $+$ and \times gates as non-leaf nodes, and constants and indeterminates as leaf nodes. Its size is the number of non-leaf nodes, and its *depth* is the length of its longest leaf-to-root path. Each gate must have out-degree ≤ 1 . This captures the constraint that while writing an expression, if a sub-expression appears multiple times, then it must be built from scratch each time (i.e., no re-use is allowed).

The class VF or VP_e (Valiant's formulas/polynomial-sized expressions) consists of p -families $(f_n)_{n \geq 1}$ that can be computed by polynomial-sized formulas. That is, there exists a polynomial function $s(n)$ such that for each $n \geq 1$, f_n can be computed by a formula of size at most $s(n)$.

Straight-line Programs (a.k.a. Algebraic Circuits). A *straight-line program* is a sequence of instructions, where every instruction adds or multiplies polynomials computed by previous instructions. For example, the sequence of instructions $R_1 \leftarrow 1 + x_1, R_2 \leftarrow 1 + x_2, R_3 \leftarrow R_1 \times R_1, R_4 \leftarrow R_3 + R_2$ computes the polynomial $(1 + x_1)^2 + (1 + x_2)$. The *size* of an SLP is the number of instructions; so, the above example has size 4. Note that some instructions can be processed in parallel, while some instructions need to wait for outputs of other instructions before being processed. This naturally gives a way to interpret an SLP as a mix of parallel-and-sequential computations. Pictorially, it can be viewed as an *algebraic circuit*, i.e., a generalization of formulas, where the out-degree ≤ 1 constraint is relaxed (i.e., re-use is allowed). Observe that slim-and-tall (i.e., large depth) and fat-and-short (i.e., small depth) circuits correspond to more sequential and parallel natures of computation respectively. The gates of a circuit can be viewed as processors, and its depth is a measure of overall runtime.

The class VP (Valiant's analogue of P) consists of p -families $(f_n)_{n \geq 1}$ that can be computed by polynomial-sized circuits. Since circuits generalize formulas, we have $VF \subseteq VP$.

Algebraic Branching Programs. An *algebraic branching program* is a layered directed acyclic graph with designated *source* and *sink* vertices. Every edge (directed from some layer to its next layer) is labelled with either an indeterminate or a constant from the base field. The ABP is said to compute the sum of product of edge labels over all its source-to-sink paths. See Figure 38 for an example.

The class VBP (Valiant's branching programs) consists of p -families that can be computed by polynomial-sized ABPs. The family (\det_n) , defined as the determinant of an $n \times n$ matrix of indeterminates, is VBP -complete under p -projections. That is, (\det_n) can be computed by

polynomial-sized ABPs [62], and any family in VBP can be obtained as its efficient projection. The power of ABPs lies between that of formulas and circuits, i.e., $VF \subseteq VBP \subseteq VP$.

Approximate computation. For any polynomials f and g over base field \mathbb{F} and its extension $\mathbb{F}(\varepsilon)$ respectively, g is said to *approximate* f if $g = f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$, where $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ refers to any polynomial of the form $\varepsilon h_1 + \varepsilon^2 h_2 + \dots + \varepsilon^r h_r$, where $r \geq 0$ and h_1, \dots, h_r are polynomials over \mathbb{F} . For example, $x_1 x_2 + \varepsilon x_1 + \varepsilon^2 x_2$ approximates $x_1 x_2$. Also, an ABP with edge labels as indeterminates or constants from $\mathbb{F}(\varepsilon)$ is said to *approximately compute* a polynomial f over \mathbb{F} if the polynomial computed by this ABP approximates f , i.e., it computes $f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

Width of ABPs. The maximum number of vertices per layer in an ABP is called its *width*. A width- k ABP can be viewed as a sequence of $k \times k$ matrices, and vice versa. To do so, set the entry at i^{th} row and j^{th} column of ℓ^{th} matrix as the label of the edge directed from i^{th} vertex of layer ℓ to j^{th} vertex of layer $\ell + 1$. Then, $(1, 1)$ -entry of the product of these $k \times k$ matrices is same as the polynomial computed by the width- k ABP. For example, the sequence of 2×2 matrices corresponding to the width-2 ABP shown in Figure 38 is $\begin{pmatrix} x_1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_3 & 1 \\ x_3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_2 & 0 \\ x_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. The class VBP_k (resp. \overline{VBP}_k) consists of p -families that can be computed (resp. approximately computed) by polynomial-sized width- k ABPs (or equivalently, polynomial-sized sequence of $k \times k$ matrices).

$\Sigma \Pi \Sigma \Pi \dots$ **Circuits.** These are circuits whose levels consist of Σ (i.e., $+$) and Π (i.e., \times) gates in an alternating manner. We number the bottom-most level (i.e., the level whose gates take indeterminates or constants as inputs) as Level 1. Then, moving bottom-to-top, we number the remaining levels as Level 2, Level 3, \dots . We use superscripts to indicate fan-in's of gates at any level. For example, $\Sigma^{(2)} \Pi^{(3)} \Sigma^{(4)}$ circuits are depth-three circuits whose Level 1, Level 2, Level 3 consist of fan-in 4 Σ gates, fan-in 3 Π gates, fan-in 2 Σ gates respectively.

Approximating $\Sigma^{(a)} \Pi^{(b)} \Sigma^{(c)} \Pi^{(2)}$ Circuits using Width-2 ABPs

In this section, we address Q1 (i.e., show universality) by proving that $\Sigma^{(a)} \Pi^{(b)} \Sigma^{(c)} \Pi^{(2)}$ circuits¹⁵ can be approximated using width-2 ABPs of size $\mathcal{O}(a \cdot c \cdot (b + 2^t))$, where t denotes the maximum number of polynomials that appear an odd number of times amongst the outputs of Level 2 Σ gates that are fed into any Level 3 Π gate (see Figure 39).

Theorem 23. *Let C be a $\Sigma^{(a)} \Pi^{(b)} \Sigma^{(c)} \Pi^{(2)}$ circuit. Then, the polynomial computed by C can be approximately computed by a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(a \cdot c \cdot (b + 2^t))$ 2-by-2 matrices, where*

$$t := \max_{G: G \text{ is a Level 3 } \Pi \text{ gate in } C} \left\{ \left| \{p \mid p \text{ appears an odd number of times amongst the } b \text{ inputs of } G\} \right| \right\}.$$

First, we prove the following three lemmas:

Lemma 7. *There is a sequence of $4c+1$ 2-by-2 matrices that computes $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon \sum_{i=1}^c x_i y_i + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$.*

Proof. For each $1 \leq i \leq c$, let Φ_i be the sequence $\begin{pmatrix} x_i & -1 \\ \varepsilon & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} y_i & 1 \\ \frac{-1}{\varepsilon} & x_i \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 \\ y_i & \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. Note that Φ_i computes $\begin{pmatrix} x_i y_i + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} & 0 \\ \varepsilon y_i & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon & 0 \\ -\varepsilon y_i & \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \varepsilon x_i y_i & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$. Concatenating the se-

¹⁵Recall that the superscripts indicate fan-in's.

Figure 39: Depth-four $\Sigma^{(a)}\Pi^{(b)}\Sigma^{(c)}\Pi^{(2)}$ circuit.

quences $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_c$ and prepending the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ gives a sequence of $4c+1$ matrices that computes $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \left(\prod_{i=1}^c \begin{pmatrix} 1 + \varepsilon x_i y_i & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon \sum_{i=1}^c x_i y_i + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. \square

Lemma 8. Let f and g be polynomials. Suppose that there are sequences σ and π of M and N matrices that compute $Q(f)^{16} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ and $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ respectively. Then, there is a sequence τ of $2M + N + 2$ 2-by-2 matrices that computes $Q(fg) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

Proof. Let τ be the sequence $\begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \sigma|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3} \pi|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix}$ of $2M + N + 2$ matrices, where $\sigma|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3}$ is the sequence obtained from σ by replacing ε with ε^3 . Note that τ computes

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{f}{\varepsilon} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & \frac{1}{\varepsilon} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \\ -1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \varepsilon + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4) \\ 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{f}{\varepsilon} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & \frac{1}{\varepsilon} + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \\ -1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^4) \\ f + \varepsilon fg + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & \varepsilon + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= Q(fg) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 9. Let f and g be polynomials. Suppose that there are sequences σ and π of M and N matrices that compute $Q(f) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ and $Q(g) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ respectively. Then, there is a sequence τ of $M + 2N + 4$ 2-by-2 matrices that computes $Q(fg^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

¹⁶Recall that $Q(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$.

Proof. Let τ be the sequence $\begin{pmatrix} -1/\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \pi|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \sigma|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^5} \begin{pmatrix} -\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \pi|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3} \begin{pmatrix} 1/\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix}$ of $M + 2N + 4$ matrices, where $\pi|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3}$ and $\sigma|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^5}$ are the sequences obtained from π and σ by replacing ε with ε^3 and ε^5 respectively. Note that $\begin{pmatrix} -1/\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \pi|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\varepsilon \end{pmatrix}$ computes $\begin{pmatrix} -1/\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\varepsilon \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & -1/\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) \\ \varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix}$, and $\begin{pmatrix} -\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \pi|_{\varepsilon \rightarrow \varepsilon^3} \begin{pmatrix} 1/\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix}$ computes $\begin{pmatrix} -\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & 1/\varepsilon \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1/\varepsilon & 0 \\ 0 & \varepsilon \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & -\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \\ 1/\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix}$. So, τ computes the following:

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} -g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & -1/\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) \\ \varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) & 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \\ 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & -\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \\ 1/\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} -fg - 1/\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) & -g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ \varepsilon^2 f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & \varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -g + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & -\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \\ 1/\varepsilon^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) & \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} fg^2 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) & 1 + \varepsilon^2 fg + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) \\ 1 - \varepsilon^2 fg + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^3) & -\varepsilon^4 f + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^5) \end{pmatrix} \\ &= Q(fg^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Theorem 23. First, consider any Level 2 Σ gate in C . Note that its output is of the form $\sum_{i=1}^c x_i y_i$. Using Lemma 7, we get a sequence of $4c + 1$ matrices that computes $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 + \varepsilon \sum_{i=1}^c x_i y_i + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2) & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. Also, using Lemma 8 (with $f = 1$ and $g = \sum_{i=1}^c x_i y_i$), we get a sequence of $4c + 5$ matrices that computes $Q(\sum_{i=1}^c x_i y_i) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

Next, consider any Level 3 Π gate G in C . Its output is the product of the b outputs of the Level 2 Σ gates that are fed as inputs into G . Let p_1, \dots, p_ℓ denote the distinct polynomials amongst these b inputs of G (say, with multiplicities k_1, \dots, k_ℓ respectively). Then, the output of G is $p_1^{k_1} p_2^{k_2} \dots p_\ell^{k_\ell}$. Without loss of generality, assume that k_1, \dots, k_t are the t odd k_i 's amongst k_1, \dots, k_ℓ . See Figure 40.

Figure 40: Level 3 Π gate G of C and its b inputs in proof of Theorem 23.

Repeatedly using Lemma 8 to get $Q(p_1 \dots p_t)$:

Using Lemma 8 (with $f = p_1$ and $g = p_2$), we get a sequence of $2 \cdot (4c + 5) + (4c + 1) + 2 =$

$12c + 13$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1 p_2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. Again, using Lemma 8 (with $f = p_1 p_2$ and $g = p_3$), we get a sequence of $2 \cdot (12c + 13) + (4c + 1) + 2 = 28c + 29$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1 p_2 p_3) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. This continues in a similar manner. Finally, using Lemma 8 (with $f = p_1 \dots p_{t-1}$ and $g = p_t$), we get a sequence of $2 \cdot ((c+1) \cdot 2^{t+1} - (4c+3)) + (4c+1) + 2 = (c+1) \cdot 2^{t+2} - (4c+3) = \mathcal{O}(c \cdot 2^t)$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1 \dots p_t) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

Repeatedly using Lemma 9 to get $Q((p_1 \dots p_t) \cdot (p_1^{\frac{k_1-1}{2}})^2 \dots (p_t^{\frac{k_t-1}{2}})^2)$:

Using Lemma 9 (with $g = p_1$) $\frac{k_1-1}{2}$ times, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot 2^t) + (\frac{k_1-1}{2}) \cdot (2 \cdot (4c+5) + 4)$ matrices that computes $Q((p_1 p_2 \dots p_t) \cdot (p_1^{\frac{k_1-1}{2}})^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. Again, using Lemma 9 (with $g = p_2$) $\frac{k_2-1}{2}$ times, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot 2^t) + (\frac{k_1-1}{2} + \frac{k_2-1}{2}) \cdot (2 \cdot (4c+5) + 4)$ matrices that computes $Q((p_1 p_2 \dots p_t) \cdot (p_1^{\frac{k_1-1}{2}})^2 (p_2^{\frac{k_2-1}{2}})^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. This continues in a similar manner. Finally, using Lemma 9 (with $g = p_t$) $\frac{k_t-1}{2}$ times, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot 2^t) + (\frac{k_1-1}{2} + \frac{k_2-1}{2} + \dots + \frac{k_t-1}{2}) \cdot (2 \cdot (4c+5) + 4) = \mathcal{O}(c \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^t k_i + 2^t))$ matrices that computes $Q((p_1 p_2 \dots p_t) \cdot (p_1^{\frac{k_1-1}{2}})^2 (p_2^{\frac{k_2-1}{2}})^2 \dots (p_t^{\frac{k_t-1}{2}})^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) = Q(p_1^{k_1} p_2^{k_2} \dots p_t^{k_t}) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

Repeatedly using Lemma 9 to get $Q((p_1^{k_1} \dots p_t^{k_t}) \cdot (p_{t+1}^{\frac{k_{t+1}}{2}})^2 \dots (p_\ell^{\frac{k_\ell}{2}})^2)$:

Using Lemma 9 (with $g = p_{t+1}$) $\frac{k_{t+1}}{2}$ times, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^t k_i + 2^t)) + \frac{k_{t+1}}{2} \cdot (2 \cdot (4c+5) + 4)$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1^{k_1} \dots p_t^{k_t} \cdot (p_{t+1}^{\frac{k_{t+1}}{2}})^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. Again, using Lemma 9 (with $g = p_{t+1}$) $\frac{k_{t+2}}{2}$ times, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^t k_i + 2^t)) + (\frac{k_{t+1}}{2} + \frac{k_{t+2}}{2}) \cdot (2 \cdot (4c+5) + 4)$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1^{k_1} \dots p_t^{k_t} \cdot (p_{t+1}^{\frac{k_{t+1}}{2}})^2 (p_{t+2}^{\frac{k_{t+2}}{2}})^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. This continues in a similar manner. Finally, using Lemma 9 (with $g = p_\ell$) $\frac{k_\ell}{2}$ times, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^t k_i + 2^t)) + (\frac{k_{t+1}}{2} + \frac{k_{t+2}}{2} + \dots + \frac{k_\ell}{2}) \cdot (2 \cdot (4c+5) + 4) = \mathcal{O}(c \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^\ell k_i + 2^t))$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1^{k_1} \dots p_t^{k_t} \cdot (p_{t+1}^{\frac{k_{t+1}}{2}})^2 (p_{t+2}^{\frac{k_{t+2}}{2}})^2 \dots (p_\ell^{\frac{k_\ell}{2}})^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. That is, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(c \cdot (b + 2^t))$ matrices that computes $Q(p_1^{k_1} \dots p_\ell^{k_\ell}) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.

Finally, consider the top-most Level 4 Σ gate. We repeatedly use $Q(f)Q(0)Q(g) = Q(f+g)$ to get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(a \cdot c \cdot (b + 2^t))$ matrices that approximately computes its output (i.e., sum of outputs of the a Level 3 Π gates) in Q -format. This proves Theorem 23.

Approximating Univariate Polynomials using Width-2 ABPs

Theorem 24. *Let p be a univariate polynomial. Then, there is a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(\text{degree}(p))$ 2-by-2 matrices that computes $Q(p) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$.*

Proof. Let $d := \text{degree}(p)$ if $\text{degree}(p)$ is even, and $d := \text{degree}(p) - 1$ otherwise. If $\text{degree}(p)$ is even, p is of the form $a_d x^d + a_{d-1} x^{d-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$. Otherwise, p is of the form $a_{d+1} x^{d+1} + a_d x^d + a_{d-1} x^{d-1} + \dots + a_1 x + a_0$. Using Horner's rule (see [81]),

$$p = \left(\dots \left((a x^2 + a_{d-1} x + a_{d-2}) x^2 + a_{d-3} x + a_{d-4} \right) x^2 + \dots + a_3 x + a_2 \right) x^2 + a_1 x + a_0,$$

where $a := a_d$ if $\text{degree}(p)$ is even, and $a := a_{d+1} x + a_d$ otherwise. First, we compute $Q(a)$. When d is even, $Q(a_d)$ computes $Q(a)$. When d is odd, we use the length-2 sequence $\begin{pmatrix} a_{d+1} & a_d \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x & \frac{1}{a_{d+1}} \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ to compute $Q(a)$. Next, using Lemma 9 (with $g = x$), we get a sequence of $\leq 2+2+4 = 8$ matrices that computes $Q(ax^2) + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$. We append this sequence

with $Q(0) \begin{pmatrix} a_{d-1} & a_{d-2} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x & \frac{1}{a_{d-1}} \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ when $a_{d-1} \neq 0$, and $Q(0)Q(a_{d-2})$ when $a_{d-1} = 0$.

This gives us a sequence of at most $8 + 3 = 11$ matrices that computes $Q(ax^2 + a_{d-1}x + a_{d-2}) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$. Again, using Lemma 9 (with $g = x$), we get a sequence of $\leq 11 + 2 + 4 = 17$ matrices that computes $Q((ax^2 + a_{d-1}x + a_{d-2})x^2) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$. As before, we append it with

$Q(0) \begin{pmatrix} a_{d-3} & a_{d-4} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x & \frac{1}{a_{d-3}} \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$ when $a_{d-3} \neq 0$, and $Q(0)Q(a_{d-4})$ when $a_{d-3} = 0$. This

gives us a sequence of $\leq 17 + 3 = 20$ matrices that computes $Q((ax^2 + a_{d-1}x + a_{d-2})x^2 + a_{d-3}x + a_{d-4}) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$. We continue this process. Finally, we get a sequence of $\leq \frac{9d+4}{2} = \mathcal{O}(\text{degree}(p))$ matrices that computes $Q(p) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon)$. This proves Theorem 24. \square

Efficiently Approximating Formulas upon Powering

Theorem 25. *Over fields of characteristic two, there exists a constant k such that for any polynomial f with a size- s formula computing it, there is a $d \leq s^k + k$ such that f^d can be approximately computed by a width-2 ABP of size $\leq s^k + k$.*

Proof. It is sufficient to consider $IMM_{3,n}$ for an arbitrary n as IMM_3 is a VF -complete family. Without loss of generality, consider n to be a power of two. These polynomials have polynomial-size formulas of depth $\mathcal{O}(\log(n))$ where every root-to-leaf path has the same number of product gates. We construct a width-2 ABP inductively from the formula as follows: For every polynomial p computed at a sub-formula with product depth d , we will compute $Q(p^{2^d})$. For input gates, this is trivial. Suppose f and g are sub-formulas that have product depth d . For the formula $f + g$, note that $(f + g)^{2^d} = f^{2^d} + g^{2^d}$ over fields of characteristic two. We compute $Q(f^{2^d} + g^{2^d})$ as $Q(f^{2^d})Q(0)Q(g^{2^d})$. For the formula $f \cdot g$, we compute $Q((f^{2^d})^2(g^{2^d})^2) = Q((fg)^{2^{d+1}})$ using Lemma 9. Since product depth is same on every root-to-leaf path, these cases are exhaustive. As each step increases the size by only at most a constant factor and depth is $\mathcal{O}(\log(n))$, the resulting width-2 ABP has $n^{\mathcal{O}(1)}$ size. \square

Directions for Future Work.

The question that whether $VF \subseteq \overline{VBP}_2$ over characteristic 2 fields remains open.

Chapter 5

Bounded-Width ABPs over Min-Plus Semirings

In this chapter, we study the power of bounded-width ABPs over min-plus semirings R and N . Specifically, we show that i) width-2 ABPs are non-universal over R , ii) any polynomial of degree d and *sparsity* (i.e., number of monomials) s can be computed by an $\mathcal{O}(d \cdot s)$ -sized width-3 ABP over R and N , iii) any univariate polynomial of degree d can be computed by an $\mathcal{O}(d)$ -sized width-3 ABP over R , iv) depth-three $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma$ circuits can be efficiently simulated using width-4 ABPs over R and N , and v) depth-four $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma\Pi$ and depth-five $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma\Pi\Sigma$ circuits can be efficiently simulated using width-5 and width-6 ABPs over N respectively.

Related work. In 1982, Jerrum and Snir obtained tight lower bounds on number of multiplications required to compute functions such as iterated matrix multiplication, iterated convolution and permanent over semirings $(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, +, \times)$ and $(\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, \min, +)$ [54]. Circuits over semirings gained attention because many known dynamic programming algorithms can be viewed as such circuits (see, for example, Bellman-Held-Karp algorithm to solve the *Travelling Salesman problem* [13]). In 2015, Jukna presented bounds on size and depth of circuits over arithmetic, Boolean and tropical semirings that compute graph polynomials such as perfect matching, spanning tree, all-pairs connectivity, s - t connectivity, s - t walk, Hamiltonian cycle and k -clique polynomials [55]. In the same work, he also discussed bounds based on polynomial properties such as t -simplicity, homogeneity, multilinearity, separability and minimum degree.

Preliminaries

Definition of semiring. Let G be a set equipped with *addition* (denoted as $+$) and *multiplication* (denoted as \cdot) operations. Then, $(G, +, \cdot)$ is called a *semiring* if i) $(G, +)$ is a commutative monoid, ii) (G, \cdot) is a monoid, iii) multiplying (from either side) the additive identity with any element of G gives back the additive identity, and iv) multiplication (from either side) distributes over addition. Based on the definition of *monoid*, the first and second conditions together can be alternatively put as follows: i) G is closed under $+$ and \cdot , ii) both $+$ and \cdot are associative, iii) $+$ is commutative, and iv) there exist additive and multiplicative identities. Semirings generalize *rings* by allowing elements to not have additive inverses.

Polynomials over semirings. We treat two n -variate polynomials f and g over a semiring $(G, +, \cdot)$ to be the same polynomial (even if their coefficients do not match) if they represent the same function from G^n to G ; that is, for each possible substitution of the n indeterminates with values from G , the polynomials f and g evaluate to the same value.

Min-plus semirings N and R . We use N and R to denote the semirings $(\mathbb{N} \cup \{\infty\}, \oplus, \otimes)$ and $(\mathbb{R} \cup \{\infty\}, \oplus, \otimes)$ respectively, where \mathbb{N} is the set of all non-negative integers, \mathbb{R} is the set of all real numbers, \oplus denotes the minimum operation (serving as the semirings' addition

operation), and \otimes denotes usual addition (serving as the semirings' multiplication operation). Note that 0 and ∞ are the multiplicative and additive identities of these semirings. Also, for any variable x and any positive integer d , we use the notation $x^{\otimes d}$ to denote $\underbrace{x \otimes x \otimes \dots \otimes x}_{d \text{ times}}$.

Non-Universality of Width-2 ABPs over R

Theorem 26. *No width-2 ABP can compute $x_1 \otimes y_1 \oplus x_2 \otimes y_2 \oplus x_3 \otimes y_3$ over R .*

Proof. For the sake of contradiction, assume that there is a width-2 ABP Γ that computes $x_1 \otimes y_1 \oplus x_2 \otimes y_2 \oplus x_3 \otimes y_3$ over R . Let $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ denote the set of all source-to-sink paths P in Γ such that no edge of P is labelled ∞ . First, we prove the following two lemmas:

Lemma 10. *No path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ can contain both x_1 and x_2 (similar argument works for the pairs (x_1, y_2) , (x_1, x_3) , (x_1, y_3) , (y_1, x_2) , (y_1, y_2) , (y_1, x_3) , (y_1, y_3) , (x_2, x_3) , (x_2, y_3) , (y_2, x_3) , (y_2, y_3) , i.e., all pairs except (x_1, y_1) , (x_2, y_2) , (x_3, y_3)).*

Proof. For the sake of contradiction, assume that there is a path P^* in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ that contains both x_1 and x_2 . The weight¹⁷ of P^* is of the form $c \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_1} \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_1} \otimes x_2^{\otimes \alpha_2} \otimes y_2^{\otimes \beta_2} \otimes x_3^{\otimes \alpha_3} \otimes y_3^{\otimes \beta_3}$, where $c \in \mathbb{R}$, α_1 and α_2 are integers ≥ 1 , and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \alpha_3, \beta_3$ are integers ≥ 0 . Note that Γ computes $\text{weight}(P^*) \oplus \bigoplus_{P \in \mathcal{P}(\Gamma) \setminus \{P^*\}} \text{weight}(P) \leq \text{weight}(P^*)$. So, we get

$x_1 \otimes y_1 \oplus x_2 \otimes y_2 \oplus x_3 \otimes y_3 \leq c \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_1} \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_1} \otimes x_2^{\otimes \alpha_2} \otimes y_2^{\otimes \beta_2} \otimes x_3^{\otimes \alpha_3} \otimes y_3^{\otimes \beta_3}$. Putting $y_1 = y_2 = x_3 = y_3 = 0$, we get $x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus 0 \leq c \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_1} \otimes x_2^{\otimes \alpha_2}$. Writing this in usual addition/multiplication notation, we get $\min\{x_1, x_2, 0\} \leq c + \alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2$. If $c = 0$, putting $x_1 = -\frac{1}{\alpha_1}$ and $x_2 = -\frac{1}{\alpha_2}$ gives $\min\{-\frac{1}{\alpha_1}, -\frac{1}{\alpha_2}\} \leq -2$, which is not possible as $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \geq 1$. Also, if $c < 0$, putting $x_1 = x_2 = 0$ gives $0 \leq c$, which is not possible. Therefore, $c > 0$. Putting $x_1 = x_2 = \frac{-c-1}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1}$ gives $\frac{-c-1}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} \leq c + (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2) \left(\frac{-c-1}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} \right)$. This simplifies to $\frac{-c-1}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1} \leq \frac{-c - (\alpha_1 + \alpha_2)}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - 1}$, which is not possible as $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \geq 1$. This proves Lemma 10. \square

Lemma 11. *There is a path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ that contains both x_1 and y_1 (similar argument works for the pairs (x_2, y_2) and (x_3, y_3)).*

Proof. Suppose not. Then, combined with Lemma 10, this implies that every path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ has weight of one of the following four types: i) $c \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha}$, where $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\alpha \geq 0$ (Type 1), ii) $c \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta}$, where $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\beta \geq 0$ (Type 2), iii) $c \otimes x_2^{\otimes \alpha} \otimes y_2^{\otimes \beta}$, where $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$ (Type 3), and iv) $c \otimes x_3^{\otimes \alpha} \otimes y_3^{\otimes \beta}$, where $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$ (Type 4). Let $c_1 \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_1}, c_2 \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_2}, \dots, c_N \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_N}$ denote all Type 1 weights (where $c_1, \dots, c_N \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_N$ are integers ≥ 0). Let $d_1 \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_1}, d_2 \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_2}, \dots, d_M \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_M}$ denote all Type 2 weights (where $d_1, \dots, d_M \in \mathbb{R}$ and β_1, \dots, β_M are integers ≥ 0). Note that Γ computes the sum of all Type 1, Type 2, Type 3 and Type 4 weights, which is \leq (sum of Type 1 weights) \oplus (sum of Type 2 weights). So, we get $x_1 \otimes y_1 \oplus x_2 \otimes y_2 \oplus x_3 \otimes y_3 \leq$

$$\bigoplus_{1 \leq i \leq N} c_i \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_i} \oplus \bigoplus_{1 \leq j \leq M} d_j \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_j}. \text{ Putting } x_2 = y_2 = x_3 = y_3 = \infty, \text{ we get } x_1 \otimes y_1 \leq$$

$$\bigoplus_{1 \leq i \leq N} c_i \otimes x_1^{\otimes \alpha_i} \oplus \bigoplus_{1 \leq j \leq M} d_j \otimes y_1^{\otimes \beta_j}. \text{ Writing this in usual addition/multiplication notation,}$$

¹⁷The *weight* of a path is the product of the labels of its edges.

we get $x_1 + y_1 \leq \min \left\{ \min_{1 \leq i \leq N} \{c_i + \alpha_i x_i\}, \min_{1 \leq j \leq M} \{d_j + \beta_j y_j\} \right\}$. Putting $x_1 = 0$ and $y_1 = c_1 + 1$ gives LHS = $c_1 + 1$ and RHS $\leq c_1$, a contradiction. This proves Lemma 11. \square

Based on Lemmas 10 and 11, it follows that there exist paths $P_1, P_2, P_3 \in \mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ such that i) in P_1 , both x_1 and y_1 appear (each at least once) as edge labels, and none of x_2, y_2, x_3, y_3 appear as edge labels, ii) in P_2 , both x_2 and y_2 appear (each at least once) as edge labels, and none of x_1, y_1, x_3, y_3 appear as edge labels, and iii) in P_3 , both x_3 and y_3 appear (each at least once) as edge labels, and none of x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2 appear as edge labels.

Amongst the edges that appear in $E(P_1) \cup E(P_2) \cup E(P_3)$, consider a first (moving from left to right) edge that is labelled by an indeterminate. Without loss of generality, assume that this edge belongs to path P_1 , and it is labelled by x_1 . Also, let i and $i + 1$ denote the indices of the layers containing the tail and head of this edge respectively. This edge has four possible orientations, i.e., top level of layer i to top level of layer $i + 1$, top level of layer i to bottom level of layer $i + 1$, bottom level of layer i to top level of layer $i + 1$, and bottom level of layer i to bottom level of layer $i + 1$ (see Figure 41).

This edge of P_1 is the first edge (moving from left to right) which is labelled by an indeterminate amongst all edges of $E(P_1) \cup E(P_2) \cup E(P_3)$

All edges of $E(P_1) \cup E(P_2) \cup E(P_3)$ in this region (i.e., before layer i) are labelled by constants from \mathbb{R}

Figure 41

Next, amongst the edges that appear in $E(P_2) \cup E(P_3)$ after layer i , consider a first (again, moving from left to right) edge that is labelled by an indeterminate. WLOG, assume that this edge belongs to path P_2 , and it is labelled by x_2 . Also, let j and $j + 1$ denote the indices of the layers containing the tail and head of this edge respectively. Assume that this edge is directed from top level of layer j to top level of layer $j + 1$ (see Figure 42); the cases corresponding to the other three orientations of this edge can be analyzed in a similar way.

Figure 42

Consider the following two cases:

Case 1: $j \neq i$

First, we show that the edge of P_1 from layer $j-1$ to layer j must have its head at the bottom level of layer j . Suppose not. Then, concatenating P_1 's portion from layers $\leq j$ (shown in purple in Figure 43) with P_2 's portion from layers $\geq j$ (shown in red in Figure 43) gives a new path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ that contains both x_1 and x_2 , which is impossible due to Lemma 10.

Figure 43

Next, consider the edge of P_1 from layer j to layer $j+1$. Its tail is same as the head of the edge of P_1 from layer $j-1$ to layer j (which, as argued above, is at the bottom level of layer j). We show that the head of this edge must be at the bottom level of layer $j+1$. Suppose not. Then, observe that y_2 appears at least once in P_2 's portion from layers $\geq j+1$. So, concatenating P_1 's portion from layers $\leq j+1$ (shown in purple in Figure 44) with P_2 's

portion from layers $\geq j+1$ (shown in red in Figure 44) gives a new path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ that contains both x_1 and y_2 , which is impossible due to Lemma 10.

Figure 44

Now, consider the edge of P_3 from layer j to layer $j+1$. This edge must be different from the edge joining the top level of layer j to the top level of layer $j+1$; this is because the latter edge is labelled with x_2 , which does not belong to P_3 . Also, we show that this edge cannot be directed from bottom level of layer j to top level of layer $j+1$. Suppose not. Then, observe that at least one of x_3 and y_3 appears at least once in P_3 's portion from layers $\geq j+1$. So, concatenating P_2 's portion from layers $\leq j+1$ (shown in red in Figure 45) with P_3 's portion from layers $\geq j+1$ (shown in blue in Figure 45) gives a new path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ that contains both x_2 and x_3 (or y_3), which is not possible due to Lemma 10.

Figure 45

Thus, the edge of P_3 from layer j to layer $j+1$ must have its head at the bottom level of layer $j+1$. Also, as proved earlier, the edge of P_1 from layer j to layer $j+1$ has its head at the bottom level of layer $j+1$. Therefore, concatenating P_1 's portion from layers $\leq j+1$ (shown

in purple in Figure 46) with P_3 's portion from layers $\geq j + 1$ (shown in blue in Figure 46) gives a new path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$. Also, this path contains both x_1 and x_3 (or y_3) because at least one of x_3 and y_3 appears at least once in P_3 's portion from layers $\geq j + 1$. However, this is not possible due to Lemma 10.

Figure 46

Case 2: $j = i$

First, we show that the edge of P_1 from layer i to layer $i + 1$ must have its head at the bottom level of layer $i + 1$. Suppose not. Then, observe that y_2 appears at least once in P_2 's portion from layers $\geq i + 1$. So, concatenating P_1 's portion from layers $\leq i + 1$ (shown in purple in Figure 47) with P_2 's portion from layers $\geq i + 1$ (shown in red in Figure 47) gives a new path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$ that contains both x_1 and y_2 , which is impossible due to Lemma 10.

Figure 47

Also, using the same reasoning as in Case 1, we know that the edge of P_3 from layer j (same as layer i here) must have its head at the bottom level of layer $j + 1$ (same as layer $i + 1$ here). Therefore, concatenating P_1 's portion from layers $\leq i + 1$ (shown in purple in Figure 48) with

P_3 's portion from layers $\geq i + 1$ (shown in blue in Figure 48) gives a new path in $\mathcal{P}(\Gamma)$. Also, this path contains both x_1 and x_3 (or y_3) because at least one of x_3 and y_3 appears at least once in P_3 's portion from layers $\geq i + 1$. However, this is not possible due to Lemma 10.

Figure 48

This proves Theorem 26. □

Universality of Width-3 ABPs over R and N

Theorem 27. *Let p be a polynomial of degree d and sparsity s over R or N . Then, there is a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(d \cdot s)$ 3-by-3 matrices that computes p .*

Proof. Define $P(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$ and $Q(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & 0 & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$. Let m_1, \dots, m_s denote

the monomials of p . Consider any $1 \leq i \leq s$. Repeatedly use $P(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} x & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix} =$

$P(f \otimes x)$ to get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(d)$ matrices that computes $P(m_i)$. Then, convert it to $Q(m_i)$

using $P(m_i) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \end{pmatrix} = Q(m_i)$. Finally, repeatedly use $Q(f) \otimes Q(\infty) \otimes Q(g) =$

$Q(f \oplus g)$ to get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(d \cdot s)$ matrices that computes $Q(m_1 \oplus \dots \oplus m_s)$. This proves Theorem 27. □

Computing Univariate Polynomials using Width-3 ABPs over R

Theorem 28. *Let $p = a_d \otimes x^{\otimes d} \oplus a_{d-1} \otimes x^{\otimes(d-1)} \oplus \dots \oplus a_1 \otimes x \oplus a_0$ be a degree d univariate polynomial over R . Then, there is a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(d)$ 3-by-3 matrices that computes p .*

Proof. Define $P(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$. First, we show how to get $P(f \oplus a \otimes x \oplus b)$ from $P(f)$,

where a and b are constants: If $a = \infty$, use $P(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ b & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix} = P(f \oplus b)$; otherwise,

$$\text{use } P(f) \otimes \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & a \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ x & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & -a \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ b & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix}}_{\begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty \\ a \otimes x \oplus b & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix}}$$

$$= P(f \oplus a \otimes x \oplus b).$$

Using Horner's rule (see [81]), we express p as follows:

$$\dots ((a_d \otimes x^{\otimes 2} \oplus a_{d-1} \otimes x \oplus a_{d-2}) \otimes x^{\otimes 2} \oplus a_{d-3} \otimes x \oplus a_{d-4}) \otimes x^{\otimes 2} + \dots$$

Now, we repeatedly use the $P(f)$ -to- $P(f \otimes x)$ conversion (described in the proof of Theorem 27) and the $P(f)$ -to- $P(f \oplus a \otimes x \oplus b)$ conversion described above as follows: Starting from $P(a_d)$, use $P(f)$ -to- $P(f \otimes x)$ conversion twice to get $P(a_d \otimes x^{\otimes 2})$. Then, use $P(f)$ -to- $P(f \oplus a \otimes x \oplus b)$ conversion (with $a = a_{d-1}$ and $b = a_{d-2}$) to get $P(a_d \otimes x^{\otimes 2} \oplus a_{d-1} \otimes x \oplus a_{d-2})$. Next, use $P(f)$ -to- $P(f \otimes x)$ conversion twice to get $P((a_d \otimes x^{\otimes 2} \oplus a_{d-1} \otimes x \oplus a_{d-2}) \otimes x^{\otimes 2})$. Again, use $P(f)$ -to- $P(f \oplus a \otimes x \oplus b)$ conversion (with $a = a_{d-3}$ and $b = a_{d-4}$) to get $P((a_d \otimes x^{\otimes 2} \oplus a_{d-1} \otimes x \oplus a_{d-2}) \otimes x^{\otimes 2} \oplus a_{d-3} \otimes x \oplus a_{d-4})$. This continues in a similar manner. Finally, we get a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(d)$ matrices that computes $P(p)$. This proves Theorem 28. \square

Remark 2. In this thesis, we allow only indeterminates and constants to be edge labels of ABPs; these are referred to as weakest ABPs. A stronger model of ABPs is where linear forms in an indeterminate are also allowed to be edge labels; these are referred to as weak ABPs. Any univariate polynomial of degree d over R can be written as a product of linear factors (see [74]) and so, it can be computed using an $\mathcal{O}(d)$ -sized weak width-1 ABP.

Simulating $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma$ Circuits using Width-4 ABPs over R and N

Theorem 29. Let C be a $\Sigma^{(s_3)}\Pi^{(s_2)}\Sigma^{(s_1)}$ circuit¹⁸ over R or N (see Figure 49). Then, there is a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(s_1s_2s_3)$ 4-by-4 matrices that computes the polynomial computed by C .

$$\text{Proof. Let } P(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}, Q(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}, T(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}.$$

First, consider any Level 1 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1)$ -sized sequence that computes its

$$\text{output in } T \text{ format by repeatedly using } T(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ x & \infty & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix} = T(f \oplus x). \text{ Next,}$$

consider any Level 2 Π gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1s_2)$ -sized sequence that computes its output

¹⁸The superscripts indicate fan-in's.

Figure 49: Depth-three $\Sigma^{(s_3)}\Pi^{(s_2)}\Sigma^{(s_1)}$ circuit in Theorem 29.

in P format by repeatedly using $P(f) \otimes T(g) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = P(f \otimes g)$. Then, we

convert this output into Q format by using $P(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = Q(f)$. Finally, con-

sider the Level 3 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1 s_2 s_3)$ -sized sequence that computes its output in Q format by repeatedly using $Q(f) \otimes Q(\infty) \otimes Q(g) = Q(f \oplus g)$. This proves Theorem 29. \square

Simulating $\Sigma\Pi\Sigma\Pi$ Circuits using Width-5 ABPs over N

Theorem 30. Let C be a $\Sigma^{(s_4)}\Pi^{(s_3)}\Sigma^{(s_2)}\Pi^{(s_1)}$ circuit over N (see Figure 50). Then, there is a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4)$ 5-by-5 matrices that computes the polynomial computed by C .

Proof. Let $P(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$, $Q(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$, $T(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$,

$A(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$. Note that $A(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} x & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f \otimes x & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \otimes x \oplus 0 \otimes 0 \\ = 0 \oplus x \end{matrix} & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$.

Since we are working over N , we have $x \geq 0$. So, $0 \oplus x$ (i.e., $\min\{0, x\}$) is 0 and thus, RHS is $A(f \otimes x)$. We repeatedly use this $A(f)$ -to- $A(f \otimes x)$ conversion to get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1)$ -sized sequence that computes the output of any Level 1 Π gate of C in A format. Next, consider any Level 2 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1 s_2)$ -sized sequence that computes its output in T format by

Figure 50: Depth-four $\Sigma^{(s_4)} \Pi^{(s_3)} \Sigma^{(s_2)} \Pi^{(s_1)}$ circuit in Theorem 30.

repeatedly using $T(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} \otimes A(g) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = T(f \oplus g).$

Next, consider any Level 3 Π gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1 s_2 s_3)$ -sized sequence that computes

its output in P format by repeatedly using $P(f) \otimes T(g) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = P(f \otimes g).$

Then, we convert this output from P format to Q format using $P(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$

$= Q(f)$. Finally, consider the Level 4 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4)$ -sized sequence that computes its output in Q format by repeatedly using $Q(f) \otimes Q(\infty) \otimes Q(g) = Q(f \oplus g)$. This proves Theorem 30. \square

Simulating $\Sigma \Pi \Sigma \Pi \Sigma$ Circuits using Width-6 ABPs over N

Theorem 31. *Let C be a $\Sigma^{(s_5)} \Pi^{(s_4)} \Sigma^{(s_3)} \Pi^{(s_2)} \Sigma^{(s_1)}$ circuit over N (see Figure 51). Then, there is a sequence of $\mathcal{O}(s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4 s_5)$ 6-by-6 matrices that computes the polynomial computed by C .*

Figure 51: Depth-five $\Sigma^{(s_5)} \Pi^{(s_4)} \Sigma^{(s_3)} \Pi^{(s_2)} \Sigma^{(s_1)}$ circuit in Theorem 31.

Proof. Let $P(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$, $Q(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$,

$$A(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}, T(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}, B(f) := \begin{pmatrix} f & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}.$$

First, consider any Level 1 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1)$ -sized sequence that computes its

output in B format by repeatedly using $B(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ x & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 \end{pmatrix} = B(f \oplus x)$. Note

that $A(f) \otimes B(g) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} f \otimes g & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 \otimes g \oplus 0 \otimes 0 \\ = 0 \oplus g & \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix}$. Since we

are working over N , we have $g \geq 0$. So, $0 \oplus g$ (i.e., $\min\{0, g\}$) is 0 and thus, RHS is $A(f \otimes g)$. We repeatedly use this $A(f)$ -and- $B(g)$ -to- $A(f \otimes g)$ conversion to get an

$\mathcal{O}(s_1s_2)$ -sized sequence that computes the output of any Level 2 Π gate of C in A format. Next, consider any Level 3 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1s_2s_3)$ -sized sequence that com-

putes its output in T format by repeatedly using $T(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} \otimes A(g) \otimes$

$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = T(f \oplus g)$. Next, consider any Level 4 Π gate in C . We get

an $\mathcal{O}(s_1s_2s_3s_4)$ -sized sequence that computes its output in P format by repeatedly using $P(f) \otimes T(g) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = P(f \otimes g)$. Then, we convert this output from

P format to Q format using $P(f) \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & 0 & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \\ \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty & \infty \end{pmatrix} = Q(f)$. Finally, consider the

Level 5 Σ gate in C . We get an $\mathcal{O}(s_1s_2s_3s_4s_5)$ -sized sequence that computes its output in Q format by repeatedly using $Q(f) \otimes Q(\infty) \otimes Q(g) = Q(f \oplus g)$. This proves Theorem 31. \square

Directions for Future Work.

The questions that i) whether width-3 ABPs can efficiently simulate formulas (i.e., $VF \subseteq VBP_3$) over R and N , and ii) whether width-2 ABPs are non-universal over N , remain open.

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